

icosHELLS

**D1.1 STAKEHOLDER
MAPPING AND
BASELINE ANALYSIS
OF LOCAL
ECOSYSTEMS**

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Executive Summary

Soil degradation poses critical challenges to environmental health, food security, and economic stability, with global impacts including reduced agricultural productivity, water contamination, and biodiversity loss. The iCOSHELLS project, funded under the EU Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe,” supports the establishment of six Soil Health Living Labs across Europe to develop scalable and sustainable soil health solutions and advance EU soil health objectives. The Living Labs place an emphasis on stakeholder engagement and co-creation, ensuring solutions are scientifically robust, locally relevant, and socially accepted.

This report outlines the stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis conducted within the iCOSHELLS project to support effective multi-stakeholder engagement and co-creation in the Living Labs. The analyses focus on the six Living Lab locations within the iCOSHELLS project to analyse the stakeholder landscapes and baseline conditions as of October 2024. The report targets project partners, Mission soil stakeholders, and the global soil health community. It provides open-access data and recommendations for stakeholder engagement and co-creation.

The stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative ratings with qualitative survey questions. Stakeholders were identified, categorised, and evaluated using a Power/Interest Matrix. The baseline analysis applied a PESTLE framework to examine the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental factors in each Living Lab.

The report presents the analyses for each iCOSHELLS Living Lab, offering detailed insights into the stakeholder map, local PESTLE baseline dynamics, and their implications for stakeholder engagement and co-creation. Analyses and their implications are presented separately for each Living Lab.

The Basque Living Lab in the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve benefits from strong political support, advanced technologies and community engagement for soil health management, but also faces some challenges such as inconsistent enforcement and balancing development and conservation. The region's rich biodiversity, strong governance, and existing stakeholder engagement channels provide a strong foundation for the Living Lab.

The Bulgarian Living Lab has a solid foundation for improving soil health, with strong political and economic support, a well-established regulatory framework, and growing adoption of sustainable practices and digital technologies. However, challenges such as slow adoption of sustainable practices by farmers, rural depopulation and climate change impacts threaten soil quality and need to be addressed. Success will depend on filling knowledge gaps, improving technology uptake and balancing environmental sustainability with economic viability.

The Greek Mining Soil Living Lab area in Western Macedonia is undergoing a critical transition from lignite mining to sustainable development, facing challenges such as soil degradation, job losses and regulatory inefficiencies. Supported by EU funding and advanced soil remediation technologies, the region has the opportunity to restore ecosystems, diversify its economy and build community resilience. Success will require coordinated efforts to balance economic, social and environmental priorities, while responding to local needs and making effective use of available resources.

Soil health in the Northern Italy Living Lab region shows strong political support and economic potential for sustainable agriculture, but implementation is hampered by regulatory complexity, fragmented governance and limited uptake of advanced technologies, while economic pressures and high crop specialisation threaten agricultural sustainability. Social commitment is strong, although knowledge gaps remain among non-professional farmers. Opportunities exist for improved carbon storage, water management and sustainable farming practices, highlighting the need for education and increased technology adoption.

The GreennoMed Living Lab ecosystem in south-eastern Spain faces significant environmental degradation, particularly in the Mar Menor lagoon, due to conflicts between agricultural practices and environmental protection, despite existing legislation and community support. Inadequate pollution control and water management infrastructure is hampering progress, despite advanced monitoring technologies. However, harnessing community engagement and technological capacity offers the potential for sustainable coastal management through improved stakeholder coordination and integrated environmental strategies.

The Swedish Soil Health Living Lab tackles soil health challenges, including compaction, poor structure, reduced biodiversity, and nutrient imbalances like phosphorus deficiency. The analysis highlights strong political and civil society support, but economic and technological hurdles remain. Climate change and implementation gaps pose additional threats, making stakeholder engagement and inclusiveness vital for sustainable solutions. Addressing economic disparities among farms will be also essential for long-term success.

The findings of this report lay the foundation for the development of strategies for stakeholder engagement and co-creation, ensuring tailored approaches to address soil health challenges and opportunities across the Living Labs. Recommendations included in this report will be discussed with the lead partners of the iCOSHELLS Living Labs to finetune the Living Labs' methodologies, building on current developments and ideas. The resulting governance framework for the co-creation sessions in the Living Labs will be presented in a separate report (D1.2).

Introduction

Setting the Scene: Soil Health and Soil Living Labs

Soil Health Challenges

Soil degradation presents a severe threat to global environmental health, human well-being, and economic stability (Sprunger, 2023). It undermines essential soil functions such as food production, water regulation, and biodiversity conservation, impacting both ecosystems and human life (UNCCD, 2019). Reduced agricultural productivity is a direct consequence (FAO, n.d.), leading to lower crop yields, threatening food security, and impacting farmers' livelihoods, especially in developing nations (Mirzabaev et al., 2023). This decline stems from nutrient depletion, erosion, and structural changes hindering plant growth (Tan et al., 2005; Pozza & Field, 2020). The economic fallout can be substantial, affecting food supply chains and potentially driving up food prices (Mirzabaev et al., 2023). Furthermore, degraded soil is more vulnerable to erosion, leading to topsoil loss (Eurostat, 2020) and water contamination, posing risks to both aquatic ecosystems (Olsson et al., 2019) and human health through polluted drinking water sources (Rashmi et al., 2022).

The human health implications of soil degradation are also significant (Brevik & Burgess, 2014). Contamination of food crops with heavy metals, pesticides, and other harmful substances threatens food safety, particularly for vulnerable populations reliant on subsistence agriculture (European Environment Agency, 2022). This contamination, coupled with reduced yields, exacerbates food insecurity, creating a cycle of poverty and ill health (HLPE, 2023). The economic costs are substantial (Görlach et al., 2004), impacting farmers' incomes, disrupting food markets, and incurring high rehabilitation costs, often with limited success in restoring full productivity (Crossman et al., 2016). This economic burden hinders sustainable development (Mirzabaev et al., 2023). The importance of healthy soil is underscored by its role in food production: Terrestrial plants, which rely on healthy soil, provide an estimated 82% of the calories in the human food supply, while terrestrial animals contribute approximately 16% (FAO, 2019). In the EU, soil supports 90% of all food, feed, fibre, and fuel production and harbours over 25% of all biodiversity (European Environment Agency, 2023).

Soil Health in the European Union

The European Union faces a serious soil health crisis, with 70% of soils in an unhealthy condition (Panagos et al., 2022) and 2.8 million potentially contaminated sites (Viera et al., 2024). The problems are widespread and complex: 83% of agricultural soils contain pesticide residues, 51% show mercury deposition, and 65–75% are at risk of eutrophication from excessive nutrients (European Commission, n.d.). Annual soil erosion totals approximately 1 billion tonnes (Akca et al., 2024), while unsustainable urban development continues to seal over more land (European Environment Agency, 2008). Land degradation is particularly severe in southern, central, and eastern Europe, where the risk of desertification increased by 11% in just a decade (Vermann et al., 2020). The economic impact is significant, with soil degradation costing the EU over €50 billion annually, although EU croplands and grasslands still provide €76 billion yearly in ecosystem services (European Commission, 2021).

Soil Strategy 2030

Launched in response to escalating threats to soil health, the EU Soil Strategy 2030 (European Commission, 2021) sets the ambitious goal of achieving healthy and sustainably used soils by 2050. This strategy is deeply integrated into the broader European Green Deal and the EU Biodiversity Strategy, emphasising the interconnectedness of environmental challenges. To achieve its goals, the strategy outlines several key actions. First, it proposes specific legislation for soil health, providing a legal framework for its protection and sustainable management. Second, it aims to promote sustainable soil management practices on the ground by offering free soil testing to landowners, enabling them to make informed decisions about their land. Third, it prioritises the protection of vital ecosystems such as wetlands and organic soils, recognising their crucial role in maintaining overall soil health. Fourth, the strategy introduces the concept of 'soil passports' to facilitate the safe and responsible reuse of clean soil, promoting circularity and minimising waste. Finally, it highlights the importance of ongoing research and monitoring efforts to deepen our understanding of soil health and to track progress towards the 2050 target. Crucially, the strategy recognises that the success of these actions depends on effective collaboration between different stakeholders, including landowners, policy makers, researchers and industry.

A Soil Deal for Europe

The European Mission Soil, officially known as "A Soil Deal for Europe", part of Horizon Europe, complements these efforts by establishing 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses by 2030 (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2023). This mission focuses on eight key objectives (European Commission. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, n.d.): reducing desertification; maintaining soil organic carbon stocks; preventing soil sealing; reducing pollution; preventing erosion; improving soil biodiversity; reducing the EU's global soil footprint; and enhancing soil literacy within society. The programme emphasises research, innovation, and public awareness through an ambitious research agenda with a strong social science component. Living Labs serve as real-world testing grounds where researchers, farmers, industry representatives, and other stakeholders collaborate to develop and validate innovative soil management practices. Lighthouses act as exemplary sites demonstrating successful implementations of sustainable soil management solutions, serving as beacons of best practice for others to follow. By developing a harmonised framework for soil monitoring across Europe, the initiative aims to create standardised methods for assessing soil health and tracking progress.

Soil Health Living Labs and Lighthouses

Living Labs and Lighthouses represent two complementary approaches in the EU's soil health initiative. Living Labs function as collaborative research ecosystems where farmers, scientists, citizens, businesses and local authorities work together to develop and test innovative soil health practices in real-world conditions. These transdisciplinary hubs coordinate multiple trial sites and emphasise user-centred solutions tailored to local challenges. Lighthouses, in contrast, are individual exemplary sites (such as farms, forests, industrial sites or urban green spaces) that demonstrate successful soil management practices and serve as educational centres. While Living Labs focus on innovation and development through multiple stakeholder collaboration, Lighthouses showcase proven solutions and act as training and communication hubs to promote wider adoption of sustainable soil management practices. Though distinct in their functions, both initiatives can work together, with Lighthouses either operating independently or being integrated into Living Labs, ultimately serving the common goal of advancing sustainable soil management across Europe (European Commission, n.d.; 2022).

iCOSHELLS

The iCOSHELLS Project

The pan-European project iCOSHELLS (innovative **CO**-creation for **Soil HE**alth in **Living Labs**), funded under the EU Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe', contributes to the establishment of 100 Soil Health Living Labs and Lighthouses by 2030. The project will establish six Living Labs on Soil Health across Europe. The Living Labs contribute to the EU soil health objectives, particularly reducing soil pollution and enhancing restoration (objective 4), improving soil structure to support biodiversity (objective 6), and promoting soil literacy in society (objective 8). Each Living Lab is anchored in a specific geographical context, recognising that soil health challenges vary greatly depending on location, climate, land use and historical factors. This place-based approach enables the development of tailored solutions that are more likely to be effective and accepted by local communities (see overview of Living Labs in Table 1). Within the Living Labs, iCOSHELLS partners will further develop and test innovative technologies and approaches such as remote sensing, precision farming, experimental crop trials and nature-based solutions. Robust ecological monitoring systems track the impact of the interventions and allow for continuous learning and adaptation. The project facilitates knowledge sharing and cross-fertilisation between the different Living Labs and Lighthouses. This will enable the replication and up-scaling of successful solutions across the European Union.

A core characteristic of the iCOSHELLS project is its commitment to stakeholder engagement and co-creation, ensuring that not only the technical aspects of soil remediation, but also social, economic, and environmental factors are addressed. By involving diverse stakeholders, including research institutions, farmers, local communities, educators, public authorities, and small and medium-sized enterprises, in the design and implementation of solutions, iCOSHELLS aims to foster a strong sense of ownership and responsibility. This inclusive approach not only considers various perspectives but also ensures that the solutions developed are scientifically sound, practically feasible, and responsive to political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental factors influencing soil management. In doing so, iCOSHELLS strives to create interventions that are sustainable and impactful in the long term.

iCOSHELLS' Multi-Stakeholder Approach

The iCOSHELLS project employs a multi-layered, multi-stakeholder approach that actively engages relevant stakeholders across several levels:

1. Within each Living Lab, a diverse group of stakeholders will collaborate to shape the soil health solutions that will be tested. These stakeholders will co-develop, evaluate, and help adapt solutions over three planned test iterations across three years. To support this collaborative process, eight co-creation sessions are planned for each Living Lab, ensuring consistent engagement and feedback.
2. Community engagement activities, such as pop-up exhibitions, are designed to foster transparency and inclusivity by keeping the local community informed and providing opportunities for community input.
3. Additional communication efforts will be directed at other interested stakeholders, tailoring messages to local contexts and selecting appropriate communication channels to ensure effective outreach.
4. Each Living Lab benefits from the involvement of consortium partners who represent various stakeholder groups and bring established local networks and engagement channels. These existing networks will be leveraged to further enhance multi-stakeholder participation in the Living Labs.

The stakeholder landscape in soil health initiatives is broad and complex, encompassing economic, environmental, legal, political, social, and technological dimensions. At the core are agricultural producers, cooperatives, and suppliers, who drive the economic aspects of soil management. Environmental stakeholders, including NGOs and advocates for sustainable practices, emphasise the importance of ecological sustainability in soil health. Critical actors, such as research institutions and technical experts, contribute scientific insights and advanced solutions, while government bodies at various levels provide essential policies and regulatory frameworks. Consumer and agricultural organisations represent social dimensions, advocating for the interests of those impacted by soil health. Additionally, water management service providers, soil analysts, and technology providers supply the necessary infrastructure and tools to improve soil management practices.

To ensure that the iCOSHELLS stakeholder engagement and co-creation activities are effectively tailored to each Living Lab’s location and local needs, a comprehensive stakeholder mapping exercise was conducted at the project’s outset. This mapping identified, assessed, and categorised the different groups involved. Additionally, understanding the political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental (PESTLE) factors shaping each Living Lab setting was essential for contextualizing stakeholders’ perspectives. These analyses of stakeholder mapping and PESTLE factors are presented in this report.

Table 1. Overview of the iCOSHELLS Living Labs

Name	Location	Land use	Soil Health Challenges include...
Basque UrbanSoils Living Lab	Basque country, Northern Spain/ Southern France, particularly Biosphere Reserve of Urdaibai	Urban areas, interspersed with wetlands and wooded areas	Flooding, erosion, pollution, poor soil structure, and the impacts of climate change.
Bulgarian Viticultural Soil Health Living Lab	Thracian Valley in Plovdiv Province, Southern Bulgaria	Mainly agricultural land use, focus on grape and wine production	Need to enhance the resilience and mitigate the vulnerabilities of vineyard soils in context of climate change
Greek Mining Soil Living Lab	Western Macedonia Region in Northern Greece	Post-lignite mining areas	Soil restoration and reclamation of mining sites, particularly with high chromium and nickel levels
Italian Soil Health Living Lab	rural, urban and peri-urban areas along the contiguous Aige and Po Valleys	Mixed: Agricultural land use, orchard, and urban land use	Soil carbon loss, urban soil sealing and pollution, poor soil structure, and loss of soil biodiversity
Spanish GreennoMed Living Lab	Campo de Cartagena (Region of Murcia) and Almería in Spain	Agricultural land use	Soil health degradation, impacting ecosystem resilience and sustainable agriculture
Swedish AgroSoils Living Lab	farm network in Southern Sweden and some places in Mid and Northern regions	Agricultural land use (crop and animal production)	Soil compaction, poor soil structure, reduced biodiversity, and nutrient imbalances

Purpose, Scope, and Target Group of this Report

Purpose of stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis

Stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis serve as essential foundational steps for successful multi-stakeholder engagement and co-creation within the iCOSHELLS six Living Labs.

Stakeholder mapping is particularly crucial for iCOSHELLS given its wide-ranging stakeholder landscape, spanning from farmers and civil society organisations to economic entities and public authorities. This systematic process helps identify and categorise all relevant actors for each of the project's six geographically distinct Living Labs, from Sweden to Greece, and from Bulgaria to Spain. By understanding stakeholders' interests, challenges, and influence, the project can effectively foster the collaboration necessary for co-creating sustainable soil management solutions that are both scientifically sound and practically feasible.

The baseline analysis complements stakeholder mapping by providing a detailed understanding of the current situation in each Living Lab's context. This is essential because iCOSHELLS recognises that soil health challenges vary significantly based on location, climate, land use and historical factors. The baseline analysis helps identify specific needs and challenges in each region, ensuring that these are considered when co-creating solutions to achieve soil health objectives.

Together, these methods support iCOSHELLS' emphasis on stakeholder engagement and co-creation by:

- Enabling targeted engagement strategies for different stakeholder groups
- Identifying existing networks that can be leveraged
- Understanding local contexts and specific soil health challenges
- Supporting the development of region-specific solutions
- Facilitating knowledge sharing between Living Labs

This systematic approach to stakeholder engagement and context analysis directly supports iCOSHELLS' goal of developing effective, locally-accepted solutions that can be replicated and scaled across the European Union.

Scope of the Stakeholder Mapping and Baseline Analysis

This report presents the stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis conducted within the iCOSHELLS project, with a defined scope limited by geography, content, and timeframe.

- **Geographically**, the analysis focuses specifically on the six Living Lab locations within the iCOSHELLS project. Each Living Lab is examined as a separate entity. While it is acknowledged that factors and stakeholders outside each Living Lab location influence soil health and project activities within the Living Lab location, only those deemed relevant by Living Lab leads are considered within this report, and no comprehensive data on external influences were collected outside of the Living Lab contexts.
- **Content-wise**, the analysis follows a PESTLE framework, addressing political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental factors and stakeholders related to soil health. All identified stakeholders in the

stakeholder mapping could be categorised to these six dimensions. Within the baseline analysis, the focus is on understanding how these PESTLE factors impact soil health and, conversely, how soil health initiatives, such as those undertaken by iCOSHells, affect PESTLE factors.

- **Time-wise**, the report reflects the status quo at the time of data collection in October 2024. While some historical dimensions are incorporated, particularly where they were deemed relevant by Living Lab leads, a comprehensive historical analysis was not within the scope of this report.

Target Group of the Report

This report is aimed at stakeholders investing in soil health across Europe and globally, with detailed analysis focused on six European regions. The report's target audience comprises three interrelated groups:

The project consortium represents the primary target group, consisting of core partners directly implementing project activities, research institutions, organisations providing expertise and Living Lab participants. These stakeholders will benefit from direct access to the results of the stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis.

The Soil Deal for Europe Mission stakeholders are the second target group, including European Mission Soil partners working towards 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses by 2030, related soil health initiatives and their participants, and policy implementation bodies. These stakeholders will benefit from regional data to inform policy decisions, methodological frameworks for (PESTLE) soil health assessment, insights from six regional case studies, and opportunities for integration with existing soil health programmes.

The wider global soil health community includes agricultural practitioners, land managers, environmental researchers, academics, policy makers, government agencies, NGOs, civil society organisations and industry stakeholders. This diverse group will benefit from access to open-source research data, practical insights from regional analysis and evidence-based recommendations. The results of this report can also create opportunities for networking and knowledge exchange, and potentially scalable solutions in different contexts.

Methodology

The following sections outline the methodology applied in the stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis for the iCOSHells project. Stakeholder mapping was conducted to identify, assess, and categorise key actors in soil health within the Living Labs (LL) framework, following a structured approach based on Enserink et al. (2022). The baseline analysis aims to better understand the strengths, weaknesses, risks, and opportunities within each Living Lab's unique political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental context.

Stakeholder Mapping

Data Collection

In October 2024, a comprehensive data collection effort was initiated through the development and distribution of a Microsoft Excel-based survey to Living Lab (LL) partners within the iCOSHells project consortium. This survey was specifically designed to gather detailed information on stakeholders, aiming to capture data for at least 60 stakeholders per LL location across a broad spectrum of categories based on the Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, and Environmental (PESTLE) framework. The survey was divided into four key sections to ensure a thorough understanding of the stakeholders and their engagement with soil health initiatives.

The first section, titled “**Basic Information**”, aimed to collect fundamental details about the stakeholders. This included the location of the Living Lab, the respondent’s details, and the organisation of the stakeholder involved. Additionally, the context of the professional relationship between the respondent and the stakeholder was recorded, along with the organisation's website or the LinkedIn profile of the contact person. These details were critical for understanding the background and connection of each stakeholder to the LL framework.

The “**Organisational Profile**” section followed, where stakeholders were classified according to the PESTLE categories to better understand their organisational focus and operations. This section gathered insights into the primary activities and responsibilities of the stakeholder's organisation, particularly their current engagement with soil health initiatives. This information is vital to assessing the role that each organisation plays in the broader context of soil health and sustainable land management.

The third section, “**Soil Health Perspectives**”, focused on understanding how stakeholders align with the objectives of the iCOSHells project. This section also delved into the perceived barriers and challenges that stakeholders face in promoting soil health, as well as the opportunities they see arising from effective soil management practices. The goal was to identify not only the difficulties encountered but also the potential for advancement and innovation in soil health practices.

Lastly, the “**Stakeholder Assessment**” section provided a more detailed evaluation of each stakeholder's influence and involvement in soil health activities. This section evaluated four main criteria: i) **Power**, which measures the stakeholder's ability to influence soil health outcomes; ii) **Interest**, which assesses their level of concern or active involvement in soil health issues; iii) **Impact**, which gauges the extent to which the stakeholder is

affected by the outcomes of the LL activities; iv) and **Importance**, which reflects the significance of the stakeholder's role within the LL framework. Each of these criteria was rated on a 0–4 scale, with qualitative explanations accompanying each rating to provide additional context and clarity.

Please refer to the complete survey template in the Appendix ([Annex I](#)), which provides a screenshot of the Microsoft Excel questionnaire used for data collection.

Applied Analytical Methods

The collected data from the survey underwent a thorough analysis process that combined both quantitative and qualitative methods to extract actionable insights that could guide the development of stakeholder engagement plans.

The analysis aimed to not only quantify stakeholder data but also capture the underlying perspectives, challenges, and opportunities related to soil health, ensuring a comprehensive approach to understanding the stakeholder landscape.

One of the key methods employed in the analysis was stakeholder clustering/mapping, which played a critical role in the overall stakeholder mapping process. A fundamental aspect of this approach was the qualitative analysis, which aimed to uncover the challenges, motivations, and interests of individual stakeholders. This step helped identify common themes among stakeholders, allowing for the formation of clusters based on shared challenges or goals. The qualitative data was gathered through the open-ended questions in the stakeholder survey. Based on the insights gained from this analysis, a map was created for each Living Lab, illustrating the influence of different actor groups and the relationships between them. By clustering stakeholders in this way, clear visualisations were developed to represent the interdependencies between various groups. These visual tools were invaluable for gaining a deeper understanding of the dynamics at play, highlighting areas where stakeholders could potentially collaborate or where conflicts might arise.

In addition to clustering, the analysis comprised of additional two components, an interdependency table and a power-interest matrix. This matrix was a key tool for categorizing stakeholders based on two critical dimensions: **power**, which refers to a stakeholder's ability to influence the outcomes of the Living Lab activities, and **level of interest**, which denotes their level of concern or active involvement in the iCOSHells project. The creation of this matrix was essential for providing strategic insights into how to manage and engage stakeholders effectively. Precisely, the Power/Interest Matrix divided stakeholders into four distinct quadrants, each with its own engagement strategy:

Image Source: Enserink et al. (2022, p.99)

Figure 1: Basque Living Lab - Power/Interest Matrix

- **Key Players (High Power/High Interest):** These stakeholders are actively involved in decision-making processes and have a significant influence on the project. It is crucial to maintain close, consistent communication with them and involve them in key discussions and decisions.
- **Context Setters (High Power/Low Interest):** Stakeholders in this category hold significant power but may not be as directly interested or involved in the day-to-day activities. They require regular updates to keep them informed, and their concerns should be addressed to maintain a positive relationship, even if they are not actively engaged.
- **Subjects (Low Power/High Interest):** These stakeholders may not have the power to influence the outcomes significantly but are highly interested in the project. It is important to keep them informed, engage them on specific topics of concern, and ensure that their views are considered in decision-making processes.
- **Crowd (Low Power/Low Interest):** Stakeholders in this category have both low power and low interest. While their involvement may be minimal, it is still important to monitor their perspectives to ensure they do not become disengaged or discontented, which could affect the project in the long run.

The approach facilitates resource allocation by identifying stakeholders with both high power and high interest. This ensures that resources will be directed efficiently towards those stakeholders who have the ability to significantly influence the project and are deeply invested in its success, maximising the impact of engagement efforts. The tools also prove essential for communication planning. By mapping stakeholders according to their levels of power and interest, the matrix will enable the development of communication strategies that is both targeted and appropriate. This allows the involved partners to adjust their communication style and frequency, ensuring that each stakeholder group receives the necessary attention and the most relevant information, thereby fostering more effective interactions. In terms of risk management, the tool helps to pinpoint potential conflicts, particularly with stakeholders who have high power but possibly conflicting priorities or concerns. By identifying these risks early on, the project partners will be able to implement proactive measures to address them, minimising disruptions and ensuring smoother cooperation as the project progressed.

In addition, the interdependency table of Enserink et al. (2022) complemented the power-interest matrix by providing a deeper understanding of the relationships between stakeholders. While the power-interest matrix groups stakeholders based on their influence and interest in the project, the interdependency table focuses on the connections and dependencies between them. Thus, the table has helped to highlight how stakeholders' actions and outcomes influence one another, capturing dynamics that might be overlooked in the power-interest matrix. When inconsistencies between the two methods were identified, the rankings for power and interest were reviewed and adjusted to ensure accuracy. Additionally, this combined analysis emphasised inclusivity, considering stakeholders with low power but high impact, affected by project outcomes.

The applied analytical tools are essential for shaping the Living Labs' co-creation stakeholder engagement activities later on, combining quantitative insights with valuable qualitative depth. By synthesising stakeholder perspectives on soil health barriers and opportunities, the analyses revealed key areas for concern and innovation.

Baseline Analysis

Data Collection

A survey was developed to collect in-depth insights into the local ecosystems of the six iCOSHELLS Living Labs. Following a PESTLE approach, the survey examined political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental aspects (see Table 2 for further definitions). The PESTLE framework is a strategic analysis tool that assesses the external factors affecting an organisation or project (DuCoin & Kuo, 2024). This systematic approach helps to identify and assess potential risks and opportunities in the operating environment, enabling informed decision-making and strategic planning. The PESTLE analysis enhances understanding of relevant external forces that should be considered in addressing soil health in the Living Lab locations. It enables to develop appropriate strategies to address challenges and capitalise on opportunities (Rastogi & Trivedi, 2016).

Table 2. Definition of the PESTLE Dimensions in the iCOSHELLS Baseline Analysis

PESTLE dimension	Definition in the iCOSHELLS baseline analysis
Political	Political factors, including European, national, or regional policies, regulations, and political debates, that influence or are influenced by soil health in the Living Lab location
Economic	Economic factors, including economic activities, economic incentives, funding & investment schemes, that influence or are influenced by soil health in the Living Lab location.
Social	Social factors, including community engagement, societal norms, social activism, and cultural factors, that influence or are influenced by soil health in the Living Lab location
Technological	Technological factors, including the biological, chemical, mechanical, and electronic technologies used in soil management and soil usage, that influence or are influenced by soil health in the Living Lab location
Legal	Legal factors, including international, European, national, and regional laws and regulations, that influence or are influenced by soil health in the Living Lab location
Environmental	Environmental factors, including climate, biodiversity, and natural resources that influence or are influenced by soil health in the Living Lab location.

Guided by the PESTLE framework, the survey included three parts:

1. Quantitative ratings: Respondents rated the six PESTLE categories on an 11-point integer scale (-5 to +5) indicating whether each category currently influences soil health positively or negatively. For example, local political efforts could be rated as strongly supportive (+5) or strongly opposed (-5) to soil health in the Living Lab location. These quantitative insights provide an overview of the relative influence of each PESTLE dimension, highlighting areas where existing support can be leveraged and opposition addressed. Additionally, they inform stakeholder mapping by indicating relative support or opposition of related stakeholder groups.

2. Qualitative questions on PESTLE factors: Respondents identified and described PESTLE factors influencing soil health in the Living Lab locations (positively, neutrally, or negatively), as well as factors impacted by soil health efforts in these locations. They additionally provided links to relevant publications. Selected PESTLE factors were covered with additional questions, such as the anticipated impact of environmental developments like climate change on soil health in the Living Lab locations. These qualitative insights offer a comprehensive understanding of each Living Lab's operational landscape, capturing both influences on soil health and reciprocal impacts on the six PESTLE dimensions. This allows for early consideration of potential risks and opportunities in the project.

3. Qualitative questions on the status quo of the Living Lab: Respondents elaborated on each Living Lab's progress in identifying soil health challenges and potential solutions, co-creation needs, and current local stakeholder involvement. While these questions were primarily aimed at understanding the Living Labs' status quo for upcoming project activities, responses contributed to the stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis by enriching the understanding of PESTLE factors, particularly risks, opportunities, and stakeholder interests.

The surveys were completed in writing by the Living Lab leaders and their local partners, whose deep familiarity with their respective communities and environments enabled them to address the unique challenges and opportunities of each region. Except in one case, Living Lab leaders completed the survey for all experimental sites within their respective Living Labs, noting where specific information applied to a single site. In Italy, each Living Lab partner completed the survey for their assigned sites, and these responses were subsequently consolidated in the analysis.

Please refer to the complete survey template in the Appendix ([Annex II](#)), which provides a copy of the PESTLE questionnaire used for data collection.

Applied Analytical Methods

The data collected from the baseline analysis survey was rigorously analysed to derive actionable insights for guiding stakeholder engagement and co-creation activities within iCOSHells. This analysis was conducted separately for each Living Lab. It primarily focused on responses to the baseline survey and was further enriched by incorporating relevant publications recommended by project partners.

The qualitative data was analysed through a content analysis approach, guided by Schreier (2014) to identify and evaluate PESTLE factors specific to each Living Lab. The main categories in the content analysis were structured according to the PESTLE framework, ensuring alignment with its political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental dimensions. The analysis was conducted in MAXQDA with AI-assisted support, which provided preliminary suggestions for text segments to be coded within each PESTLE category. Each coding suggestion was carefully verified by the research team, with irrelevant codes removed as necessary. Once coding was refined, sub-

categories were created using an iterative process, that combined manual and AI-assisted analysis steps. A SWOT categorisation (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats) emerged as the most insightful way to structure insights. For each PESTLE factor, relevant SWOT categories were identified as defined in Table 3.

Quantitative insights were analysed descriptively and are used in the following analyses section to provide context for the baseline findings.

Table 3. Sub-Categories of the PESTLE Baseline Analysis

Sub-Category	Definition
Strengths	Strengths of this PESTLE dimension in regard to soil health; PESTLE factors with a positive influence on soil health in the Living Lab location
Weaknesses	Weaknesses of this PESTLE dimension in regard to soil health; PESTLE factors with a negative influence on soil health in the Living Lab location
Opportunities	Opportunities arising for PESTLE dimension through soil health improvements and initiatives; Positive influence of soil health (initiatives) on PESTLE factor
Threats	Potential threats arising for PESTLE dimension through soil health improvements and initiatives; Negative influence of soil health (initiatives) on PESTLE factor

Methodological Considerations and Limitations

This analysis was conducted early in the iCOSHells project, imposing time constraints on survey respondents as well as the authors and reviewers. As the project progresses and partners delve deeper into Living Lab activities, insights will naturally evolve. Additionally, it needs to be noted that each Living Lab represents diverse sub-areas, which may differ significantly in stakeholders and PESTLE factors. Particularly, the Italian Living Lab shows notable internal variation. While the analysis presents integrated results to reflect each Living Lab as a whole, some specific details of sub-areas might not have been fully captured.

Stakeholder Mapping: The stakeholder ranking process may exhibit some biases, partly due to the 5-point scale used for assessing power and interest, which might limit nuanced differentiation. Cognitive biases may have influenced some respondents, conflating power with interest or assuming high interest based on an actor’s perceived importance. Social and legal stakeholders may also be underrepresented, possibly reflecting their indirect involvement in most Living Lab activities or the explicit focus on Living Lab areas.

Baseline Analysis: Overlap between PESTLE factors made it challenging to avoid redundancy while capturing interrelationships. Differences in respondent interpretations of PESTLE categories resulted in occasional inconsistencies, such as focusing on farmers in the social category versus their concerns in the economic category. The level of detail provided and the inclusion of relevant literature also varied among respondents.

Implications for Stakeholder Engagement and Co-Creation: Recommendations are based on analysis results and will require further development. A two-way feedback process is essential. The first direction involves study authors sharing feedback with Living Lab leaders based on the analysis, highlighting areas that may need reassessment. The second direction requires integrating the Living Lab leaders’ evolving strategies for stakeholder engagement and co-creation into the project’s next phases.

Analyses

In the following, we present a comprehensive analysis of the initial situation for each of the six Living Labs. The analysis for each Living Lab is divided into three sections:

1. The first section offers an introduction to the Living Lab, outlining its objectives and explaining the rationale behind focusing on this critical area of interest. It also provides contextual information, including the geographical location and relevant background details to help frame the unique characteristics of the Living Lab.
2. The second section focuses on stakeholder mapping, presenting a detailed analysis of the key stakeholders involved in the Living Lab. This part delves into the relationships and power dynamics among stakeholders, identifying the roles and influence of each group. Visual tools, such as a stakeholder relationship map, an interdependency table, and a power-interest matrix, are employed to illustrate these findings and provide a clearer understanding of the stakeholder landscape.
3. The final and most in-depth section of the analysis is dedicated to a comprehensive PESTLE analysis. This section examines the political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental factors that influence and are influenced by soil health within the Living Lab. For each of these factors, the report identifies strength, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, offering a holistic view of the external factors shaping the project's context and direction.

Basque UrbanSoils Living Lab

Introduction

Overview of LL's Objectives

The Basque UrbanSoils Living Lab addresses soil health challenges in areas encompassing wetlands and wooded spaces, with a particular focus on issues such as flooding, erosion, pollution, poor soil structure, and the impacts of climate change. The project's objective is to enhance soil health and the overall health of urban ecosystems through collaborative experimentation and community engagement, with the goal of developing sustainable solutions to environmental challenges. The Living Lab is led by GAIA (the Association of Applied Knowledge and Technology Industries in the Basque Country) and benefits from the support of research and academic institutions, including the Euskampus Foundation (University of Bordeaux, Public University of the Basque Country). It also receives backing from various civil society groups, such as Eskilara S. Koop, Board of Urdaibai, Euskadi-Navarre-Aquitaine Euroregion, and the municipality of Forua. Additionally, educators, such as San Fidel School and Armeria Eskola, have also pledged their support. Moreover, small and medium-sized enterprises are engaged in the project, specifically INNOVATEKBI and the Urremendi local association. A total of ten co-created test sites, in addition to a designated lighthouse project, will be employed for the purpose of developing and testing innovative solutions. The collaborative endeavour is centred on the design of salubrious green spaces, the integration of the arts and culture for enhanced well-being, the implementation of nature-based solutions and the establishment of robust ecological monitoring systems. It is anticipated that these outcomes will include an enhanced biodiversity, a stronger sense of community and improved citizen well-being, and sustainable regional development.

Geographical Location and Context

The Basque Country, a region straddling the border between Spain and France, covers approximately 21,000 square kilometres and is home to some 3.2 million people. Its political division reflects its historical geography. Administratively, the Spanish Basque Country is divided into three provinces: Álava (Áraba), Vizcaya (Bizkaia) and Gipuzkoa, together with the historically Basque-speaking part of Navarre (Nafarroa). The French Basque Country, also known as the Basque Country or Euskal Herria, consists of three traditional provinces: Labourd (Lapurdi), Lower Navarre (Nafarroa Beherea) and Soule (Zuberoa). The topography of the region is varied. The inland areas are characterised by the foothills of the Cantabrian Mountains, which significantly influence the region's drainage patterns and the distribution of settlements. In contrast, the coastline offers a variety of coastal landscapes. Numerous rivers cut through the region. These valleys are often fertile and densely populated. The climate of the Basque Country is classified as temperate oceanic. It has mild winters and relatively humid summers. The proximity of the Atlantic Ocean is a key factor, moderating temperatures and maintaining high humidity levels throughout the year. This maritime influence creates a relatively stable and pleasant climate, although rainfall can be significant, especially in the mountainous areas. The Basque Country faces several soil challenges: Extensive industrialisation has led to widespread soil contamination, threatening environmental health and food security; a Master Plan for Soil Protection is underway to address this. Soil erosion is also critical, exacerbated by intensive agriculture and urbanisation, and soil instability, particularly in mountainous areas, increases the risk of landslides. Soil compaction by heavy machinery and livestock reduces porosity, impairing root growth and water infiltration. Soil

degradation has reduced organic matter and biodiversity, affecting ecosystem health. Salinisation, possibly from poor irrigation, reduces soil quality and crop viability (Van Den Brink et al., 1995; Soiluzioak; 2023).

Stakeholder Mapping Results

In the Basque Living Lab, a significant emphasis is placed on the technological and environmental domains, with 29 and 18 stakeholders identified, respectively. Notably, the social sector is also well-represented, encompassing 14 stakeholders. While fewer stakeholders have been identified in the political, legal, and economic dimensions (8, 3, and 2 stakeholders respectively), it is important to notice that these include political representation of the municipality of Forua, a member of EUDEL, the Basque Association of Municipalities, which links over 1,000 municipalities and plays a vital role in governance. Similarly, GAIA – iCOSHELLS project partner and key stakeholder, is a technology and economic cluster representing 303 companies and over 14,000 employees—contributing 7% to the region’s GDP. This broader perspective highlights the diverse and collaborative efforts in the Basque Living Lab to address challenges related to soil health comprehensively.

Economic stakeholders include farms, associations, public authorities, and research entities. Farms play a central role, demonstrating high interest and influence in soil health, particularly concerning climate impacts such as erosion and moisture loss. Similarly, two farmer associations, categorised as "keep informed," showcase moderate engagement. Public authorities in energy and research fall into the "manage closely" category, reflecting their strategic importance in integrating soil conservation with broader energy development goals. These authorities address challenges such as balancing productivity with sustainability, mitigating soil degradation, and fostering cross-sectoral coordination. In the Urdaibai area, the Urremendi agency plays a central role by representing the primary sector and bringing together all relevant stakeholders in the region. This collective approach ensures effective coordination and alignment of efforts, supporting the adoption of soil-friendly agricultural methods.

Environmental stakeholders are diverse, including eco-innovation hubs, NGOs, public authorities, and utilities. Among these, research institutions play a pivotal role, with 5 out of 6 stakeholders classified as "manage closely." Local authorities actively govern environmental management, while utilities in energy and waste management also demonstrate significant engagement. In the Urdaibai area, the Patronato of Urdaibai has already developed four strategic plans, including the most recent one for 2024-2027, which outlines innovative strategies to address challenges such as limited control over land use, integrating soil health into industrial zones, and addressing historical pollution. These efforts underscore the region’s proactive approach to aligning environmental goals with sustainable economic development.

Three stakeholders in the legal domain highlight the interconnection between soil and water health. Public water management bodies, critical to soil health, face cross-border governance challenges, while the University of Bordeaux addresses transboundary soil and water issues through collaborative research. Key challenges include managing soil erosion and pollution impacts on water quality, as well as navigating climate-induced stressors such as shifting precipitation patterns.

Political stakeholders, primarily local and regional public authorities, focus on cross-border governance, innovation, and environmental management. Their high interest and influence underscore their role in balancing urban development, agriculture, and conservation. However, resource constraints and complex cross-border regulatory environments present significant hurdles. These stakeholders are essential for aligning soil health

initiatives with broader policy frameworks, particularly in the context of climate resilience and sustainable development.

Social stakeholders include civil society organisations, cultural centres, educational bodies, and training facilitators, all ranked as "high interest and influence." Challenges revolve around interdisciplinary collaboration, translating research into practical solutions, and raising public awareness of soil health. Balancing economic, cultural, and environmental priorities requires creative strategies to enhance community engagement and foster long-term sustainability.

Technological actors span farm suppliers, innovation clusters, research institutions, SMEs, and utilities in energy and water management. With most stakeholders ranked as "manage closely," their role in driving innovation and addressing systemic barriers is crucial. Challenges include bridging research with practical applications and fostering cross-sectoral collaboration for systemic improvements.

Figure 2: Basque Living Lab - Stakeholder Map

The stakeholder map for the Basque Living Lab reveals a highly interconnected network where economic, technological, and environmental sectors collaborate closely to drive innovation and sustainable practices. At the economic core are the small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and cooperatives that form the backbone of the region's industrial and agricultural activities. These entities not only contribute significantly to the regional economy but also embody the cooperative spirit and socio-economic resilience that define the Basque identity. Their operations are guided by robust support from public authorities, which implement policies promoting sustainable practices, industrial modernisation, and compliance with EU frameworks.

The environmental sector complements this by ensuring that industrial and agricultural practices align with sustainability goals. Regional environmental agencies play an active role in fostering biodiversity, reducing emissions, and managing natural resources. These efforts are reinforced by local NGOs and community groups, which advocate for climate action and environmental protection, providing a grassroots perspective that influences policy implementation and public awareness.

The technological sector acts as a critical enabler of innovation and systemic change in the Basque Living Lab. Research centres, universities, and industry clusters form a collaborative ecosystem that integrates cutting-edge research with practical applications. For example, partnerships between industrial actors and technological institutions facilitate advancements in energy efficiency, waste management, and circular economy models. Additionally, digital transformation initiatives, supported by government funding, accelerate the adoption of Industry 4.0 practices across the region.

The Basque Living Lab demonstrates a high degree of integration between sectors, underpinned by strong institutional frameworks and long-standing traditions of collaboration. Cross-border elements, such as partnerships with neighbouring regions and participation in transnational EU projects, further enhance its capacity for innovation and systemic change. However, this complexity requires sophisticated governance mechanisms and sustained stakeholder engagement to balance competing priorities and maintain alignment across diverse objectives.

Power-interest Matrix

The power-interest matrix for the Basque Living Lab reveals that nearly all stakeholders exhibit high interest in soil health, with many also possessing high influence. This concentration towards the right side of the matrix suggests an unusually engaged stakeholder base, highlighting the importance of cross-sectoral and cross-border collaboration, as also revealed by the outcomes of the mapping exercise:

Figure 3: Basque Living Lab - Power-Interest Matrix

Manage closely - High Power, High Interest: Key stakeholders, including farmers, research institutions, utilities, and local authorities, hold significant influence and are deeply invested in the project's outcomes. These stakeholders are critical drivers of innovation, policy development, and resource allocation. To ensure sustained engagement and alignment, they require meticulous management through proactive strategies. Joint initiatives would not only foster a sense of ownership but also leverage their expertise to shape impactful solutions.

Keep satisfied - High Power, Low Interest: Broader public authorities, particularly those focused on energy and climate regulation, wield significant influence but may exhibit limited direct interest in soil health or related initiatives. Their engagement is crucial to bridge the gap between overarching regulatory goals and the specific priorities of the project. Targeted strategies, such as tailored briefings, and showcasing the link between soil health and broader sustainability targets like carbon sequestration or water quality, can help align their objectives with the project's outcomes.

Keep informed - Low Power, High Interest: Stakeholders such as farmer associations, grassroots organisations, and community groups possess a strong vested interest in the project's success, as its outcomes directly impact their livelihoods and operations. Although their influence may be limited, they play a vital role in shaping on-the-ground practices and fostering community buy-in. Empowering these stakeholders through capacity-building initiatives, such as, workshops, and access to technical expertise, equips them to implement and advocate for sustainable practices. Their insights and experiences also provide valuable feedback loops for refining project strategies.

Monitor - Low Power, Low Interest: Peripheral entities, such as auxiliary service providers, local businesses, or non-specialised organisations, have limited influence and interest in the iCOSHells project. While their engagement is not critical for strategic decision-making, they can still provide occasional support or act as conduits for information dissemination. Maintaining a low-maintenance engagement strategy, such as periodic newsletters, informational updates, or invitations to broader project events, ensures that these stakeholders remain informed and are available to contribute if their role becomes relevant. These light-touch strategies minimise resource expenditure while preserving a positive relationship with these entities.

Baseline Analysis: Local Ecosystems of the Living Lab

Introduction

The assessment of soil health drivers in the Basque Living Lab, located within the UNESCO-designated Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve, reveals a robust framework for soil health management and conservation.

Living Lab leaders were asked to rate PESTLE influences on a scale from -5 (strong negative influence) to +5 (strong positive influence). These ratings are presented here as they offer a valuable overview for the analysis:

The assessment identified varying levels of strength in the key enabling factors, with political support emerging as the dominant driver with a score of +4. This exceptional political support reflects the region's deep-rooted institutional commitment to environmental protection and sustainable land management practices.

Four critical factors—economic incentives, civil society engagement, technological applications and regulatory frameworks—each scored a strong +3, demonstrating a well-balanced support system. This harmonious integration of financial mechanisms, community involvement, technological innovation and legal structures provides a solid foundation for soil health initiatives. However, the status of soil health itself, rated at +2, indicates that despite the strong enabling environment, there remains significant potential for improvement in terms of tangible outcomes.

This initial assessment highlights both the achievements and the challenges within the Basque Living Lab. While the region benefits from an integrated approach where political will, community engagement, economic instruments and technological capabilities work together, the gap between enabling factors and actual soil health conditions suggests opportunities for improved implementation strategies. The following analysis explores the complex interplay of these factors, examines how this comprehensive support system translates into practical conservation measures, and identifies areas where interventions could have a greater impact on soil health outcomes.

Political Factors

Strengths of current political actions and policies for soil health: The Basque Living Lab within the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve benefits from several significant political strengths in its soil health policies and actions. The Living Lab operates within the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve, which has a strong environmental protection status and considerable political support for sustainability initiatives. The region has strict regulations on land use, biodiversity conservation and soil protection, with particularly strong enforcement in designated protected areas. A notable strength is the collaborative governance approach, where municipalities work closely with environmental organisations and local communities. This cooperation enables the successful implementation of community-driven soil conservation initiatives, such as reforestation projects. The combination of comprehensive regulatory frameworks and collaborative governance models creates a supportive environment that is particularly conducive to maintaining healthy soils. These policy strengths work together to provide a strong foundation for soil health protection and management in the region.

Weaknesses of current political actions and policies countering soil health: While environmental policies provide a strong foundation for soil conservation, certain challenges persist that warrant attention. Consistent enforcement at the local level can be difficult due to limited resources and competing political priorities. Additionally, while policies and subsidies support sustainable practices, there is a perceived bias favouring larger, industrial-scale farms, which can disadvantage small-scale farmers. This may inadvertently encourage practices, such as excessive use of fertilisers and pesticides, that risk degrading soil quality. Moreover, while regional economic development and infrastructure projects are important, they can sometimes conflict with soil conservation goals. Urbanisation, road construction, and industrial activities may lead to soil erosion and loss of agricultural land if environmental impact assessments are not consistently thorough or well-enforced. These challenges highlight areas for improvement without diminishing the value of existing policies.

Opportunities of soil health for local politics: Opportunities of soil health improvements for local political development in the Basque Living Lab are multifaceted. Enhancing soil health can showcase the region as a leader in sustainable practices, fostering political support for further environmental initiatives and boosting the region's influence in broader political contexts. By improving soil productivity and reducing erosion, local leaders can strengthen economic stability and reduce tensions between development and conservation, demonstrating their capacity to balance competing priorities. Soil health achievements aligned with national and EU sustainability goals can attract funding for conservation efforts, reinforcing the region's standing as a model for effective governance. Additionally, integrating soil health into local policy agendas can help mitigate risks caused by soil degradation such as land degradation and desertification, positioning leaders as proactive stewards of environmental and economic well-being, which enhances public trust and political capital.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local politics: The main challenge lies in managing the tensions between environmental protection and economic development, particularly in relation to infrastructure projects and urbanisation. Limited enforcement capacity and resource constraints can pose threats to the effective implementation of soil health legislation. While the Biosphere Reserve status prioritises environmental protection, political decisions often seek to balance conservation with economic development, such as tourism and infrastructure projects. While promoting eco-tourism can raise awareness about soil health, increased human activity may still lead to soil compaction or erosion if not carefully managed.

Economic Factors

Strengths of current economic actions for soil health: The strengths of current economic action for soil health in the region cover several key areas. Local cooperatives play an important role in promoting sustainable agricultural practices, including organic farming and regenerative techniques, which help to improve soil structure, fertility and biodiversity. The region has also invested in renewable energy projects, particularly solar and wind power plants, which reduce reliance on fossil fuels and help mitigate land degradation. The introduction of advanced soil monitoring technologies has enabled precision farming practices, allowing farmers to manage soil conditions more effectively and prevent degradation. In addition, the development of ecotourism in the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve serves a dual economic and environmental purpose. This tourism activity not only generates economic benefits, but also raises awareness of soil conservation and supports sustainable land use practices throughout the region.

Weaknesses of current economic actions countering soil health: The weaknesses of the current economic approach to soil health manifest themselves in a number of significant ways. Intensive agricultural practices are a major concern, particularly the overuse of chemical fertilisers, pesticides and heavy machinery. These practices degrade soil quality by reducing biodiversity, causing soil acidification and leading to soil compaction. Increasing urbanisation and infrastructure development create a further set of problems, leading to soil compaction, erosion and the loss of valuable fertile topsoil. Industrial activities contribute to soil degradation through pollution and waste contamination, requiring costly remediation. In addition, livestock farming practices, particularly overgrazing, are another weakness of current economic activities. This practice can deplete soil organic matter and potentially lead to desertification, further compromising soil health and agricultural productivity in the region.

Opportunities of soil health for local economic development: Opportunities of soil health for local economic development are vast and interconnected. Healthy soils enhance agricultural productivity by supporting sustainable and organic farming practices, leading to higher yields, reduced input costs, and greater profitability for farmers and cooperatives. This not only strengthens food security but also stabilises the agricultural economy. Maintaining soil health preserves the region's natural landscapes, which are vital for ecotourism, ensuring continued attraction for visitors and economic growth for tourism-dependent businesses. Soil restoration also enables the successful integration of innovative renewable energy projects, such as agrivoltaic systems, which combine solar power generation with sustainable farming, optimizing land use and creating dual revenue streams. By improving soil health, the region mitigates risks caused by soil degradation like reduced agricultural productivity, loss of natural beauty, and challenges in renewable energy development, securing long-term economic sustainability.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local economic development: The potential threats of soil health improvement measures for economic development in the Basque Country centre on immediate economic challenges and resource allocation conflicts. The transition from intensive to sustainable agricultural practices may initially result in reduced productivity, leading to financial strain during the adaptation period.

Social Factors

Strengths of social/community support for soil health: Social and community support for soil health in the Basque Country has several important strengths. Local civil society shows strong support for both the restoration and protection of soil health. A collaborative governance model is in place, where local governments work in close partnership with environmental organisations to promote best practices in soil and land management. This collaboration ensures that decision-making processes are inclusive, environmentally focused and in line with scientific research and innovation. Educational institutions play a key role, with schools such as San Fidel School and IES Barrutialde actively incorporating environmental education into their curricula. This educational focus helps to foster a culture of environmental responsibility among the younger generations. Community engagement extends further through a variety of channels, including community-based renewable energy initiatives, local agricultural cooperatives, public awareness campaigns and collaborative projects with local governments. These various initiatives and partnerships strengthen community engagement and create broad-based support for sustainable land management practices.

Weaknesses of social/community activities countering soil health: Social weaknesses in the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve include urban expansion and infrastructure development driven by community interests, which lead to soil sealing and depletion. As urban areas grow, soil's ability to retain moisture and support biodiversity is compromised. Additionally, prohibited recreational activities such as off-road driving, off-trail hiking, and camping contribute to soil compaction and erosion, further degrading the land. These leisure activities disrupt soil structure and contribute to long-term degradation. There is also a challenge regarding the overuse of public spaces for events, which increases foot traffic and damages the soil. These social pressures, combined with limited awareness and engagement around soil protection, create significant challenges for maintaining soil health in the region.

Opportunities of soil health for local communities and social development: Soil health offers several opportunities for social and community development. Maintaining healthy soils creates opportunities for educational programmes and hands-on learning experiences, particularly through school gardens and community farming initiatives. These programmes help build environmental awareness and strengthen community ties. Successful implementation of soil health projects can serve as a model for other communities, creating opportunities for knowledge sharing and community leadership in environmental conservation. By improving soil health, the region additionally mitigates risks caused by soil degradation. Declining soil health threatens food security, increasing food costs and reducing access to locally grown produce. It also creates public health risks due to contamination of water and food, exposing communities to pollutants. The loss of soil fertility impacts traditional farming practices, undermining cultural heritage. Additionally, soil degradation reduces access to green spaces, which are important for recreational and social well-being.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local communities and social development: Cultural resistance manifests itself primarily in the reluctance of communities to abandon traditional farming methods in favour of more sustainable practices. This attachment to conventional approaches, while understandable from a cultural heritage perspective, can hinder the adoption of soil-friendly agricultural innovations. Unregulated activities pose another challenge, particularly through uncontrolled recreational activities such as off-road driving and uncontrolled hiking, which contribute to soil degradation. Implementation challenges arise in the complex task of balancing community needs with soil conservation objectives.

Technological Factors

Strengths of current technologies for soil health: Technological advancements in the Basque Living Lab significantly enhance soil health by integrating innovative solutions with traditional agricultural practices. Regenerative methods like cover cropping, crop rotation, and rotational grazing, widely used by local cooperatives, boost organic matter, biodiversity, and soil structure while preventing erosion. The adoption of organic fertilisers and natural pest control reduces reliance on synthetic chemicals, preserving soil fertility and microbial life. Advanced electronic technologies, such as soil and environmental sensors from Libelium and Metos Iberia, provide real-time data on moisture, oxygen levels, and nutrients, allowing farmers to optimise irrigation and fertilisation practices, thereby minimizing resource overuse. Precision agriculture machinery, equipped with GPS-guided systems, minimises soil compaction and ensures efficient planting and harvesting with reduced disturbance, preserving soil structure and reducing erosion risks. Local farmers also combine traditional land knowledge with scientific techniques, such as minimal tillage and organic amendments, creating a comprehensive approach to sustainable soil management.

Weaknesses of current technologies countering soil health: Heavy agricultural machinery causes soil compaction and structural damage, reducing soil porosity and water infiltration, which hinders root growth, increases erosion, and makes it harder for soils to retain nutrients. Over-reliance on chemical-intensive technologies, including automated fertiliser and pesticide applications, leads to soil acidification, biodiversity loss, contamination, and nutrient depletion, harming microorganisms crucial for fertility. Inefficient irrigation systems contribute to salinisation, waterlogging, erosion, and structural damage if not calibrated to local conditions, while poor water management exacerbates nutrient loss. Monocultures without crop rotation deplete specific nutrients, reduce fertility, and increase reliance on chemical inputs, further degrading soil health. Frequent and deep tillage disturbs soil structure, accelerates erosion, and leads to organic matter loss and topsoil degradation.

Opportunities of novel technologies: Advanced sensing and monitoring technologies, including Internet of Things sensors and satellite imagery, allow real-time tracking of soil conditions, enabling more precise and responsive soil management practices. These technologies help farmers detect early signs of degradation and optimise resource use. Emerging biotechnological solutions, such as enhanced microbial amendments and biofertilisers, offer opportunities for natural soil restoration and enhancement. In addition, precision agriculture technologies, including GPS-guided machinery and smart irrigation systems, enable site-specific management practices that can reduce chemical inputs while maintaining productivity. Drones and remote sensing can provide aerial data on soil conditions, plant health and land use patterns, enabling early intervention and targeted measures to improve soil health. These innovations, combined with data analysis, create opportunities to develop more sustainable and efficient farming practices that protect and improve soil health.

Potential threats of novel technologies: Some technologies offer promising benefits for soil health but also carry risks if mismanaged. Precision agriculture tools improve efficiency by reducing fertiliser and water use, but heavy machinery can still compact soil, reducing water infiltration and root growth. Drip irrigation systems conserve water and prevent over-irrigation but risk localised salinisation from salt buildup if poorly managed. Organic fertilisers boost organic matter and fertility but may cause nutrient imbalances and leaching if overused. Greenhouses reduce pesticide use but isolate soil from natural ecosystems and depend on artificial nutrient management, potentially harming long-term fertility. Conservation tillage limits soil disturbance and retains moisture but may increase reliance on herbicides, risking soil contamination. These technologies require careful management to maximise benefits and mitigate risks.

Legal Factors

Strengths of current legal regulations for soil health: The Basque Living Lab benefits from robust legal frameworks at local, regional, national, and EU levels. Local regulations, such as those in Forua and Gernika, promote sustainable agricultural practices and enforce land-use zoning, helping to prevent soil degradation. Regional initiatives, including the Basque Environmental Protection Law and the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve Management Plan, emphasise conservation and sustainable land use, safeguarding soil health in protected areas. The KLIMA 2050 strategy highlights soil's role in carbon sequestration, linking soil health to climate change mitigation. Nationally, the Spanish Soil Conservation Law addresses erosion, desertification, and soil pollution, promoting sustainable practices. At the EU level, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) incentivises sustainable farming methods like crop rotation and organic farming, while the EU Soil Thematic Strategy provides a framework to combat soil erosion and contamination. Together, these regulations support biodiversity, soil fertility, and environmental sustainability.

Weaknesses of current legal regulations countering soil health: Despite comprehensive laws, enforcement remains partially inconsistent, especially in rural areas where monitoring resources are limited. Municipalities can lack personnel to oversee compliance, creating gaps in soil protection efforts. National and EU regulations, including the CAP, tend to favour larger agricultural operations, leaving smaller farmers struggling to comply with guidelines or access financial support for sustainable practices. Stakeholders also highlight a lack of localisation in some laws, which fail to address the Basque region's unique environmental and agricultural needs. Standardised EU policies may not adequately reflect the specific challenges of the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve. Additionally, the emphasis on short-term economic priorities, such as land development or intensive farming, sometimes overshadows long-term soil sustainability. Bureaucratic hurdles, particularly around accessing subsidies or conservation programmes, further discourage smallholders from fully engaging in sustainable land-use practices.

Opportunities associated with legal regulations for soil health: Legal frameworks present significant opportunities to enhance soil health by fostering sustainable practices and innovation. The CAP's financial incentives encourage methods like crop rotation, cover cropping, and organic farming, improving soil fertility while supporting biodiversity. Regional initiatives, such as KLIMA 2050, promote climate-resilient farming and soil carbon sequestration, aligning environmental and agricultural policies. Locally, municipal regulations in areas like Forua and Gernika drive community-led soil conservation initiatives. National laws like the Spanish Soil Conservation Law provide a foundation for sustainable agriculture by tackling erosion and pollution. EU-wide frameworks, such as the Soil Thematic Strategy, harmonise efforts across member states, offering a cohesive approach to soil protection. By tailoring these policies to local contexts, leveraging financial tools, and simplifying procedures, governments can enhance participation and maximise the impact of legal frameworks on soil health.

Potential threats associated with legal regulations for soil health: Legal frameworks can inadvertently create risks for soil health when poorly implemented or misaligned with local conditions. Inconsistent enforcement can undermine effectiveness, allowing harmful practices like over-fertilisation to persist. Limited resources for monitoring and enforcement exacerbate this issue, while complex frameworks and overlapping regulations between different jurisdictions can lead to confusion and inadequate implementation. Generalised EU or national policies partially overlook specific local challenges, such as soil salinity or erosion in the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve. Furthermore, policies that favour large-scale farming, such as certain CAP incentives, may encourage industrial agriculture, which risks soil compaction and over-reliance on chemical inputs. Legal priorities favouring economic development over conservation can also lead to soil degradation in urban expansion or intensive agriculture areas, while bureaucratic complexities deter smallholders from participating in sustainable practices.

Environmental Factors

Strengths of the natural environment for soil health: The Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve offers a strong foundation for soil health due to its rich biodiversity and favourable natural environment. High plant diversity promotes organic matter accumulation, enhances soil fertility, and supports beneficial microbial communities. The region's forests and wetlands help protect soil from erosion and maintain its structure. Strong conservation policies within the Biosphere Reserve limit harmful activities like deforestation and intensive agriculture, further safeguarding soil health. The mild climate with consistent rainfall ensures optimal conditions for vegetation growth, reducing the need for excessive irrigation. This balance of moisture and temperature supports active microbial life, which is essential for organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling. Additionally, reforestation and afforestation projects led by local communities enhance soil stability, reduce erosion, and increase organic matter content through leaf litter and root systems, contributing to long-term soil health.

Weaknesses of the natural environment countering soil health: Weaknesses of the natural environment for soil health in the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve include the region's topographical features, such as steep slopes, which make soils more prone to erosion, especially during heavy rainfall. This erosion strips away nutrient-rich topsoil, reducing fertility and leaving the land vulnerable to further degradation. Climate change exacerbates these issues by increasing the frequency of extreme weather events, such as intense rainfall and droughts, which dry out soils and reduce organic matter. Additionally, although conservation efforts are strong, deforestation in unprotected areas or those used for agriculture can further exacerbate soil erosion and loss of biodiversity. The removal of tree cover exposes soils to the elements, increasing vulnerability. While reforestation efforts aim to mitigate these effects, logging activities can temporarily disrupt and compact soil, negatively impacting soil health in the short term.

Opportunities of soil health for the natural environment: Maintaining and restoring soil health offers significant opportunities to support the region's environmental sustainability. Healthy soils can enhance water regulation, improve climate resilience through carbon sequestration and cooling effects, and sustain biodiversity. Soil health initiatives can also contribute to the preservation of the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve's natural landscapes, which are crucial for eco-tourism and community engagement. Successful soil health outcomes in the Basque Living Lab can serve as a model for sustainable land management practices and influence regional, national, and European environmental policies.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for the natural environment: Measures to improve soil health can sometimes harm the environment if not carefully managed. Eco-tourism, while promoting conservation, can cause soil compaction and erosion when activities like off-trail hiking are unregulated, especially in sensitive areas like the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve. In forestry, sustainable practices prevent erosion, but improper logging can cause short-term soil disruption and compaction. Similarly, while organic farming methods such as crop rotation support soil health, monoculture practices or excessive use of organic fertilisers can lead to nutrient imbalances, undermining the benefits. The region's mild climate generally supports soil health, but extreme weather events like floods or droughts, exacerbated by climate change, can lead to erosion or reduced fertility. Additionally, poor water management in irrigation can cause salinisation or nutrient leaching, harming soil health over time.

Implications for stakeholder engagement and co-creation

The stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis provide valuable insights for stakeholder engagement and co-creation within the Basque Living Lab. The stakeholder mapping offers specific recommendations on managing stakeholder groups, identifying which stakeholders to engage closely, which to keep satisfied, which to inform, and which to monitor. Complementing this, the baseline analysis highlights opportunities presented by soil health initiatives across political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental dimensions. These opportunities can serve as compelling arguments to involve relevant stakeholders in Living Lab activities. Simultaneously, the analysis identifies potential threats associated with a focus on soil health that may concern specific stakeholder groups. These concerns can be taken into account in communication strategies and incorporated into Living Lab solutions, ensuring project partners are equipped with clear responses to alleviate existing fears.

The Basque Living Lab operates in an environment with extensive experience in stakeholder engagement and co-creation. Many of the involved actors have a longstanding history of collaboration, fostered by the region's collaborative governance approach. This context has facilitated the identification of core challenges, as well as promising solutions to be tested within the iCOSHells Living Lab. To address challenges such as erosion control, soil fertility maintenance, and flood management, the Living Lab might test nature-based solutions (e.g., reforestation and salt marsh stabilisation) and technological innovations (e.g., LoRa digital monitoring systems and real-time soil health sensors). Co-creation sessions can identify further solutions, prioritise and refine feasible options, and plan their implementation in the Living Lab.

The following section outlines initial strategies derived from stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis, recommending tailored engagement levels ranging from active co-creation to minimal interaction with peripheral stakeholders. These insights build on and complement the Living Lab's earlier work, providing an external perspective to enhance ongoing strategic development. It thereby needs to be noted that many of the recommended strategies confirm what is already planned in the Living Lab. In the next phase of the project, stakeholder engagement and co-creation plans will be further refined, integrating findings from the stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis with existing plans of the Living Lab. A particular focus will be placed on detailing planned co-creation sessions, with results to be documented in a publicly accessible report.

Recommended strategies:

Active engagement through co-creation: Engaging core stakeholders in the Living Lab activities is pivotal to developing innovative, scientifically robust, practical, and locally accepted soil health solutions in the Basque LL. Key stakeholders, particularly local farmers, research institutions, utilities, technology providers, and local environmental authorities, hold high influence and exhibit high interest in the project outcomes. Their contributions can encompass generating further ideas for enhancing soil health, refining pre-selected solutions, planning and implementing solution testing, and monitoring, evaluating, and adapting tested solutions. Participation in co-creation sessions also fosters a sense of ownership and ensures long-term commitment to the project's objectives, which is essential for its sustained impact. Special emphasis should be placed on engaging farmers, especially small-scale farmers. Actively involving them in co-creation not only enhances solution development but also raises awareness of soil health challenges and empowers them to implement effective solutions. Moreover, cultivating these relationships through regular consultations and tailored communication strategies is crucial, particularly for stakeholders unable to participate directly in co-creation activities.

Incentivise and Empower Farmer Associations: Farmer associations, which have a strong vested interest but limited influence, are acutely aware of the challenges farmers may face in adopting soil health solutions, such as the financial burden or skill gaps. Engaging these associations requires emphasising the long-term economic benefits of improved soil health for farmers and local communities. Empowering them through capacity-building initiatives, workshops, and access to technical resources is equally important. Incentivised and empowered farmer associations can play a pivotal role in disseminating tested solutions to a broader audience, providing guidance on securing funding, and advising on the practical implementation of these solutions. This dissemination is critical to extending the impact and knowledge gained from the Living Labs to a wider audience.

Empower Cultural, and Educational Community Groups: For stakeholders such as community groups - who have a strong vested interest but limited influence - it is vital to empower them through capacity-building exchanges, workshops, and access to technical resources. By integrating their feedback and amplifying their voices as ambassadors of the project, these groups can extend the project's reach and foster community-wide adoption of sustainable practices. Community groups and local schools can play a key role in educating the public about the importance of soil health and methods for maintaining healthy soils. Cultural groups can further engage the public in sustainability conversations by incorporating soil health topics into their cultural programmes.

Incentivise Broader Public Authorities: broader public authorities focused on energy and climate regulation, while highly influential, may show limited direct interest in soil health initiatives. To engage these stakeholders effectively, it is critical to emphasise co-benefits such as carbon sequestration, biodiversity enhancement, and water quality improvements. By tailoring communications and showcasing the alignment between the project's outcomes and their sustainability objectives, these authorities can be incentivised to integrate soil health considerations into their agendas. The creation of policy briefs based on the project results can further encourage the integration of soil health considerations into environmental policies and legislation. These briefs can effectively highlight the needs of local soil users to policymakers, fostering greater political support for soil health initiatives.

Enable cross-border collaboration: The unique location of the Basque region, which encompasses areas in both Spain and France, makes fostering cross-border collaboration particularly valuable. Engaging relevant political, technical, and legal institutions can ensure the long-term uptake of the tested practices and technologies, not only within the Basque region as a whole but also in neighbouring areas of Spain and France.

Connect with Local Environmental Initiatives and Actors: Environmental protection has a long-standing tradition in the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve. Collaborating with these initiatives can uncover synergies and foster knowledge exchange. Furthermore, these organisations can play a crucial role in ensuring the sustainability of the Living Lab beyond the project's duration and in disseminating lessons learned to a wider audience.

Maintain Low-Maintenance Engagement with Peripheral Entities: these entities, including auxiliary service providers, local businesses, and non-specialized organisations, require a low-maintenance engagement approach. Periodic updates via newsletters, or invitations to broader project events will keep them informed and ready to contribute if their roles become relevant. These light-touch strategies ensure the efficient allocation of resources while maintaining positive relationships with these stakeholders.

Bulgarian Viticulture Soil Living Lab

Introduction

Overview of the Bulgarian Viticulture Soil Living Lab's Objectives

The objective of this Living Lab is to enhance the resilience and mitigate the vulnerabilities of vineyard soils in the context of climate change, particularly within the context of grape and wine production. A total of ten experimental sites will be utilised for collaborative research and development activities. The Living Lab is led by the Agricultural University of Plovdiv (AUP). Key stakeholders include research institutions, such as the AUP, the Institute of Soil Science, Agroecology and Plant Protection, as well as farmer representatives, such as the Regional Agricultural Advisory Service of Plovdiv and the Association of Fruit Growers in Bulgaria. Additionally, technology providers, such as Summit Agro Bulgaria, and other relevant organisations, such as Ondo Solution Ltd. and the National Grape and Vineyard Chamber, are involved. The solutions under investigation encompass the integration of remote sensing for irrigation systems, the utilisation of satellite data for precision farming, and the development of a novel decision support system. The anticipated outcomes are enhanced soil health, augmented resilience of vineyards to climate change impacts, and optimised grape and wine production. The project directly addresses the intricate interrelationship between land use, agricultural techniques, and the long-term health of the soil ecosystem within the context of a changing climate.

Geographical Location and Context

The Viticulture Soil Living Lab is located in the Plovdiv region, in the wine region known as the Thracian Valley. The Thracian Valley is an important viticultural area in southern Bulgaria, producing approximately 75% of the country's wine. The valley is nestled between two significant mountain ranges: the Balkan Mountains to the north and the Sredna Gora Mountains to the south. This topography creates a protected environment that contributes to the region's distinctive terroir. The climate of the Thracian Valley is classified as temperate continental, characterised by low rainfall. These dry conditions are particularly suited to the cultivation of red wine grapes, which thrive in sunny, arid environments. The vineyards themselves are located on a mixture of fertile plains and gently sloping hillsides. This varied terrain offers a range of soil types, including clay, limestone and loam. However, this established viticultural heritage faces a growing threat from climate change (World Bank, 2021). Rising temperatures and shifting rainfall patterns are disrupting the delicate ecological balance that has long underpinned the region's wine production. The increased risk of extreme weather events, such as heavy downpours and prolonged droughts, exacerbates these challenges (Georgieva et al., 2022). These climatic changes increase the risk of soil erosion, potentially removing valuable topsoil and reducing soil fertility. This soil degradation poses a significant threat to the long-term viability of viticulture in the Thracian Valley.

Stakeholder Mapping Results

The stakeholder mapping exercise revealed a significant emphasis on economic and technological stakeholders, with 39 and 17 identified, respectively, compared to six political and three environmental stakeholders. This distribution reflects the region's prioritisation of economic development and technological innovation as key drivers of its agricultural advancements. However, the comparatively lower representation of political and environmental stakeholders suggests potential gaps in aligning policy frameworks and ecological objectives with the lab's broader goals.

Economic stakeholders form the backbone of the lab's activities, spanning diverse subtypes such as associations, farms, and processing entities. For instance, the "Association/Interest Group" subtype comprises nine stakeholders, with six actively managed - indicating both high power and interest - and three monitored, reflecting moderate engagement. Among these, vineyards stand out as a major subgroup, highlighting the region's rich viticultural tradition, with 13 stakeholders, which underscores the economic importance of viticulture in the region. However, only three of these vineyards have defined engagement strategies, indicating a gap in strategic involvement. Other subtypes, such as "Processing," "Innovation," and "Farms Suppliers," demonstrate a mixed engagement approach, with stakeholders variably managed, monitored, or kept informed. Despite their significance, economic stakeholders still face systemic barriers, limited financial resources, insufficient administrative support, and barriers to adopting innovative soil health practices. The lab offers an opportunity to address these obstacles by providing technical guidance, fostering capacity-building initiatives, and creating pathways for innovation adoption.

Environmental stakeholders, while fewer in number, play a crucial role, primarily through public authority functions. This group includes subtypes such as "Public Authority, Water Management" and "Public Authority, Vineyard Regulation," which emphasise regulatory roles. However, with only three stakeholders identified, broader environmental considerations, such as biodiversity and soil conservation, may require additional attention to ensure comprehensive integration into the living lab's activities.

The political stakeholders, though a smaller group, are diverse and include municipalities, regional governments, NGOs, and public authorities. Their varying engagement levels suggest different roles and priorities within the project. For example, municipalities and regional governments reflect localised governance structures, while NGOs and energy authorities highlight opportunities for collaboration in areas such as energy efficiency and climate resilience. The presence of a closely managed general public authority indicates its strategic importance in aligning regional development goals with the project's objectives.

Technological stakeholders, including research institutions and innovation-focused entities, are well-represented and play a pivotal role in driving advancements. The "Research" subtype is the largest, with eight stakeholders actively managed, underscoring the lab's emphasis on research-driven solutions. Other subtypes, such as "Training" and "Public Authority, Agriculture," indicate efforts to bridge knowledge gaps and translate research into actionable strategies. Additionally, the inclusion of stakeholders focused on innovation and farms supply chains reflects a commitment to fostering technological advancements and supporting systemic improvements.

Figure 4: Bulgarian Living Lab - Stakeholder Map

The stakeholder map for the Bulgarian Living Lab highlights the significant roles played by the technological, environmental, and economic sectors in shaping its activities and focus. At the heart of the economic sector lie the vineyards, which are pivotal not only for their contribution to the local economy but also as a cornerstone of the region's agricultural identity. These vineyards operate under stringent oversight from the public authority responsible for vineyard regulation, ensuring compliance with production standards and fostering alignment with national and EU policies. Other public bodies, while less directly involved in the environmental regulation of vineyards, contribute indirectly by setting broader environmental standards and promoting initiatives for biodiversity and climate resilience. These entities, though peripheral, still hold a supporting role in influencing practices within the sector.

The technological sector plays a vital role by bridging research, innovation, and practical application within the agricultural landscape. Training facilities for agricultural professionals and research institutions drive the development of cutting-edge, sustainable agricultural practices. Their work not only supports economic actors like vineyard owners and workers but also fosters a culture of continuous improvement and environmental stewardship.

When compared to the Basque Country, the Bulgarian Living Lab's stakeholder dynamics are less integrated across sectors, with fewer examples of collaboration between economic, environmental, and technological actors.

Additionally, the absence of cross-border elements simplifies governance structures and stakeholder engagement processes. While this might reduce complexity, it also presents challenges in fostering innovation and broader systemic change, which often benefit from cross-sectoral and cross-regional synergies.

Power-interest Matrix

By systematically categorizing stakeholders through the power-interest matrix, the project can implement targeted engagement strategies that maximise collaboration, minimise risks, and ensure the alignment of diverse stakeholder groups with its overarching objectives. This approach fosters an inclusive, adaptive, and efficient framework for stakeholder management, enhancing the project's potential for long-term success. Below the analysis for the Bulgarian living lab is provided.

Figure 5: Bulgarian Living Lab - Power-Interest Matrix

Manage closely - High Power, High Interest: Stakeholders in this quadrant, such as research institutions and key vineyards, possess both significant influence over project outcomes and a vested interest in its success. These stakeholders are pivotal to driving project goals and require close management to ensure their active participation. For example, research institutions play a critical role in developing and disseminating innovative solutions, while vineyards are directly impacted by the project's outcomes and contribute valuable on-the-ground insights. Proactive engagement strategies, such as regular consultations, co-development of initiatives, and inclusion in decision-making processes, are essential to maintain their commitment and leverage their influence.

Keep satisfied - High Power, Low Interest: This group includes stakeholders such as "Public Authority, Energy," whose decisions and actions may significantly affect the project's trajectory, even though their direct interest might be limited. Engaging these stakeholders requires a tailored approach to sustain their satisfaction and prevent potential roadblocks. This might involve highlighting the project's alignment with broader policy goals, showcasing its potential to address systemic issues, or demonstrating mutual benefits. Regular updates, targeted communications, and strategic partnerships can help maintain their involvement and foster a sense of shared purpose.

Keep informed - Low Power, High Interest: Stakeholders such as "Farms Suppliers" fall into this category, showing a strong interest in the project's success but lacking significant influence to shape its direction. These stakeholders are often highly motivated to contribute but may require additional support to amplify their impact. Capacity-building initiatives, such as training programs, technical assistance, and opportunities for collaborative innovation, can empower these stakeholders to play a more active and influential role. Enhancing their capabilities not only strengthens their contributions but also bolsters the project's overall resilience and sustainability.

Monitor- Low Power, Low Interest: While stakeholders in this quadrant, such as peripheral entities or marginal subtypes, may have limited influence and interest, they should not be overlooked. These stakeholders can still play supporting roles, such as providing specific resources, insights, or indirect support that contributes to the project's success. Periodic updates and low-maintenance engagement strategies, such as newsletters or community briefings, can help keep these stakeholders informed and aligned with the project without requiring significant resources.

Baseline Analysis: Local Ecosystems of the Living Lab

Introduction

Living Lab leaders were asked to rate PESTLE influences on a scale from -5 (strong negative influence) to +5 (strong positive influence). These ratings are presented here as they offer a valuable overview for the analysis:

Based on the first survey data from Bulgaria's Living Lab location, the overall conditions for soil health present a predominantly positive outlook, with ratings between 3 and 4 on a scale from -5 to +5. Political support and economic incentives stand out with particularly strong ratings of 4, reflecting robust governmental and financial backing for soil health initiatives. Additionally, the engagement of civil society, the impact of current technologies, and the legal/regulatory framework all receive moderate ratings of 3, indicating solid support systems that are ripe for improvement. The average level of soil health across the surveyed sites is also rated at 3, signifying generally good soil conditions with opportunities for enhancement.

This balanced yet optimistic assessment lays the groundwork for a detailed analysis of the various factors influencing soil health in Bulgaria's agricultural sector, particularly in vineyard management. The following comprehensive PESTLE analysis explores the strengths, weaknesses, risks, and opportunities within the Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, and Environmental dimensions, providing deeper insights into each of these rated aspects.

Political Factors

Strengths of current political actions and policies for soil health: The strengths of the current political actions and policies for soil health in Bulgaria include free advisory services, with the government providing farmers with access to extension services to help them adopt sustainable practices. Additionally, financial support is available in the form of compensatory payments for farmers who implement agro-ecological measures, offering incentives for sustainable agriculture. The regulatory framework also includes mandatory plans for the proper management of organic livestock waste, encouraging environmentally sound practices. Furthermore, support for conservation practices is provided through financial assistance to farmers who adopt conservation farming practices, which helps maintain soil health.

Weaknesses of current political actions and policies countering soil health: The current policy framework has some significant weaknesses in addressing soil health. At regional and local levels, there is insufficient work to raise awareness of the need to maintain and restore soil health. Farmers are slow to adopt sustainable soil health practices, indicating a gap between policy development and actual implementation. Agricultural input suppliers are not adequately incentivised to promote sustainable practices, creating a barrier in the supply chain for soil-friendly solutions. In addition, there is insufficient support for producers wishing to invest in digital technologies to maintain soil health, hindering technological progress in this area.

Opportunities of soil health for local politics: Opportunities for soil health in local policy include the potential to improve the resilience of vineyard soils to climate change, which can improve overall agricultural sustainability. There is an opportunity for grape and vine associations to showcase research and innovation results to policy makers and local decision-makers, thereby fostering collaboration. In addition, alignment with the EU's "A Soil Deal for Europe" is a strategic advantage. The Living Lab research and innovation ecosystem can also provide valuable evidence to support the implementation of the Bulgarian Strategic Plan for Agriculture and Rural Development 2021-2027, promoting effective policies and practices in soil health management.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local politics: The costs of implementing sustainable soil practices through compensatory payments and financial support schemes can put a strain on public budgets, potentially leading to conflicts over resource allocation. Slow adoption of sustainable practices by farmers (e.g. only 10% adoption of conservation agriculture) risks policy failure and loss of political credibility. In addition, insufficient regional engagement and knowledge transfer can lead to implementation gaps and reduced political support at the local level. These challenges are compounded by past failed infrastructure projects, such as irrigation system improvements, which can undermine public confidence in soil health policies and lead to political backlash.

Economic Factors

Strengths of current economic actions for soil health: Current economic measures have several strengths in promoting soil health. These include the redesign of vineyard management plans to include sustainable soil practices such as mulching, plant cover, organic fertilisation, organic farming and conservation tillage. The measures also include the digitalisation of agricultural production processes, which improves efficiency and control. The use of mineral fertilisers and pesticides has been successfully reduced, promoting more environmentally friendly practices. In addition, the current economic framework has succeeded in creating market niches for organic grape growers, providing economic incentives for sustainable farming practices.

Weaknesses of current economic actions countering soil health: Current economic practices have two major weaknesses that have a negative impact on soil health. First, there is continued investment in heavy machinery that compacts the soil, reducing infiltration and water-holding capacity. Second, intensive farming practices reduce soil biodiversity and organic matter, leading to potential pollution and higher production costs. These practices illustrate how certain economic decisions work against soil health objectives and create additional environmental and financial challenges for farmers.

Opportunities of soil health for local economic development: Maintaining good soil health offers several promising economic opportunities. Improving soil quality through conservation tillage, management of organic matter and biodiversity, efficient water use and safe crop protection can significantly improve the productivity, quality and marketability of grapes and wine. These improvements can lead to increased competitiveness and higher incomes for grape producers. In addition, the transition to sustainable soil management practices can create new employment opportunities for marginalised rural groups, contributing to wider economic development in the region. By improving soil health, the region additionally mitigates economic risks caused by soil degradation. The combination of soil degradation, compaction and loss of organic matter and biodiversity, which are strongly influenced by climate change, can reduce both the productivity and quality of vineyards. This reduction in yield and quality directly affects the competitiveness and income potential of vineyards.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local economic development: The threat to soil health improvements and initiatives comes from the potential short-term costs and perceived lower yields associated with transitioning to more sustainable practices. While the long-term benefits are clear—improved soil health leads to better yields, quality and market access—the initial investment and potential temporary drop in production may deter some producers. Switching to sustainable practices such as organic farming, reducing chemical inputs and investing in soil-friendly machinery can require significant up-front investment, which can be a barrier for some producers. There are also risks in terms of demand and available market niches for sustainably produced wines: If there is not a strong market demand or premium price for sustainably produced grapes and wine, producers may lack the economic incentive to adopt soil health initiatives.

Social Factors

Strengths of social/community support for soil health: Few social or community factors supporting soil health were identified in the baseline analysis survey and literature. The Bulgarian Soil Science Society plays an active role in promoting soil conservation and land management through public events, conferences, and workshops. These initiatives aim to raise awareness of soil protection, highlighting a strong community interest in sustainable practices. Additionally, farmer-to-farmer learning, training, and exchange programmes within agricultural associations encourage practices that protect soil health, fostering collaboration and the adoption of more sustainable farming methods. These activities reflect a starting recognition of the importance of soil health within the local community.

Weaknesses of social/community activities countering soil health: There are several key weaknesses in social and community activities related to soil health. There are insufficient knowledge and dissemination structures to reach private vineyard growers and advisors on best practices for managing soil health. The local community does not effectively recycle organic matter from rural villages. There is also a lack of understanding within the community of the importance of maintaining soil health and implementing soil conservation practices. Additionally, there is also a growing reluctance among young people to live and work in rural areas, leading to capacity loss. Another

weakness is that some farmers are trying to generate income from vineyards independently, without joining cooperatives, and are struggling to find and apply soil conservation practices on their own.

Opportunities of soil health for local communities and social development: Soil health initiatives offer several opportunities for local communities and social development. Capacity-building efforts, such as training for farmers, agronomists, and researchers, will strengthen the local workforce and support vineyard producers in maintaining soil health. Healthier soils can enhance the quality and productivity of local wine production, benefiting the wider community. By improving the sustainability of wine production in the Thracian Valley, these initiatives can also create more job opportunities for rural marginalised groups, helping to counteract rural depopulation. Additionally, the reputational benefits for stakeholders involved in these soil health efforts could translate into increased political support at local, regional, and national levels.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local communities and social development: A major challenge in the wine-growing communities of the Plovdiv region is the human capital gap, characterised by farmers' lack of modern skills in precision technologies and a shortage of skilled agronomists. This is compounded by the reluctance of young people to pursue a career in agriculture. The region faces knowledge and capacity constraints, requiring additional efforts to build expertise across different stakeholder groups, from farmers to researchers. Behavioural and social barriers present a further layer of challenge. Local communities often fail to recognise the importance of maintaining soil health, leading to poor implementation of conservation practices and inadequate recycling of organic matter. The tendency of farmers to work individually rather than in cooperatives further hinders progress by limiting knowledge sharing and adoption of best practices. These interrelated challenges create a cycle in which limited expertise and isolated farming practices continue to have a negative impact on the development of sustainable agriculture.

Technological Factors

Strengths of current technologies for soil health: The technological strengths for soil health in the Plovdiv region include a range of biological, chemical, and mechanical technologies. Biological technologies involve the use of special crops, grass-clover mixtures, composted animal manure, and beneficial microorganisms to enhance soil health. Chemical and biochemical technologies rely on both artificial and natural fertilisers, pesticides, and herbicides to support soil fertility and manage pests. Electrical and electronic technologies such as meteorological stations, data processing applications, decision support systems, and unmanned aerial vehicles aid in effective monitoring and management of soil conditions. Additionally, mechanical technologies like precision drip irrigation and fertigation systems optimise water and nutrient delivery to crops. These technologies are complemented by skilled practices, with specialised knowledge and training in sustainable soil management enhancing their application and effectiveness.

Weaknesses of current technologies countering soil health: The current technological framework has several weaknesses in addressing soil health. There is insufficient knowledge and skills among farmers about new precision (digital) technologies, which is a barrier to adoption and leading to a reluctance of young people to work in rural areas. The region lacks adequate digital infrastructure for comprehensive soil monitoring and data collection. Many smallholders cannot afford modern soil management technologies and equipment. In addition, there is limited integration between different technological systems, making it difficult to create a unified approach to soil health management. Available technological solutions are often not adapted to local conditions and specific

vineyard management needs, reducing their effectiveness. These weaknesses create gaps in the technological capacity to effectively monitor and manage soil health.

Opportunities of novel technologies: The technological opportunities for soil health in the Plovdiv region include the development of digital precision models and decision support systems to optimise soil-water management and soil-plant interactions. Collaborating with local stakeholders to co-design, test, and validate agro-ecological conditions and practices in vineyards can enhance the adoption and implementation of sustainable practices. Additionally, training programmes to improve farmers' skills in using new digital precision technologies, including integrated decision support systems, offer further opportunities. Enhancing the technical skills of stakeholders such as agronomists and extension workers can improve communication and problem-solving related to soil health. The implementation of remote sensing and digital solutions for monitoring and managing soil conditions can also lead to better-informed decisions and more effective soil management practices.

Potential threats of novel technologies: New technologies pose risks to soil health if they are implemented unsustainably. These include in-row tillage practices that deplete nitrogen and phosphorus, leading to nutrient deficiencies. In addition, inappropriate tillage can lead to poor soil structure and reduced biodiversity, negatively affecting soil health.

Legal Factors

Strengths of current legal regulations for soil health: The regulatory framework supporting soil health in the Plovdiv region has several strengths. Firstly, mandatory waste management plans ensure proper collection, recycling and application of organic waste such as animal manure, which directly benefits soil health. Second, a national action programme focusing on sustainable land management and combating desertification underlines the commitment to soil health. Thirdly, the Ministry of Agriculture, supported by the Directorate of Waste Management and Soil Protection, is actively implementing a soil protection policy in line with EU and national legislation. This framework provides a clear structure for compliance, educates farmers on sustainable practices and promotes their adoption. In addition, the region benefits from alignment with EU regulations on soil protection and agricultural practices, established legal mechanisms for implementing the Strategic Plan for Agriculture and Rural Development (2021–2027), specific provisions for vineyard soil protection and management, and local ordinances supporting sustainable agriculture and soil protection. The legal structure also underpins organic farming certification and environmental protection measures, all of which are supported by monitoring and enforcement by regional agricultural authorities.

Weaknesses of current legal regulations countering soil health: Some of the legal shortcomings in the current legislation include challenges in balancing environmental regulations with production and marketing needs for wine producers, which may lead to resistance to necessary changes. Additionally, the lack of validated methods for determining soil parameters according to international standards complicates compliance and monitoring efforts. Beyond these issues, there are also insufficient incentives for farmers who actively maintain soil health, such as those engaged in organic matter composting, biodiversity conservation, or efficient irrigation practices. Furthermore, farmers, policymakers, and consumers often lack adequate training and education on soil health laws and regulations, which impedes effective implementation. Finally, there is inadequate knowledge transfer from universities and research organisations to farmers, resulting in gaps in understanding and the application of best practices.

Opportunities associated with legal regulations for soil health: The opportunities associated with the legal regulation of soil health in the Plovdiv region and in the South-Central wine belt as a whole include several key areas for improvement. An important opportunity is the involvement of legal stakeholders, such as legal experts and local authorities, in initiatives such as the Living Lab. This collaboration can help identify appropriate incentives for farmers who prioritise soil conservation, thereby promoting a more supportive legal environment. In addition, there is potential to develop comprehensive training and education programmes to improve farmers' understanding of soil health legislation and best practices. This can facilitate better compliance and adoption of sustainable practices. Building farmers' capacity to implement legal requirements without compromising production is also crucial. This approach can improve their ability to meet environmental standards while maintaining economic viability. Promoting the use of validated methods for soil and crop quality testing can also improve compliance and support sustainable agricultural practices.

Potential threats associated with legal regulations for soil health: Legal regulations for soil health face several risks. Inadequate or outdated methods for assessing soil parameters, potentially not aligned with international standards (EU regulations, or ISO standards), may lead to inconsistent assessments and enforcement. Implementation challenges can hinder farmers, potentially compromising production and marketing, creating conflict between compliance and economic viability. The cost of compliance can be prohibitive, especially for smallholders, deterring investment in soil health improvements. Finally, overly burdensome or impractical regulations may lead to non-compliance, undermining soil health efforts and causing environmental damage.

Environmental Factors

Strengths of the natural environment for soil health: A key strength is the improved air quality in the region, which has a positive impact on overall ecosystem health and supports soil vitality. The topographical advantages of the region also play a crucial role; vineyards located on sloping terrain help to reduce water run-off and erosion, promoting better water retention and soil stability. In addition, the presence of diverse plant species and beneficial soil organisms supports soil biodiversity, which is essential for maintaining soil health and fertility. In addition, many vineyards maintain grass between rows, which helps to retain soil moisture and prevent erosion, thereby improving soil conditions. Farmers in the area are increasingly turning to organic fertiliser and compost, which enrich soil fertility by adding essential nutrients and organic matter.

Weaknesses of the natural environment countering soil health: First, the region faces significant climate change impacts such as high temperatures, droughts, heat waves and excessive rainfall, all of which contribute to soil erosion and degradation. These climatic extremes can affect soil structure and reduce fertility. In addition, poor soil structure and low biodiversity are widespread problems as many areas suffer from inefficient land management practices that further degrade soil quality. The decline in soil organic matter, nitrogen and phosphorus levels due to unsustainable management practices exacerbates these problems and leads to lower agricultural productivity. Also, the lack of effective water management practices can result in inadequate moisture retention during dry periods, making soils more vulnerable to degradation.

Opportunities of soil health for the natural environment: Opportunities for soil health in the region's natural environment include the potential to mitigate climate change impacts, such as reducing the risks of heavy rainfall and flooding by improving soil's water absorption capacity. Additionally, involving environmental stakeholders in soil health research and co-creation fosters validation of methods that benefit both soil and broader environmental goals. This collaborative approach not only leads to environmental-friendly soil health solutions but also stimulates

innovation and further research on related environmental concerns, such as biodiversity preservation, water management, and ecosystem restoration, benefiting the region's natural systems overall.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for the natural environment: Soil health improvements have negative effects on the natural environment, which need to be considered when deciding on soil health solutions. For example, promoting optimal irrigation management can lead to stressing local resources and altering hydrological cycles. Increased use of organic fertilisers can lead to nutrient imbalances and eutrophication. Focusing on a single crop, such as grapes, can encourage monoculture practices, reducing biodiversity and ecosystem resilience. The use of compost can introduce invasive species or alter soil pH if not managed properly. The introduction of non-native vegetation can displace native plant species and alter ecosystem processes. In addition, prioritising crop productivity can lead to over-fertilisation and over-irrigation, compromising environmental sustainability.

Implications for stakeholder engagement and co-creation

The stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis provide valuable insights for stakeholder engagement and co-creation within the Bulgarian Living Lab. The stakeholder mapping offers specific recommendations on managing stakeholder groups, identifying which stakeholders to engage closely, which to keep satisfied, which to inform, and which to monitor. Complementing this, the baseline analysis highlights opportunities presented by soil health initiatives across political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental dimensions. These opportunities can serve as compelling arguments to involve relevant stakeholders in Living Lab activities. Simultaneously, the analysis identifies potential threats associated with a focus on soil health that may concern specific stakeholder groups. These concerns can be taken into account in communication strategies and incorporated into Living Lab solutions, ensuring project partners are equipped with clear responses to alleviate existing fears.

This section summarises initial strategies derived from the stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis, recommending different engagement levels—from active co-creation to low-maintenance interactions with peripheral entities. These recommendations will be further refined in collaboration with Living Lab leaders in the coming months, with a particular focus on substantiating and detailing planned co-creation sessions in a publicly accessible report.

Recommended strategies:

Active engagement through co-creation: Engaging core stakeholders in the Living Lab activities is pivotal to developing innovative, scientifically robust, practical, and locally accepted soil health solutions in the Bulgarian LL. Key stakeholders, particularly local farmers, farm advisors, research institutions, and technology partners hold high influence and exhibit high interest in the project outcomes. Their joint contributions can encompass refining the pre-selected solutions to be tested in the Bulgarian LL, planning and implementing solution testing, and monitoring, evaluating, and adapting tested solutions. Participation in co-creation sessions fosters a sense of ownership and ensures long-term commitment to the project's objectives, which is essential for its sustained impact. Special emphasis should be placed on engaging vine growers and research institutions. Actively involving them in co-creation not only enhances solution development but also raises awareness of soil health challenges and

empowers them to implement and develop effective solutions. Moreover, cultivating these relationships through regular consultations and tailored communication strategies is crucial, particularly for stakeholders unable to participate directly in co-creation activities.

Incentivise and Empower Economic Stakeholders: Economic stakeholders, especially vine growers, their advisors and associations, are pivotal to the Bulgarian living lab success. Engaging these associations requires emphasising the long-term economic benefits of improved soil health for viticulture. Empowering them through capacity-building initiatives, workshops, and consultation on financial, technological and administrative resources is equally important. Incentivised and empowered vine growers, advisors, and associations can play a pivotal role in disseminating tested solutions to a broader audience, providing guidance on securing funding, and advising on the practical implementation of these solutions. This dissemination is critical to extending the impact and knowledge gained from the Living Labs to a wider audience.

Highlighting economic benefits for young generations: Even though soil health initiatives offer several opportunities for local communities and social development, Bulgaria is currently facing a growing reluctance among young people to live and work in rural areas. By showcasing potential job opportunities, young generations could feel motivated to bring their capacity and talent to the project.

Enhance Representation of Political and Environmental Stakeholders: Although fewer in number, political and environmental stakeholders play a critical role in the project's success. Political stakeholders, such as municipalities and regional governments, provide governance frameworks that can either enable or hinder the adoption of sustainable practices. Engaging these entities more actively will ensure that policies and regulations support the initiative's objectives. Similarly, environmental stakeholders, such as public authorities overseeing water management and biodiversity, offer essential expertise in ecological considerations. Enhancing their representation and integrating their perspectives will help align economic and technological initiatives with environmental imperatives, addressing broader sustainability challenges. Furthermore, targeted policy advice based on Living Lab experience can motivate a mindset change in the current political and legal landscape leading to better policy support of soil health protection.

Leverage Technological Synergies: Collaboration between research institutions and innovation-driven stakeholders will be strengthened to promote the adoption of advanced precision agriculture tools and other technological advancements. These synergies can accelerate the deployment of remote sensing technologies, satellite data applications, and decision support systems, driving both productivity and sustainability in viticulture practices. This integration of technology into the Bulgarian Living Lab's framework will help address soil degradation and climate change vulnerabilities while fostering innovative solutions.

Raise Awareness for Soil Health Opportunities in the Community: A lack of awareness within the local community about the importance of soil health and conservation practices presents a current challenge in the Plovdiv region. The Living Lab provides an opportunity to bridge research and innovation with targeted awareness campaigns, showcasing the benefits of soil-friendly farming methods in an engaging and accessible manner. Highlighting the economic and social potential of sustainable soil health practices can inspire behavioural change and foster community interest.

Draw Insights from Comparable Contexts: Lessons from other initiatives will be further incorporated to enhance the project's approach across living labs. Specifically, the deployment of advanced technological solutions, such as satellite-based precision farming tools, and strategies to mitigate climate-related vulnerabilities offer valuable

insights. These practices can inform the design and execution of interventions in the Bulgarian Living Lab, ensuring that solutions are both context-specific and adaptable to broader challenges.

Greek Mining Soil Living Lab

Introduction

Overview of the Greek Mining Soil Living Lab's Objectives

This Greek Mining Soil Living Lab focuses on soil restoration and reclamation in post-lignite mining areas characterised by high levels of chromium and nickel. The project addresses the unique soil health challenges of these sites, recognising that different soils require tailored remediation processes at different rates. The Living Lab aims to identify the ideal approach for the restoration of opencast former lignite mining sites. Eleven co-created test sites (with the possibility of a twelfth Living Lab joining the project) will be used for collaborative research and development. The Living Lab is led by CluBE (Cluster of Bioeconomy and Environment of Western Macedonia) from Kozani, Greece. Key stakeholders include research institutions (University of Thessaly), companies (DIADYMA S.A.) and an NGO (New Agriculture for a New Generation). This collaboration will facilitate the development and testing of practical solutions. The solutions being explored focus on experimental planting and testing of different crops for feedstock, essential oil production and other non-food uses. The aim is to identify the most efficient crop types for soil restoration and eventual return to agricultural use. The Living Lab directly addresses the complex interactions between mining practices, land use and the long-term health of the soil ecosystem.

Geographical Location and Context

Western Macedonia is a region in northwestern Greece, covering 9,451 square kilometres, and is characterised by its mountainous terrain, with approximately 82% of the area being mountainous or semi-mountainous. According to the 2021 census, Western Macedonia has a population of approximately 254,595 people. Mining has historically been an important part of the region's economy, particularly through the extraction of lignite, which is a cornerstone of Greece's energy production. The region has been home to around 80% of the country's lignite industry for around 70 years. Lignite production has declined significantly, from 43.2 million tonnes in 2010 to just 10.3 million tonnes in 2020, due to the Greek government's decision to phase out lignite plants by 2028 (Pavloudakis et al. 2022). As a result of extensive lignite mining and the burning of lignite in power plants, soils in Western Macedonia, particularly in areas such as the Sarigkiol Basin, are contaminated with potentially toxic elements (PTEs) such as chromium, nickel and arsenic (Psarraki et al. 2023). The contamination and alteration of soil properties have led to reduced soil fertility, which negatively affects agricultural productivity. The degradation of soil quality has also increased the risk of erosion. The rehabilitation of the Western Macedonian mining landscapes poses significant challenges, including the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil, which have been adversely affected by mining activities.

Stakeholder Mapping Results

The Greek Living Lab (LL) showcases a diverse stakeholder landscape comprising 61 actors from various sectors, including economic, technological, environmental, political, legal, and social backgrounds. This analysis explores the key stakeholder dynamics and their implications for the success of the project.

The economic sector, with 26 stakeholders, plays a central role in the Greek LL, with 9 stakeholders identified as high interest and high influence actors (manage closely). These include horticulture farms, forestry enterprises, soil monitoring companies, training facilitators, and woodworking industry actors. Nine high-interest, high-influence economic actors face challenges such as limited land availability and poor soil quality, which directly affect productivity and profitability. The LL offers critical solutions, including reduced production costs, sustainable sourcing practices, and a more resilient supply chain. Additional benefits include the development of sustainable agricultural practices, biodiversity conservation, and soil restoration, positioning these stakeholders as primary beneficiaries of the project. Their close management ensures alignment with project goals and fosters robust participation.

The 14 technological stakeholders identified include four key players with high interest and influence, all rooted in research and innovation. Their focus on soil health provides a natural avenue for engagement. By participating in the LL, these stakeholders contribute to enhanced data analysis and knowledge sharing, enriching the project's outcomes. Their involvement is pivotal in integrating cutting-edge solutions and fostering innovation within the LL.

Environmental actors account for 12 stakeholders, with 8 ranked as “manage closely.” These include NGOs, environmental innovation actors, and landowners of former lignite mines. Their involvement in the LL allows them to directly engage in testing and refining sustainable agricultural practices, contributing to soil restoration and environmental conservation. Their active participation underscores the LL's potential to align environmental objectives with broader sustainability goals, making them key partners in achieving project success.

Among the eight political stakeholders, four are recommended for close management, including municipalities and public authorities. These actors play a critical role in promoting innovative agricultural practices in the LL area. Their participation provides valuable insights into policy development and fosters cross-sectoral collaboration, vital for scaling sustainable solutions. One public authority focusing on innovation is ranked as “keep informed” ensuring they remain aware of developments while maintaining lower engagement levels.

The sole legal stakeholder, a public authority with a forestry focus, holds high interest and influence. Their involvement in the LL is crucial, particularly in shaping regulations and ensuring sustainable forestry practices. Managing this stakeholder closely can enhance policy alignment and project impact.

The social sector is represented by a single stakeholder with low influence and interest, reflecting limited engagement opportunities. However, occasional updates may keep them informed of broader developments.

Figure 6: Greek Living Lab - Stakeholder Map

The stakeholder mapping analysis for the Greek Living Lab underscores the intricate and mutually reinforcing relationships between key sectors in the region of the former lignite mines. As shown in Figure 6, central to this dynamic is the collaboration between the political, economic, environmental, and technological sectors, which collectively drive the success of soil restoration and sustainable land-use initiatives.

Landowners of the former lignite mines provide the crucial operating space for soil restoration activities, while the wood and horticulture industries, which depend on soil quality, are directly impacted by the degraded and contaminated soils. These economic actors face significant challenges but also stand to benefit greatly from the project through improved soil health and more sustainable production practices.

Research and innovation stakeholders in the technological sector play a critical role by introducing new technologies and agricultural practices that can enhance both yields and biodiversity. Their expertise provides valuable support to the economic actors, offering pathways for innovation and improvement that are essential for the long-term viability of the region’s industries.

Local municipalities and public authorities have significant roles in promoting innovative practices and creating regulatory frameworks that support the LL’s goals. The involvement of two municipalities in particular enhances the LL’s connection to regional governance and public policy, ensuring that soil health restoration aligns with broader

regional development objectives. The public forestry authority's regulatory impact on the wood industry highlights the importance of aligning environmental and regulatory frameworks to foster sustainable land use and industry growth.

Public authorities for innovation are also pivotal in fostering cross-sectoral collaboration, which could facilitate long-term partnerships and knowledge exchange among the economic, technological, and environmental actors. Their role in connecting stakeholders across sectors will be instrumental in ensuring that the LL's efforts not only succeed in the short term but also lay the foundation for sustained, collaborative efforts in the future.

Overall, this interconnected stakeholder landscape provides a robust foundation for the success of the Greek Living Lab, with each sector contributing vital resources, knowledge, and support that will enable the region to overcome its soil degradation challenges and transition towards more sustainable agricultural practices.

Power-interest Matrix

The power-interest matrix for the Greek Living Lab reveals a highly interconnected landscape where economic, political, environmental, and technological stakeholders all play pivotal roles in ensuring the project's success.

Figure 7: Greek Living Lab - Power-Interest Matrix

Manage closely- High Power, High Interest: Wood and horticulture industries are highly influenced by soil quality and land availability, making them directly invested in the success of the project. Their active participation is crucial, and their needs must be closely managed. The degraded soil conditions limit their productive capacity, and

the project offers them the opportunity for more sustainable sourcing practices, higher yields, and improved resilience. Regular consultations and co-development of sustainable agricultural practices are vital strategies for engaging these stakeholders. Research institutions, particularly those focused on soil restoration and agricultural innovation, hold both high interest and high influence in the Greek Living Lab. Their expertise in developing new technologies and practices directly supports the economic actors and facilitates the transition to more sustainable land use. Engaging them in co-created initiatives and knowledge exchange platforms will be essential for ensuring continuous innovation and integration of best practices. The involvement of the municipalities and public authorities for innovation is also essential for promoting cross-sectoral collaboration and fostering long-term partnerships. These stakeholders have significant regulatory influence and can support the creation of frameworks that encourage the integration of innovative practices in agriculture. Their engagement is pivotal for ensuring policy alignment with project goals, and active management will help ensure that these authorities remain aligned with the project's objectives.

Keep satisfied- High Power, Low Interest: Public Forestry Authority: Although this authority holds significant regulatory power over the wood industry, its interest in actively working on soil health or reclamation is uncertain. This stakeholder plays a key role in shaping the regulatory environment for forestry activities, which can directly impact the success of the Greek Living Lab. Tailored engagement strategies, such as demonstrating the alignment of the project with broader regulatory goals for sustainable land use and biodiversity conservation, will be necessary to maintain their involvement. Periodic updates and consultations on the potential regulatory benefits of the project could help ensure their support.

Keep informed - Low Power, High Interest: Environmental NGOs and Interest Groups: Environmental stakeholders have a strong vested interest in the project's success, particularly in relation to the restoration of biodiversity and the reduction of contamination in former lignite mining areas. While they may lack the regulatory or financial power of other sectors, their support is invaluable for enhancing public awareness, advocacy, and the overall environmental impact of the project. Providing opportunities for these stakeholders to actively engage in the development and testing of sustainable agricultural approaches will amplify their contributions and increase the project's visibility.

Monitor - Low Power, Low Interest: Local businesses and service providers while peripheral to the project's core objectives, still play supportive roles. Although their direct interest or influence in the Greek Living Lab may be limited, they can contribute to the success of the project by providing services, resources, or indirect support. Low-maintenance engagement strategies, such as periodic newsletters, informational updates, or invitations to broader project events, will ensure that these stakeholders remain informed and engaged without demanding significant resources.

Baseline Analysis: Local Ecosystems of the Living Lab

Introduction

Western Macedonia faces complex soil health management challenges, with an initial assessment revealing interrelated factors influencing environmental restoration efforts. The region shows varying levels of development across the six PESTLE dimensions, creating a nuanced landscape for soil health initiatives.

Living Lab leaders were asked to rate PESTLE influences on a scale from -5 (strong negative influence) to +5 (strong positive influence). These ratings are presented here as they offer a valuable overview for the analysis:

Political support shows strong positive momentum (rated +3), supported by the European Green Deal and the Greek National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), although implementation faces challenges from overlapping authorities and competing regional interests. Business initiatives show modest progress (rated +1), supported by the Just Transition Mechanism, but constrained by resource limitations and transition costs from traditional industries.

Civil society engagement is exceptional (rated +5), characterised by active community participation, strong NGO presence and established local knowledge networks. Technological capacity makes a positive contribution (rated +3), with advanced remediation technologies and monitoring systems such as Geographic Information System (GIS) based analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Spectroscopy.

The regulatory framework is neutral (rated 0), balancing comprehensive EU and national environmental legislation with enforcement challenges and legislative gaps. Current soil health conditions show slight improvement (rated +1), reflecting successful rehabilitation efforts while acknowledging contamination and erosion challenges.

This rating indicates both promising progress and critical areas requiring attention in Western Macedonia's soil health management strategy. Strong civil society engagement and technological capacity provide a foundation for addressing the region's environmental challenges, while economic and regulatory frameworks offer opportunities for improvement.

Political Factors

Strengths of current political actions and policies for soil health: Western Macedonia shows commitment to environmental protection and sustainable development. The Greek government's target to phase out all lignite power plants by 2028, with most units already phased out since 2023, constitutes an important step in reducing the region's reliance on polluting industries and promoting a low-carbon economy. The European Green Deal and the Just Transition Mechanism provide crucial funding and support to coal-dependent regions such as Western Macedonia, enabling the implementation of initiatives aimed at environmental rehabilitation, sustainable agriculture and clean energy development. The region's Territorial Plan for the Just and Developmental Transition of Western Macedonia serves as a key policy instrument, outlining measures for environmental rehabilitation and land reclamation, as well as the transformation of former mining sites into productive or recreational land. In addition, Greece's National Energy and Climate Plan (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment and Energy (2019)) sets clear environmental targets and provides a framework for the country's transition to a low-carbon economy, including measures to promote sustainable land use and soil health. National legislation, such as the Law on Environmental Protection, provides a robust framework for addressing soil health issues, although gaps and inconsistencies in implementation remain. Local authorities and stakeholders in Western Macedonia, CluBE as an

example, have launched various initiatives and projects to promote soil health, including reclamation and reforestation efforts, sustainable agricultural practices and phytoremediation techniques. The involvement of research institutions, such as the University of Western Macedonia, in supporting these efforts through partnerships and knowledge dissemination further strengthens the region's capacity to address soil health challenges.

Weaknesses of current political actions and policies countering soil health: Despite the progress made in promoting soil health in Western Macedonia, several weaknesses in current policies and practices hinder the effective protection and restoration of the region's soils. One of the main problems is the lack of comprehensive soil protection legislation, which leads to confusion and inefficiency in enforcement, as different authorities have overlapping or unclear responsibilities. The implementation of rehabilitation programmes has been delayed due to bureaucratic inefficiencies and financial constraints, resulting in continued soil degradation in unrehabilitated areas. In addition, the rapid phase out of lignite activities poses significant challenges for the region, including the potential for economic decline, job losses and social impacts that may undermine the effectiveness of soil health policies. Conflicts over land use, such as prioritising agricultural development or forest restoration, have also affected the effectiveness of soil health policies. In addition, the inconsistent application of environmental regulations and the lack of effective enforcement mechanisms have hampered progress in restoring degraded land and promoting soil health. Most of the land belongs to the Power Plant Company. The administrative inefficiencies, transparency issues, and governance challenges have historically plagued environmental governance in Greece also pose a risk to the effective implementation of soil health policies in Western Macedonia.

Opportunities of soil health for local politics: Improvements in soil health present valuable opportunities for local political development in Western Macedonia, especially during its phase out of lignite mining and transition to a low-carbon economy. Enhancing soil health can increase agricultural productivity, promote land rehabilitation, and improve local ecosystems, thus supporting sustainable economic development. Strengthening land management and sustainable farming practices can also create new employment opportunities, particularly for communities affected by the phase out of lignite mining. This shift towards sustainable agriculture can foster social stability, increase public trust in local governance, and reduce inequalities. Moreover, better soil management can mitigate the impacts of climate change, such as reduced fertility and water availability, helping the region adapt to changing weather patterns. Successful soil health initiatives can also position the region as a model for environmental and energy transition, improving its public image and attracting additional EU funding and support, while promoting innovative environmental policies.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local politics: The implementation of stricter environmental regulations to improve soil health can lead to inter-regional conflicts, pitting industrial interests against those advocating sustainable practices. Bureaucratic inefficiencies and funding constraints can further complicate matters, causing delays in the implementation of soil health programmes and undermining public trust in political institutions. Powerful vested interests linked to existing industries may actively resist changes that prioritise soil health and environmental protection through lobbying, political campaigns and legal challenges. In addition, the potential danger of failing to meet EU environmental standards on soil health in the required timeframe, can lead to increased scrutiny, potential sanctions and pressure on national governments to improve their performance, straining relations with international bodies. Finally, competing demands for land use, such as prioritising agriculture over forest restoration to improve soil health, can lead to political conflict and complicate decision-making processes. An uneven distribution of benefits from these initiatives can also exacerbate existing inequalities, leading to further political tensions and demands for more equitable solutions.

Economic Factors

Strengths of current economic actions for soil health: Western Macedonia has made significant progress in supporting soil health, especially during its transition to a low-carbon economy. Key strengths include financial support from the Just Transition Mechanism and the Greek National Energy and Climate Plan, which allocate funds for environmental restoration, sustainable agriculture, and reforestation. Reclamation of former mining sites aids soil restoration by planting native species, improving soil structure, increasing organic matter, and enhancing biodiversity. Growing economic diversification, including sustainable tourism and agrotourism, promotes soil health and preserves local biodiversity. The renewable energy sector's growth, especially solar and wind, reduces dependence on fossil fuels. Sustainable forest management, such as selective and controlled logging, helps maintain soil quality and healthy ecosystems. Furthermore, sustainable agricultural practices, such as organic farming and agroforestry, enhance soil health, improve water retention, reduce erosion, and increase biodiversity. The region's skilled workforce and research institutions support ongoing innovation and sustainable practices.

Weaknesses of current economic actions countering soil health: Mining operations in Western Macedonia are a major source of soil degradation, causing significant erosion and contamination. The use of heavy machinery for mining reduces soil porosity, impairing its ability to retain water and nutrients, which in turn diminishes soil fertility and biodiversity. Additionally, the chemicals involved in mining, such as heavy metals and acids, further contaminate the soil, negatively impacting both agricultural productivity and local ecosystems. The region's economic challenges, such as limited diversification and the potential for job losses due to the mining phase out, further hinder efforts to promote sustainable agricultural practices. The mixed impact of the Common Agricultural Policy can encourage intensive farming methods, which often damage soil health. There is also a lack of funding and resources for soil protection, compounded by bureaucratic inefficiencies, an ageing population, out-migration, and limited technical knowledge and digital infrastructure for farmers.

Opportunities of soil health for local economic development: Promoting soil health in Western Macedonia presents opportunities for local economic development, especially during the region's transition to a low-carbon economy. Healthy soils can increase agricultural productivity, raise land values, and make the region more resilient to the impacts of climate change, such as soil erosion and water scarcity. Furthermore, healthy soils are key for promoting alternative economic activities like sustainable agriculture and eco-tourism, which support both local businesses and biodiversity. Reclamation and reforestation of former mining sites can restore soil health and open avenues for new industries, such as soil remediation services. Additionally, investing in soil health enhances the region's reputation, improving its brand and attracting international collaboration on soil reclamation initiatives. This fosters knowledge exchange, further stimulating economic opportunities tied to sustainable land use.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local economic development: Post-mining regions face a tough balancing act: environmental restoration versus economic revitalisation. While crucial for long-term sustainability, soil improvements must be strategically implemented to avoid hindering economic recovery. Land use conflicts arise as restoration competes with immediate development needs, exemplified by Western Macedonia's debates prioritising agriculture over forest restoration. Limited land availability due to restoration further complicates new projects. Resource allocation poses another challenge, as rehabilitation costs potentially divert funds from urgent job creation. Finally, environmental regulations and soil protection measures can cover vast areas, restricting their use for other opportunities.

Social Factors

Strengths of social/community support for soil health: Western Macedonia benefits from strong community support for soil health, a critical element of sustainable development. There is an established network of community workshops and educational programmes, alongside grassroots support for various environmental initiatives. Community-led projects such as community gardens and green spaces promote soil health, biodiversity and a sense of shared responsibility for the environment. Environmental education in local schools and institutions raises awareness of soil health and sustainable development. Strong cultural ties to the land and traditional farming practices passed down through generations provide valuable expertise and promote sustainable land use. Existing social infrastructure, including community centres, cooperatives and local organisations, provides a foundation for community-led initiatives and social entrepreneurship. Research institutes and universities provide technical expertise and resources. Funding from the European Green Deal and the Just Transition Mechanism supports these initiatives, promoting soil health, restoring degraded land and fostering sustainable economic development. Finally, a strong sense of community and social cohesion encourages collective action and cooperation on soil health initiatives, which are essential to address environmental challenges and promote sustainable development.

Weaknesses of social/community activities countering soil health: While there is community support for soil health in Western Macedonia, several weaknesses hinder its effective promotion. Limited awareness and understanding of soil health issues within the community makes it difficult to mobilise collective action. The region's long-standing dependence on lignite mining creates cultural and economic resistance to the transition to sustainable development, and the potential job losses associated with the industry's phase out can strain community cohesion and cooperation. An ageing population and the risk of out-migration due to high unemployment pose challenges for community-led initiatives and social entrepreneurship. Limited resources, including funding, expertise and infrastructure, further hamper these efforts. Ineffective communication and collaboration between government, local communities and the private sector, as well as potential conflicts of interest, create additional obstacles. Limited information about education and training programmes in sustainable agriculture, environmental conservation and social entrepreneurship limits the uptake of these programs and therewith the development of the necessary skills and knowledge.

Opportunities of soil health for local communities and social development: Promoting soil health in Western Macedonia offers valuable opportunities for local communities and social development. Healthy soils contribute to sustainable agriculture, bolstering food security and enhancing community well-being. Additionally, soil health incentives can stimulate community-led initiatives and social entrepreneurship, leveraging the region's strong sense of community. Addressing the legacy of lignite mining and soil contamination, such initiatives can also mitigate risks like water and air pollution, promoting public health. Furthermore, sustainable soil management prevents community displacement.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local communities and social development: While environmentally beneficial, soil health initiatives in Western Macedonia might be considered to pose a socio-economic threat to lignite-dependent communities. Job losses are likely, affecting lignite workers who lack restoration skills. With 21,000 jobs at risk, equivalent opportunities are uncertain. Landscape changes could disrupt community identities linked to industrial history. Land use conflicts may arise, leading to tensions over access and competing needs. Social inequality could increase, disproportionately affecting low-income households, the elderly, youth and communities dependent on lignite. Successful implementation will require addressing these social impacts and ensuring community support and cohesion during the transition.

Technological Factors

Strengths of current technologies for soil health: Current technologies provide tools for enhancing soil health and reclaiming degraded lands. Phytoremediation techniques, which use specific plant species to absorb toxic metals like lead, cadmium, and zinc, are effective in restoring soil fertility and stabilising contaminated soils. Tree planting, the cultivation of selected plants and intercropping also aid in stabilising terrain and extracting heavy metals in coal mining regions. Mechanical reshaping and soil compaction play a critical role in land reclamation, preventing erosion and stabilising post-mining landscapes. Labour-intensive practices, such as removing contaminated topsoil and replacing it with clean soil, combined with land reshaping, allow for ecological or agricultural reuse. Additionally, reclaimed lands are being repurposed for photovoltaic solar parks, providing sustainable energy solutions while ensuring these areas are utilised without further soil degradation. For an even better outcome, agrivoltaics systems can be used.

Weaknesses of current technologies countering soil health: Mining operations in Western Macedonia have significantly impacted soil quality through multiple mechanisms. Heavy machinery operations have compacted soil structures, compromising their natural porosity and capacity to retain water and essential nutrients. This physical degradation is compounded by chemical contamination, particularly from heavy metals and acidic compounds used in industrial processes. The management of industrial byproducts, especially fly ash from power generation, has introduced additional contamination challenges. These combined effects have created a complex pattern of soil degradation that extends beyond the immediate mining areas, affecting both ecosystem function and agricultural potential in the broader region.

Opportunities of novel technologies: Novel technologies offer opportunities to improve soil health through advanced monitoring, analysis, and innovative remediation strategies. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) enhance soil mapping and understanding of land characteristics, while Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) analysis enables precise monitoring of contamination, facilitating targeted reclamation efforts. Remote sensing technologies provide comprehensive land-use assessments, complemented by digital soil sampling and testing infrastructures for data-driven decision-making. Collaboration with research institutions promotes the development and testing of region-specific solutions, integrating traditional knowledge with cutting-edge technology to enrich restoration strategies. Engaging technological stakeholders, including universities, research bodies, and environmental technology firms, fosters innovation and supports the creation of advanced soil remediation tools. These opportunities not only enhance soil health but also contribute to sustainable land management, benefiting both local ecosystems and communities.

Potential threats of novel technologies: Renewable energy projects, such as solar farms, may cause soil compaction, though sustainable management practices like integrating vegetation can reduce impacts on soil health. Mechanical reshaping of landscapes and soil compaction, commonly used in land reclamation efforts, can also negatively affect soil structure. In addition, there may be unforeseen interactions between different remediation methods and technical failures in the containment of contamination. Implementation issues of novel technologies further complicate the situation, such as the risk of technology obsolescence in long-term projects and compatibility issues with existing systems.

Legal Factors

Strengths of current legal regulations for soil health: The legal framework to support soil health in Western Macedonia draws its strength from three key areas: national legislation, regional mechanisms and EU legal support. At the national level, Greece has a robust environmental protection regime, anchored in Law 1650/1986 (FAO, 2023), which establishes the basic principles of environmental protection and conservation. This law, in conjunction with environmental impact assessments for mining activities, creates a comprehensive system for monitoring and controlling industrial impacts on land. The national framework also includes specific requirements for land rehabilitation, ensuring that companies take responsibility for restoring degraded landscapes. Regional legal mechanisms further strengthen soil protection through the Territorial Plan for Fair and Developmental Transition of Western Macedonia (cf. World Bank, 2020), which provides a structured approach to environmental management at the local level. This is complemented by detailed local environmental bylaws and regulations that address specific regional challenges. The region has established an effective legal framework for land use planning and maintains a systematic environmental permitting system that regulates development activities that affect soil quality. The legal framework is significantly strengthened by EU-level regulations. The EU Industrial Emissions Directive provides key standards and controls for industrial activities that affect soil quality. This is reinforced by the broader framework of the EU Soil Strategy, which provides guidance and requirements for soil protection.

Weaknesses of current legal regulations countering soil health: The legal framework governing soil health in Western Macedonia faces three primary weaknesses. First, legislative gaps create significant challenges, particularly the absence of comprehensive soil protection legislation and fragmented regulatory responsibilities. Enforcement presents the second major challenge, characterised by inconsistent application of regulations and overlapping jurisdictions between authorities. Limited resources for monitoring compliance, combined with complex bureaucratic procedures, further hamper effective enforcement of existing laws. Administrative inefficiencies constitute the third weakness. The enforcement of environmental regulations in Greece has been inconsistent, particularly in regions like Western Macedonia, due to varying political priorities, lack of resources, and occasional administrative inefficiencies.

Opportunities associated with legal regulations for soil health: The EU's Soil Strategy for 2030 and the potential for new regulations from the EU to address soil health issues present opportunities for Greece to strengthen its legal framework and enforcement mechanisms. Regional politicians may also be pressured to implement more strict environmental regulations to address soil health concerns, leading to increased collaboration and tension between regions that rely on mining and those advocating for sustainable practices. Participation in the iCOSHHELLS' Living Lab can also help stakeholders stay ahead of regulatory changes and benefit from potential incentives for sustainable practices, while also allowing them to influence policy-making and advocate for supportive regulations that benefit the Living Lab's goals.

Potential threats associated with legal regulations for soil health: The inconsistent application of environmental regulations presents a significant challenge in the region's soil restoration efforts. Political dynamics often create tension between immediate economic priorities and long-term environmental goals, particularly in areas traditionally dependent on mining activities. This balancing act is further complicated by administrative processes, including environmental impact assessments, which can delay crucial rehabilitation work. While these procedures are essential for ensuring proper environmental protection, their lengthy nature sometimes allows soil degradation to progress while awaiting necessary approvals and implementation. The situation is particularly evident in former mining areas, where delays in rehabilitation can lead to continued soil erosion and contamination issues.

Environmental Factors

Strengths of the natural environment for soil health: The local natural environment in the region supports soil health. Its favourable climate, with warm summers, adequate autumn rainfall, and winter snowfall, sustains a balanced four-season cycle crucial for maintaining soil fertility and ecosystem functionality. This climate creates ideal conditions for sustainable agriculture and forestry practices, which enhance soil structure, retain nutrients, and reduce erosion. The availability of high-quality ground and surface water further benefits soil health, supporting moisture levels necessary for healthy microbial activity and plant growth.

Weaknesses of the natural environment countering soil health: The local natural environment faces several weaknesses impacting soil health. The climate crisis is disrupting ecological systems, altering biodiversity, nutrient cycling, and overall ecosystem health. The region is experiencing more frequent extreme weather events, such as rising temperatures and unpredictable rainfall patterns. These changes increase soil moisture fluctuations, contributing to prolonged droughts and intense rainfall, which significantly raise the risk of soil erosion, particularly in already vulnerable areas. Erosion leads to the loss of vital nutrients, further impairing soil fertility and productivity. Additionally, reduced biodiversity, caused by a decline in soil microbes and nutrients, hampers essential ecosystem functions like soil structure maintenance and water regulation. These challenges threaten the balance of local ecosystems, undermining efforts to promote sustainable agriculture and forestry practices.

Opportunities of soil health for the natural environment: Opportunities for soil health in the local natural environment include targeted restoration initiatives that enhance climate resilience through drought-resistant landscaping, which supports ecological function. Soil reclamation can restore vital topsoil, crucial for plant growth and ecosystem stability. This helps mitigate biodiversity loss from mining, re-establishing habitats and improving the natural environment. Improving soil health also reduces water pollution risks by preventing contaminants like heavy metals from leaching into groundwater and surface water. By enhancing soil health, the region can address the ongoing pollution challenges, including groundwater contamination, dust, and air pollution. Soil degradation exacerbates biodiversity loss, facilitates invasive species, and disrupts ecosystems, threatening environmental resilience and resource sustainability. Soil restoration efforts help counter these risks, promoting long-term ecological stability and resource sustainability.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for the natural environment: The rapid implementation of soil health initiatives, driven by the 2028 phase out of lignite, may pose several transitional environmental risks. Remediation efforts may be inadequate to address complex ecological needs, potentially disrupting ecosystems adapted to post-mining conditions and impeding natural recovery processes. Land use changes on former mining sites could disrupt existing biodiversity, eliminate unique industrial ecological niches and alter local hydrology during rehabilitation. Conflicts may also arise between different restoration objectives, such as forest versus agricultural development. In addition, new clean energy projects may risk degrading microclimates and biodiversity in rehabilitated areas, competing with natural habitat restoration. Finally, intensive water use for restoration, soil compaction from equipment, erosion during the transition period and potential contamination from mismanaged soils are additional environmental concerns.

Implications for stakeholder engagement and co-creation

The stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis provide valuable insights for stakeholder engagement and co-creation within the Greek Living Lab. The stakeholder mapping offers specific recommendations on managing stakeholder groups, identifying which stakeholders to engage closely, which to keep satisfied, which to inform, and which to monitor. Complementing this, the baseline analysis highlights opportunities presented by soil health initiatives across political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental dimensions. These opportunities can serve as compelling arguments to involve relevant stakeholders in Living Lab activities. Simultaneously, the analysis identifies potential threats associated with a focus on soil health that may concern specific stakeholder groups. These concerns can be taken into account in communication strategies and incorporated into Living Lab solutions, ensuring project partners are equipped with clear responses to alleviate existing fears.

This section summarises initial strategies derived from the stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis, recommending different engagement levels—from active co-creation to low-maintenance interactions with peripheral entities. These recommendations will be further refined in collaboration with Living Lab leaders in the coming months, with a particular focus on substantiating and detailing planned co-creation sessions in a publicly accessible report.

Recommended strategies:

Active engagement through co-creation: stakeholders, such as landowners, key players in the wood and horticulture industries, and research institutions, are central to the success of the Greek Living Lab. These stakeholders not only have significant influence over the project's direction but also possess a strong interest in its outcomes. To effectively engage them, the project should prioritise co-creating solutions with these groups. Their contributions can encompass generating new ideas for restoring soil health, refining pre-selected solutions, planning and implementing solution testing, and monitoring, evaluating, and adapting tested solutions. Participation in co-creation sessions also fosters a sense of ownership and ensures long-term commitment to the project's objectives, which is essential for its sustained impact and funding. Research institutions, in particular, can play a pivotal role by offering innovative technologies and practices that may improve soil quality and increase agricultural yields. By maintaining continuous communication, progress updates, and direct discussions, the iCOSHELLS project can ensure that these stakeholders remain actively involved.

Strategic Alignment: Although stakeholders such as public authorities (municipalities, forestry authorities, and government bodies) have the power to significantly influence the project's trajectory, their direct interest in the project may be limited. For these groups, it is crucial to align the objectives of the Greek Living Lab with broader policy goals and regional priorities. Framing the project as a contribution to sustainability, economic regeneration, and environmental restoration could help demonstrate its alignment to their regulatory goals for sustainable land use and biodiversity conservation. To maintain their engagement, the project should provide regular, high-level updates that focus on how it aligns with government policies, addresses regional issues, and offers long-term benefits. By ensuring that their interests and concerns are considered, the project can maintain their support and avoid potential roadblocks.

Highlight potential individual and communal benefits: Local communities in the Living Lab area are undergoing a significant transformation due to the phase out of lignite mining. Soil health initiatives can provide these

communities with new prospects for the future. However, since transformation often feels threatening to individuals, it is crucial to emphasise the potential benefits of the project. These include improved social and economic opportunities at both individual and community levels. For example, alternative economic activities, such as sustainable agriculture and eco-tourism, can create new pathways for growth and resilience.

Empowering Local Champions: The low power, high interest stakeholders, such as local farm suppliers and small businesses, may not have the influence to shape the project's direction, but they are highly motivated to contribute. Engaging these stakeholders requires providing them with the knowledge, and resources needed to actively participate in the project. The LL will enable these stakeholders to participate to regular consultations while direct involvement in the localised pilot projects will further empower them, providing a platform for hands-on engagement. By recognizing their contributions and ensuring they have a voice in project discussions, the Greek Living Lab can cultivate their commitment and strengthen their role in achieving the project's goals. This support will also help build the resilience and sustainability of the project by empowering a broader range of local actors.

Maintaining Light Touch with Low Power, Low Interest Stakeholders: While stakeholders in the low power, low interest quadrant may have limited influence or direct interest in the project, they still play a role in its overall success. These stakeholders, such as peripheral entities or marginal industry players, can contribute resources, insights, or support in less direct ways. The engagement strategy for these stakeholders should be low-maintenance but consistent, ensuring that they remain informed and aligned with the project's progress without requiring significant resources. Periodic updates through newsletters, community briefings, or public information sessions will help keep them aware of the project's objectives and outcomes. This ensures they are engaged enough to contribute, should their interest or capacity to participate increase over time. Additionally, monitoring their involvement for any shifts in interest or influence will allow for adaptive engagement strategies if their role in the project evolves.

Bridging Sectors! Strengthening Cross-Sector Collaboration: Cross-sectoral collaboration is a critical component for the success of the Greek Living Lab, particularly among stakeholders from the environmental, technological, and economic sectors. To strengthen this collaboration, the Living Lab will facilitate regular dialogues between these groups, encouraging knowledge exchange and joint initiatives. Research institutions and technology providers should work closely with the wood and horticulture industries to pilot innovative solutions and demonstrate their benefits in real-world scenarios. Public authorities focused on innovation should be encouraged to support these cross-sectoral efforts, as they can help streamline the integration of new technologies and practices into the local industries. These efforts will not only ensure the project's success but also help establish a foundation for long-term cooperation and knowledge-sharing between the different sectors involved, ultimately contributing to the sustainability and scalability of the project.

Boost effective communication within cross-sector collaboration: Stakeholders from various sectors are expected to be engaged through the project. Therefore, it is essential to use neutral and inclusive language that ensures clarity, fosters motivation, and makes all participants feel welcome. This approach should also emphasise both the responsibilities and opportunities stakeholders will gain by participating in the project.

Italian Soil Health Living Lab

Introduction

Overview of the Italian Soil Health Living Lab's Objectives

This Italian Soil Health Living Lab addresses a range of soil health challenges across diverse agricultural, orchard, and urban landscapes. Its research agenda encompasses issues such as soil carbon loss, urban soil sealing and pollution, poor soil structure, and biodiversity decline. A total of 13 co-created experimental sites will be utilised for research and development purposes. The Living Lab is led by the Rome based research institute ISINNOVA. Key partners include research institutions, such as Università degli Studi di Trento, Politecnico di Milano, Università degli Studi di Milano, and Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, as well as public authorities, including the Comune di Oppeano. Furthermore, the consortium includes a number of other key partners, such as the Parco Regionale del Mincio, RUMA Srl, and a diverse range of other stakeholders, including representatives from multi-level governments, farmers' associations, agronomists, landscape architects, IT companies, civil society organisations, artists, educational institutions, and students. The solutions under investigation include drip irrigation, remote-control systems for water management, satellite data integration for precision agriculture, and experimental crop testing. It is anticipated that these solutions will result in improved soil health, increased agricultural productivity and sustainability, and enhanced urban green spaces.

Geographical Location and Context

The Italian Living Lab is located in Northern Italy, mainly in the regions of Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol and Lombardy, with individual experimental sites in the neighbouring provinces of Emilia-Romagna and Veneto. Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol is defined by its alpine landscape. The region is predominantly mountainous, with peaks often exceeding 900 metres. In addition to the towering peaks, the interior of the region features high plateaus, creating a diverse environment that supports unique ecosystems. Water is a defining feature, with the Adige River carving its way through the mountains, influencing both the local climate and landforms. Lombardy features more varied geographical profile. While its northern reaches share the Alpine terrain, the region extends southwards into the fertile Po Valley. This plain, formed by the Po River, is an important agricultural area and contrasts sharply with the mountainous north. The Po river crosses Lombardy and plays a vital role in the region's agricultural productivity and overall economy, serving as a transport artery and a source of irrigation. While Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol is more rural (1.1 million inhabitants), Lombardy is more urban, with a population of around 10 million. Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol has a transitional climate, combining subcontinental and alpine influences, resulting in cold winters and warm summers, with temperature differences depending on altitude. Lombardy's climate is humid subtropical in the plains, with hot summers and cold winters, while the Alps to the north contribute substantial precipitation, including significant snowfall. Due to the diversity of the study area, soil erosion can be attributed to a complex interplay of factors. Water erosion, heavy rainfall and snowmelt lead to leaching of the topsoil. Intensive agricultural practices such as monocultures, overgrazing and unfavourable crop rotation worsen the soil structure and increase susceptibility to erosion. Climate change exacerbates the problem by increasing the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events. Land use changes such as deforestation and urbanisation disrupt the natural balance of the soil, reduce water storage and increase water runoff. Poor soil management without effective conservation measures further contributes to degradation (Costantini 2013; Copernicus Climate Change Service, n.d.)

Stakeholder Mapping Results

The stakeholder mapping for the Italian Living Lab (LL) identified 154 stakeholders, with 148 analysed in relation to their influence and interest in soil health. These stakeholders span across several sectors, each playing a distinct role in the project's success. The economic sector dominates the stakeholder landscape, comprising 63 actors, followed by the political sector with 48 stakeholders, the social sector with 19 actors, the technological sector with 13 stakeholders, and the environmental sector with 5 actors.

The economic sector features several key actors, most notably vineyards, which are highly influential and interested in the project's outcomes. A total of 40 vineyards were identified, including both organic and non-organic vineyards, all ranked with high interest and influence. These stakeholders face complex challenges, particularly related to soil health, such as soil compaction from disease control, the limitations of copper use in organic farming, and the necessity of precision irrigation to cope with climate change-induced water shortages. By participating in the LL, these actors stand to benefit from innovative solutions that address soil degradation, improve water retention, and enhance nutrient availability.

In addition to vineyards, the sector includes 11 farms, with 4 categorised as having high interest and high influence, while the remaining 7 have high interest but low influence. These farms are engaged in various agricultural activities, including olives, agroforestry, and poultry. Financial constraints often limit their ability to innovate, but they remain valuable for testing new sustainable practices, providing an opportunity to bridge traditional farming with innovative solutions. Furthermore, several farming associations play a critical role in advocating for agricultural businesses, with three of them identified as highly relevant. These associations focus on promoting farmers' income and market competitiveness and could benefit from LL participation through insights into innovative agricultural practices and technologies.

The tourism and leisure sector also contributes to the economic landscape, with 5 stakeholders identified. These actors rely on river-based activities for income and are highly affected by soil erosion and the resulting degradation of the river environment, often due to runoff from vineyards. Although their influence on soil health is limited, actively engaging these stakeholders could enhance their economic outlook and contribute to more sustainable practices within the LL framework.

The political sector comprises 48 stakeholders, with 19 municipalities, 2 regional governmental bodies, and 29 public authorities identified. All of these actors exhibit high interest and influence, with many of them involved in soil health, agricultural management, and environmental sustainability. However, one of the main challenges facing political stakeholders is a lack of awareness regarding the importance of soil health, particularly at the local level.

Local authorities are responsible for managing public resources such as olive trees and irrigation systems, as well as addressing urban climate resilience and soil pollution. However, multi-level regulatory complexities and difficulties in innovating management practices limit their ability to effectively promote sustainable soil health. At the regional and national levels, the public authorities focus on environmental and agricultural management, providing an opportunity to engage these actors in advancing policy goals that align with the Living Lab's objectives.

The social sector includes 8 stakeholders, including environmental NGOs, community groups, and associations. These stakeholders generally exhibit high interest but low influence, making them crucial for raising awareness and

fostering community engagement around soil health issues. Several of these groups focus on eco-tourism, environmental preservation, and promoting sustainability through public education, particularly in areas like the Mincio River.

Among the social stakeholders, 2 associations are recommended for active engagement due to their high interest and power, including a public health entity and an environmental education organisation. These groups have the potential to significantly contribute to the dissemination of project results and public awareness, enhancing the LL's impact.

The technological sector includes 13 stakeholders, most of whom are consultancies, research organisations, and utility operators involved in water management. Of these, 9 are classified as "manage closely," indicating their critical role in developing and disseminating innovative solutions for soil and water management. Engaging these technological stakeholders will be key to leveraging their expertise in optimizing agricultural practices, providing technical assistance, and enhancing the uptake of project results among broader sectors.

The environmental sector consists of 5 key stakeholders, including forestry authorities and public environmental management authorities. These actors are highly influential and interested in the project's outcomes, particularly in addressing soil pollution and improving water quality. Engaging these stakeholders in the LL will create synergies that can advance soil and water management practices, with a focus on mitigating the impact of invasive species and pollution from agricultural and industrial activities.

Figure 8: Italian Living Lab - Stakeholder Map

The stakeholder mapping of the Italian Living Lab highlights the critical role of agricultural actors, particularly vineyards and farms specializing in olives, and agroforestry, in driving soil health initiatives. These agricultural stakeholders, along with their associations, are pivotal in influencing the political landscape and advancing their economic interests. However, the interconnectedness between agriculture and tourism cannot be overlooked, as tourism, especially water-based activities in the rivers, is indirectly impacted by the runoff and soil pollution from vineyards and farms. Conversely, the tourism sector also benefits from the local agricultural culture, which contributes to the region's appeal to tourists.

The social sector further amplifies environmental concerns, with local groups working to preserve river valleys and educate younger generations on sustainable practices. This engagement creates a broader demand for political authorities to balance environmental management with economic growth, further highlighting the importance of municipalities. Municipalities play a crucial role in implementing water management strategies, managing public spaces, and supporting shared urban gardening initiatives. While these gardens offer opportunities to teach sustainable practices, they also present challenges due to limited knowledge and resources among voluntary participants.

The technological sector complements these efforts by providing innovative solutions for sustainable soil management, offering valuable support to financially restricted farms looking to improve both soil health and economic viability. Water utility operators are also key stakeholders, given the region's focus on water management. Their involvement is crucial to optimizing water use and supporting sustainable soil practices. In this way, the stakeholder network for the Italian Living Lab creates a complex web of interactions where agriculture, tourism, social engagement, technological innovation, and municipal governance intersect to promote soil health and sustainable development.

Power-interest Matrix

The Power-Interest Matrix for the Italian Living Lab highlights the complex relationships between various stakeholders, all of whom play different but interconnected roles in advancing soil health initiatives. The agricultural sector, particularly vineyards and farms, holds central importance and should be actively engaged, along with municipalities and key environmental authorities. Social and technological sectors are crucial for raising awareness, supporting innovation, and providing on-the-ground engagement. Tourism stakeholders, while indirectly affected, also have a vested interest in sustainable soil and water management, making them a critical yet under-engaged group.

Figure 9: Italian Living Lab - Power-Interest Matrix

Manage closely - High Power, High Interest: Agricultural actors are central to the Living Lab, with vineyards and farms, particularly those involved in olives, agroforestry, and poultry. They hold significant influence in the local economy and are directly impacted by issues like soil degradation, water management, and sustainability challenges. Their interest in the lab stems from their need to find sustainable practices that balance environmental and economic considerations. Following, municipalities and public authorities, including local governments and regional bodies, hold significant regulatory and decision-making power over land use, public resources, and environmental policies. Their high interest comes from the role they play in managing water strategies, soil health, and agricultural policies, which are directly linked to the lab's objectives of fostering sustainable practices. Although the power of environmental groups and NGOs may not be as direct as that of the agricultural or political actors, these groups are highly invested in soil and water health. They play a vital role in advocating for sustainable practices and raising public awareness, influencing both local policy and public behaviour. Water-based tourism actors are in this quadrant due to their reliance on healthy rivers and ecosystems. Their interest in the lab comes from the potential impact of soil erosion and water pollution caused by agricultural runoff. Despite their lower power, their economic relevance makes them an important stakeholder for the project's success. Finally, technology companies that supply innovative solutions for sustainable soil management are also in this quadrant. They provide the tools that vineyards and farms need to implement more sustainable practices, which directly impacts both environmental outcomes and their own business interests.

Keep satisfied - High Power, Low Interest: The Living Lab partners identified selected non-governmental organisations and technology innovation actors that have the power to influence soil health improvements but may not be directly engaged in soil health issues unless prompted. Maintaining their satisfaction through ongoing

updates and showing the benefits of the project for broader environmental management will be essential to keeping their support.

Keep informed - Low Power, High Interest: community groups and associations, such as local environmental groups, historical preservation organisations, and educational associations, are highly interested in the project's outcomes but lack the direct power to influence decision-making. They can, however, play a role in disseminating information and promoting the project's results within their communities. **Community Gardens and Volunteer-Based Groups:** These actors are concerned with sustainability and soil health but have limited resources and influence. They need to be informed about innovative practices that can enhance their gardening efforts and build awareness around soil and environmental issues.

Monitor - Low Power, Low Interest: This quadrant includes some less engaged local businesses or social groups who are not directly impacted by the project may fall into this category. These actors do not play a significant role but should still be monitored to ensure that any potential concerns are addressed proactively, especially if their circumstances change in the future.

Baseline Analysis: Local Ecosystems of the Living Lab

Introduction

Living Lab partners were asked to rate PESTLE influences on a scale from -5 (strong negative influence) to +5 (strong positive influence). These ratings are presented here as they offer a valuable overview for the analysis:

Consortium partners of the Italian Living Lab completed seven separate baseline surveys, each focused on a different experimental site. The results were compiled and analysed collectively. Quantitative assessments varied among respondents, likely due to the specific site each respondent evaluated. In summary, the following observations can be made:

Political support for soil health initiatives shows a consistently positive trend, with ratings ranging from neutral to strongly positive (+4). This indicates strong government support for soil health protection and restoration in all Italian regions. Civil society involvement also shows encouraging levels of support, with most sites reporting moderate to positive involvement from local communities.

However, economic incentives emerge as a challenging area. Ratings in this category range from slightly negative (-2) to slightly positive (+1), suggesting that financial mechanisms to support soil health initiatives may need to be strengthened in all regions. This consistent pattern indicates a potential systemic issue that requires attention at both regional and national levels.

The impact of current technologies on soil health shows mixed results, ranging from slightly negative (-1) to moderately positive (+2). This variation may reflect differences in technology adoption rates or effectiveness across the Living Lab sites.

Legal and regulatory frameworks are generally rated favourably, ranging from neutral to positive (+3). This suggests that while basic regulatory structures are in place, there may be room for improvement in some regions. None of the sites surveyed reported a strongly negative regulatory environment, indicating a solid foundation for soil health governance. Current soil health conditions vary considerably between sites, ranging from slightly negative (-1) to moderately positive (+3). This variation reflects the different geographical and environmental contexts of the experimental sites, as well as potentially different historical land use patterns and management approaches.

The overall assessment suggests that while Italy has strong institutional and social support structures for soil health management, the economic mechanisms for implementing soil health initiatives could be strengthened. The generally optimistic rather than pessimistic assessments in most categories suggest a positive basis for future improvements in soil health management and protection. This analysis points to opportunities for cross-regional learning and potential focus areas for policy development, particularly in strengthening economic incentives and technological applications for soil health management.

Political Factors

Strengths of current political actions and policies for soil health: Current political actions and policies for soil health show strong support for sustainable agriculture. Regional and national policies offer financial incentives for practices benefiting soil health, such as directives on nitrates and conservation agriculture programs. EU regulations, including those on organic production, provide a broader framework for sustainable farming. Local initiatives, like those in the Franciacorta region, limit harmful agrochemical use and promote soil quality. Additionally, strategies such as the Parco del Mincio focus on holistic environmental management, incorporating soil health. Programs reducing chemical inputs and promoting organic farming, along with soil monitoring policies, support soil protection. Community involvement through regional development programs ensures greater acceptance and effectiveness of soil health initiatives. These policies demonstrate a multi-pronged approach to sustainable soil management and regional development.

Weaknesses of current political actions and policies countering soil health: Current policies and actions for soil health have several weaknesses. A major issue is the lack of comprehensive legislation focused on overall soil health, hindering effective management. Bureaucratic barriers in accessing and administering sustainable agriculture incentives also reduce participation. Intensive agricultural practices that degrade soil fertility threaten long-term health, necessitating stronger regulations. A lack of knowledge and awareness about soil quality further hampers policy development and public support. Policies supporting activities that degrade soil, like quarries, landfills, and urban expansion, create conflicts. Additionally, the inadequate control of micropollutants and the narrow focus on pollutants, rather than holistic soil health, limit the effectiveness of current regulations. A more integrated approach is needed, addressing soil structure, organic matter, and biodiversity to ensure long-term soil sustainability.

Opportunities of soil health for local politics: Improved soil health offers significant opportunities for local policy. It provides a foundation for enhanced environmental strategies, demonstrating commitment to sustainability and attracting funding. Healthy soils support green infrastructure goals by enhancing carbon sequestration, water filtration, and biodiversity, thereby increasing ecological resilience. Proactive policies focused on soil health can improve public reputation, attract businesses, tourism, and skilled workers. Success in soil health initiatives also presents opportunities for positive political messaging, boosting public support and trust. Regions prioritising soil health are more likely to secure funding for sustainable development projects. Conversely, land degradation poses

risks such as hydrogeological instability, including landslides and erosion, which demand disaster management resources. Declining agricultural productivity can lead to food shortages and economic hardship, putting pressure on local authorities to support the agricultural sector.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local politics: Economic-political tensions may arise, particularly from businesses benefiting from current land uses, such as quarries and landfills. Conflicts could emerge between economic development and soil protection, with stricter regulations potentially causing short-term economic losses. Bureaucratic challenges include the risk of increased administrative burdens and complicated implementation processes, which may fuel political resistance. Stakeholder opposition is likely from intensive agriculture, urban development, and companies with conflicting plans. Policy implementation risks include budgetary resistance to new programme costs, difficulties in demonstrating short-term benefits, and the potential for ineffective implementation, which could undermine political credibility.

Economic Factors

Strengths of current economic actions for soil health: The economic activities in the Living Lab location offer some strengths for soil health. Sustainable and organic farming practices, such as crop rotation, the use of natural fertilisers, and minimizing chemical inputs, significantly improve soil fertility, structure, and biodiversity. In Franciacorta over 50% of vineyards already use organic methods. Biodynamic farming and "real" organic farming techniques further enhance soil health by promoting ecological balance and reducing reliance on synthetic chemicals. Additionally, the preservation of "prati stabili" (permanent meadows), which are left uncultivated for long periods, supports soil regeneration and biodiversity. Financial incentives provided through regulations and policies, such as CAP payments and organic farming grants, encourage the adoption of these sustainable practices, contributing to improved soil quality. Furthermore, knowledge sharing through agricultural networks and economic institution support for sustainable farming can be increasingly observed.

Weaknesses of current economic actions countering soil health: Current economic activities in the Living Lab location reveal several weaknesses that hinder soil health progress. The presence of chemical hubs and contaminated industrial sites poses a significant threat, with limited remediation efforts failing to address industrial pollution fully. Urban sprawl and ongoing construction encroach on agricultural land, leading to soil sealing and the permanent loss of arable land. Intensive farming practices continue to degrade soil health, with monoculture farming depleting soil nutrients. Farmers face challenges, including resource competition, access to water, and high production costs linked to sustainable practices. Market pressures prioritise short-term profits over long-term soil health, while high land costs make it difficult for new farmers to establish sustainable operations. These economic dynamics create barriers to implementing effective soil health practices.

Opportunities of soil health for local economic development: Improved soil health offers substantial opportunities for local economic development, particularly in agriculture, tourism, and innovation. Enhanced soil management can boost agricultural productivity, particularly in the rice, fruit, and wine sectors, while sustainable practices open access to premium markets for environmentally conscious consumers. Soil preservation can also help avoid costly infrastructure repairs and water management challenges. The tourism sector can benefit from ecotourism and agrotourism by promoting sustainable farming practices and landscapes like 'prati stabili' (permanent meadows). Financial incentives, such as EU CAP payments, support the transition to sustainable practices. Soil degradation, on the other hand, poses risks to economic development, including reduced

agricultural productivity, increased production costs, and lower farm incomes. Erosion and instability also damage infrastructure, driving up costs, while declining soil quality reduces property values.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local economic development: Short-term challenges include increased implementation costs for farmers transitioning to sustainable practices, such as higher operating expenses for new equipment and techniques, as well as reduced yields during the transition. Competitive disadvantages may arise from higher production costs compared to conventional agriculture, price competition from regions using less sustainable methods, and potential loss of market share. Land use conflicts could emerge from reduced availability of land for development, restrictions on industrial expansion, and limitations on tourism infrastructure. Structural economic challenges include industry adjustments, such as the need for costly remediation of industrial sites and business model shifts for agricultural suppliers. Employment changes may include job losses in conventional agriculture, workforce retraining needs, and shifts in required skills. Additionally, market disruptions are expected, including supply chain adjustments, changes in business relationships, and potentially costly market repositioning.

Social Factors

Strengths of social/community support for soil health: The strengths of social and community support for soil health show several notable features in the region. Active community engagement stands out as a primary strength, with strong citizen participation in environmental conservation and organised community activities to protect the area. Direct involvement in tree planting to absorb heavy metals, led by Soulfood ForestFarms, and the collaborative sowing of cereal crops with local schools to improve soil conditions, as conducted by Terzopaesaggio in Vettabbia Park, highlight hands-on community action. Regular waste collection initiatives and high community awareness further demonstrate a commitment to environmental stewardship. Institutional support reinforces these efforts, with the Franciacorta Consortium's collaboration on environmental projects, such as plastic-free vineyard initiatives. Educational efforts round off these strengths, with knowledge sharing and awareness programs enhancing the community's capacity for environmental stewardship. Practical demonstrations of sustainable farming methods ensure the continuation and improvement of soil health practices

Weaknesses of social/community activities countering soil health: Key weaknesses in community and social activities that counter soil health include significant knowledge gaps and infrastructure issues. One of the most pressing challenges is the lack of awareness among non-professional farmers about sustainable farming practices. This knowledge gap often results in the overuse of chemicals and fertilisers, which can damage soil health over time. There is a clear need for more targeted education and training programs to promote sustainable agricultural methods within local communities. Additionally, the continued expansion of urban areas and infrastructure development frequently encroaches on agricultural land, highlighting weaknesses in land-use planning and community-based zoning regulations. This urban sprawl is driven by community priorities that fail to adequately protect agricultural land from development pressures.

Opportunities of soil health for local communities and social development: Improving soil health offers significant benefits to local communities, enhancing both quality of life and environmental resilience. Healthy soils support better agricultural and livestock products, promoting food safety and community health. Soil health interventions contribute to cleaner air and water, as well-maintained soils filter pollutants and reduce runoff, protecting local natural resources and mitigating broader environmental issues. Healthy soils also play a key role in carbon storage, reducing greenhouse gas emissions like methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O), contributing to

climate resilience. Improved soil quality can enhance green spaces, providing more appealing recreational areas. Soil degradation, on the other hand, poses significant challenges, compromising food safety and health. Resource degradation, soil sealing, and urban sprawl reduce agricultural capacity, affecting future generations' ability to maintain productivity and food security.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local communities and social development:

Socially, disruptions can include conflicts between traditional and organic farmers, opposition from established industrial agricultural interests, community divisions over land use changes, and cultural shifts in farming practices. Land use conflicts could arise from reduced availability for urban development, restrictions on existing practices, and competition between food production and nature conservation. Implementation challenges include unequal distribution of transition costs, knowledge gaps requiring training, resource allocation conflicts, and potential exclusion of smaller farmers due to compliance costs.

Technological Factors

Strengths of current technologies: In northern Italy, several key technologies support soil health management. Automation technologies improve farming efficiency and precision. Soil enhancement techniques, including liming for acidic soils, compost production, green manuring, and innovative hydrochar production from lotus flowers, strengthen soil quality. Sustainable practices like no-till farming, cover cropping, intercropping, and crop rotation help maintain soil structure and fertility. Environmental technologies focus on mitigating heavy metal contamination, reducing greenhouse gas emissions (especially nitrous oxide and methane), and using crops like rye and spelt for pollutant storage. Willow plants also show promise in absorbing heavy metals. Monitoring and control technologies provide cost-effective solutions, especially for organic farming, where over 50% of vineyards use such methods. Mechanical weed control is also implemented effectively through row grassing.

Weaknesses of current technologies: Several weaknesses hinder the effectiveness of current soil health technologies in Italy. Precision farming adoption is limited, primarily due to high costs, the need for technical expertise, and scalability challenges, especially on smaller farms. Traditional ploughing and deep tillage, while still common, disrupt soil structure, accelerate organic matter loss, increase erosion risks, and cause soil compaction, undermining long-term soil health. Synthetic fertilisers are overused due to inadequate application techniques, leading to nutrient imbalances, soil acidification, and water pollution through run-off. Additionally, soil health monitoring technologies are underdeveloped, and current practices often rely on external inputs like compost, which can create dependencies and introduce external risks. Systems need to move toward greater self-sufficiency and closed-loop management. Conventional vineyard management also lacks technological innovation, limiting optimal soil health practices. The slow adaptation to changing conditions, such as climate change, and limited involvement of technological stakeholders further complicate progress.

Opportunities of novel technologies: Novel technologies offer significant potential for environmental improvement, productivity gains, and economic benefits in agriculture. Advanced soil management techniques could reduce greenhouse gas emissions (N₂O and CH₄) and improve soil health. Innovations such as hydrochar production from lotus flowers could have widespread environmental benefits. Automation and new soil management technologies promise to increase agricultural productivity and reduce reliance on synthetic inputs, leading to more efficient farming that optimises both yields and soil health. These technologies can also improve the efficiency of fertiliser, water, and other resource use. New approaches may reduce dependence on synthetic fertilisers while maintaining soil fertility. The expansion of organic farming, already widespread in local vineyards,

creates opportunities for these technologies to further support sustainable agriculture. Additionally, cost-effective monitoring solutions and improved soil management technologies could offer economic benefits to farmers, including reduced input costs, enhanced crop quality, and new market opportunities.

Potential threats of novel technologies: The risks of novel technologies in relation to soil health were not explicitly stated in the responses to the iCOSHells PESTLE questionnaire but can be inferred. The responses mention the potential of lotus flower hydrochar to improve soil properties, but its effectiveness is not guaranteed and requires further research and testing in the Living Lab context. Furthermore, while the importance of involving technology stakeholders was highlighted, there is an implicit acknowledgement of the risk that these stakeholders may not be effectively engaged, potentially hindering the development and implementation of novel solutions such as hydrochar production. Finally, the reference in the questionnaires to the need for 'more or new technologies' suggests that existing practices may be inadequate and that new approaches need to be developed. This inherent novelty carries the risk of unforeseen challenges in implementation and adoption.

Legal Factors

Strengths of current legal regulations for soil health: The local regulations benefit from a comprehensive multi-level governance, ranging from local regulations for protected areas and forests, to regional laws in Lombardy and Trentino, to national environmental regulations and the European Union framework. Of note are the protective measures, which provide safeguards against both chemical and biological degradation, while preserving natural environments and habitats. These are reinforced by supportive policy frameworks, including the National Organic Farming Plan, the National Soil Protection Strategy, the EU Organic Regulation and the forthcoming Nature Conservation Act. The regulations also provide support mechanisms. Farmers receive financial incentives for adopting organic methods, as well as support for regenerative and conservation farming practices. The integration of soil health considerations into broader environmental policies further strengthens this approach. Finally, the establishment of designated protected areas is another major strength of the current legislation. By creating protected agricultural areas and bio-districts, these measures actively promote sustainable land use practices.

Weaknesses of current legal regulations that counter soil health: Current legislation has several weaknesses that hinder effective soil health management. The most prominent problem is the lack of specific legislation that focuses directly on soil health. Instead of being treated as a primary concern, soil health is often relegated to a secondary status compared to other environmental issues such as air and water quality. The regulatory framework suffers from excessive complexity due to the multiplicity of laws and regulations at different levels of government. This leads to confusion and operational inefficiencies in addressing soil health issues. The overlapping responsibilities between local, regional, national and European levels can lead to implementation challenges and potential conflicts between different legal frameworks. There is also a lack of a truly holistic, integrated approach to soil health management. The current fragmented regulatory landscape fails to provide a comprehensive strategy that addresses all aspects of soil health protection and restoration. This piecemeal approach potentially leaves gaps in soil protection and may lead to inconsistent implementation of soil health measures.

Opportunities associated with legal regulations for soil health: The multi-level governance structure (local, regional, national and European) offers opportunities for comprehensive soil health management. There are significant opportunities for collaboration between different stakeholders. Responses to the questionnaire specifically mention that collaboration between scientific, agricultural and legal stakeholders will be crucial to improving soil health through effective policies and regulations. The existing financial incentive structure for farmers offers opportunities to expand and improve sustainable practices. Integrating soil health into wider

environmental and agricultural policies offers opportunities for a more holistic approach. This includes potential synergies with water management, biodiversity conservation and carbon sequestration initiatives. The establishment of protected agricultural areas and bio-districts offers opportunities to develop model regions for sustainable land use and soil health management, which could serve as examples for wider implementation.

Potential threats associated with legal regulations for soil health: The risks stem from regulatory complexity and the multiplicity of frameworks. This complexity can lead to confusion in implementation and enforcement, as well as inefficiencies in addressing soil health concerns. In addition, the existence of multiple frameworks can lead to potential conflicts between different legal frameworks at different levels of governance. Another risk relates to the secondary treatment of soil health in legislation. In situations where other environmental concerns, such as air and water, are prioritised, soil protection may not be adequately addressed. In addition, gaps in protection could arise due to the lack of a holistic, integrated approach that considers the interconnected nature of environmental issues.

Environmental Factors

Strengths of the natural environment for soil health: Strengths related to environmental factors for soil health in northern Italy include good air quality in certain areas, which promotes healthy plant growth and contributes to soil health. The generally favourable climate supports robust agricultural practices and healthy soil ecosystems. Protected natural areas help to maintain biodiversity and act as refuges for beneficial soil organisms, further supporting regional soil health. Finally, the existing adoption of sustainable farming practices, such as organic, biodynamic and traditional pasture management, actively improves soil fertility and nutrient cycling and reduces greenhouse gas emissions.

Weaknesses of the natural environment countering soil health: Environmental vulnerabilities affecting soil health in northern Italy include poor air in urban areas and reduced water quality and the effects of climate change, such as drought and changing rainfall patterns. Climate change, biodiversity loss, and other future environmental developments pose significant risks, as they are expected to exacerbate existing problems such as water scarcity, temperature extremes, and soil degradation. The presence of invasive species is an additional challenge. The region also suffers from acid and sub-acid soils, as well as the ongoing challenge of maintaining adequate levels of soil organic matter. Together, these factors work against maintaining optimal soil health.

Opportunities of soil health for the natural environment: Improved soil health offers several opportunities for enhancing the natural environment. First, healthy soils support carbon storage, helping to regulate greenhouse gases, including CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O, which contributes to climate stability. Enhanced soil structure also improves water retention, which plays a crucial role in flood mitigation by slowing down water runoff and reducing erosion. Soil health is essential for biodiversity, as it provides habitats and supports various species, contributing to a balanced ecosystem. Additionally, healthy soils enhance landscape aesthetics, making natural areas more visually appealing and boosting tourism. Finally, stable and healthy soils support infrastructure by preventing erosion and soil degradation, which is essential for the longevity and safety of roads, buildings, and other structures.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for the natural environment: Although not explicitly mentioned in the data provided, soil health initiatives in the region could pose potential threats to the natural environment. Ecosystem disturbance may be a concern, as well-intentioned interventions may disrupt existing ecological balances. Resource competition may arise from the diversion of water for soil projects, and land-use changes may affect natural habitats. Unintended chemical changes include changes in soil pH affecting

surrounding areas, changes in nutrient cycling affecting nearby ecosystems, and potential nutrient leaching into water bodies. Biodiversity could be negatively affected by standardising soil conditions, reducing specialised species and homogenising the soil microbiome. Implementation risks include over-application of organic amendments, poorly timed interventions that disrupt natural cycles, and poorly managed restoration practices that cause soil erosion.

Implications for stakeholder engagement and co-creation

The stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis provide valuable insights for stakeholder engagement and co-creation within the Italian Living Lab. The stakeholder mapping offers specific recommendations on managing stakeholder groups, identifying which stakeholders to engage closely, which to keep satisfied, which to inform, and which to monitor. Complementing this, the baseline analysis highlights opportunities presented by soil health initiatives across political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental dimensions. These opportunities can serve as compelling arguments to involve relevant stakeholders in Living Lab activities. Simultaneously, the analysis identifies potential threats associated with a focus on soil health that may concern specific stakeholder groups. These concerns can be taken into account in communication strategies and incorporated into Living Lab solutions, ensuring project partners are equipped with clear responses to alleviate existing fears.

Particularly for the Italian Living Lab it needs to be noted that the heterogeneity of the individual experimental sites may pose challenges for managing the Living Lab as a whole. Some sites have developed advanced ideas of potential solutions keen on co-developing plans for implementation, whereas others are more open to harness co-creation at earlier stages of the Living Lab. This will be taken into account in developing the recommendations for the engagement.

This section summarises initial strategies derived from the stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis, recommending different engagement levels—from active co-creation to low-maintenance interactions with peripheral entities. These recommendations will be further refined in collaboration with Living Lab leaders in the coming months, with a particular focus on substantiating and detailing planned co-creation sessions in a publicly accessible report.

Recommendations:

Develop tailored cross-sectoral engagement strategies for co-creation in all sites: Engaging key stakeholders, with high influence and interest in soil health, in co-creation sessions is essential for the success of the Living Lab. These stakeholders include agricultural actors, municipalities, technology providers, and research institutions. Co-creation sessions generally can focus on generating new ideas for improving soil health, refining pre-selected solutions, planning and implementing solution testing, and monitoring, evaluating, and adapting the tested solutions. Active participation in these sessions fosters a sense of ownership and ensures long-term commitment to the project’s objectives, which is vital for its sustained impact. The focus of activities and the selection of participants for co-creation sessions should depend on the specific experimental site in Italy. At the Mincio, Nosedo, and RUMA sites, co-creation can address the full spectrum of steps, including solution definition, selection, implementation planning, and solution monitoring. Broad cross-sectoral collaboration at these sites can

facilitate knowledge exchange, foster innovative local solutions, and ensure public support and trust. At the Oppeano, UNITN, and Franciacorta sites, co-creation might focus on identifying pathways to scale and facilitate the uptake of solutions, alongside monitoring, evaluating, and adapting them. In these cases, engaging stakeholders beyond immediate technological and agricultural partners will be crucial to creating innovation networks and governance frameworks that ensure the long-term viability and broad adoption of more sustainable practices.

Prioritise Cross-Sectoral Collaboration: Stakeholder engagement of the Italian Living Lab should prioritise cross-sectoral collaboration, recognizing the importance of aligning diverse interests across agriculture, tourism, municipalities, environmental groups, and technology providers. Partnerships with agricultural actors, including vineyards and farms, should be strengthened through tailored support like financial incentives and training to promote sustainable soil and water management practices. Municipalities, given their regulatory power, should be empowered to integrate Living Lab goals into local planning documents, including water management strategies and public land-use plans. Technology providers should also be involved early, co-developing innovative solutions and contributing to pilot projects that address technical challenges in sustainable soil management.

Promote Economic Development and Resilience: Economic benefits of soil health initiatives can serve as incentive, both for smaller and less financially solvent agricultural actors to engage with the Living Lab and scaling-up of existing solutions. Additionally, it is an incentive for economic public authorities and municipalities to support the effort. Increasing soil health reduces risks far beyond the agricultural sector, by protecting public infrastructure and the built environment, and reducing the risk of disasters. Additionally, climate adaptation in the agricultural and subsequently tourism sectors is promoted, increasing the resilience of the economic sector to cross-cutting threats such as climate change.

Championing Partnerships: at the same time stakeholders in the “keep satisfied” and “keep informed” quadrants need consistent communication and opportunities to contribute. High-power but lower-interest actors, such as water utility operators, should receive regular updates that highlight the importance of their cooperation in achieving broader goals. Voluntary groups, such as those involved in urban gardening, would benefit from workshops to increase their capacity to implement sustainable practices, enabling grassroots support for broader initiatives.

Strengthen Environmental Advocacy and Public Awareness: Environmental advocacy and public awareness efforts must be strengthened by collaborating with NGOs and local groups, including schools, farms, and tourism operators, fostering a culture of sustainability. Already existing engagement channels with social stakeholders are recommended to be built upon and strengthened. Partnerships with groups monitoring river health could also be established to create joint action plans addressing pollution and soil runoff, reinforcing the interconnection between agricultural practices and water quality.

Address Power Asymmetries and Build Trust: Recognising the power asymmetries among stakeholders is crucial for equitable engagement. Marginalised actors, such as small farms or volunteer groups, often lack resources and require support through micro-grants or access to shared technologies. Transparent decision-making processes and open communication channels are essential for building trust, ensuring that all stakeholders feel valued and heard in the decision-making process.

Integrate the Local Context and Culture: for this living lab, it is of paramount importance that overall, Living Lab engagement strategy incorporate the local context and culture, acknowledging the cultural significance of

agriculture and tourism. Soil management initiatives should be framed as a means to preserve the region's traditions, such as wine production and agroforestry, which resonate deeply with local identity. They should also integrate the already engaged civil society in their plans, teaching about sustainable practices for (home and shared) gardening and supporting their efforts such as tree planting that have already effectively reduced the soil impacts of industrial pollutants in the region in the past.

Spanish GreennoMed Living Lab

Introduction

Overview of the Spanish GreennoMed Living Lab's Objectives

The Spanish GreennoMed Living Lab's primary areas of focus are land use, agriculture, and the resolution of soil health challenges in areas where intensive crop and woody crop cultivation is prevalent. The principal objectives are to address soil health degradation, enhance ecosystem resilience and promote sustainable agricultural practices. The Living Lab is led by CETENMA (Centro Tecnológico de la Energía y del Medio Ambiente) from Cartagena, Murcia, Spain and is supported by following research and academic institutions, including CEBAS-CSIC, IMIDA and Fundación Cajamar. Farmer organisations, such as COAG, also play a pivotal role in providing input and expertise. The Living Lab will establish 10 co-creation test sites, the purpose of which is to evaluate and refine a variety of solutions. The solutions developed target three key areas: efficient fertiliser management, irrigation water treatment and the introduction of external biodiversity agents.

Geographical Location and Context

The Spanish GreennoMed Living Lab is located in the Murcia region and Almería province, Spain. The Region of Murcia is an autonomous community of Spain, located in the southeastern part of the Iberian Peninsula, on the Mediterranean coast. It had a population of 1,511,251 at the beginning of 2020 and is 11,313 km² in area, with about half of the area dedicated to agricultural production. The region is one of Europe's largest producers of fruit, vegetables and flowers. It is known as 'Europe's orchard' because of its long agricultural tradition and its production and export of fruit, vegetables and flowers. The region's fertile soil, mild winters and long growing season make it an ideal place for agriculture. It is a semi-arid region with hot, dry summers, sporadic heavy autumn rains and mild winters. It is a world leader in agricultural production, exporting 2.5 million tonnes of fruit and vegetables a year. It has a leading position in international sales of many fresh products, including lettuce, broccoli, lemons, melons and artichokes (Martin-Gorriz et al. 2020). The region's unique ecosystem includes the Mar Menor lagoon, the largest saltwater lagoon in Europe, covering some 135 square kilometres. It's a vital part of the region's ecosystem, providing habitat for numerous marine species and supporting local fisheries. Intensive agriculture in the surrounding areas results in high levels of nitrates, ammonium and phosphates from fertilisers being washed into the lagoon. The Murcia region is experiencing progressive desertification, caused by poor land and forestry management, in combination with unsustainable agricultural practices. Climate change exacerbates this situation. Droughts and heavy rainfall damage the soil structure and cause erosion. Heavy rain washes away the nutrient-rich top layer, while wind removes organic matter. Intensive agriculture with high fertiliser uses and irrigation has also led to soil degradation. The abandonment of agricultural land due to unprofitability and rural exodus also contributes to soil degradation (Martin-Gorriz et al. 2020). Erosion and loss of biodiversity occur on abandoned land. Soil pollution due to the excessive use of chemicals in agriculture also affects soil quality and health.

Stakeholder Mapping Results

The stakeholder mapping for the Spanish Living Lab (LL) reveals a dynamic network of 112 stakeholders distributed across five key sectors: economic, technological, political, environmental, and social. Each sector plays a distinct yet interconnected role in addressing soil health challenges and fostering sustainable agricultural practices. Below is an analysis of the composition, roles, relationships, and challenges of these stakeholders, emphasizing the need for cross-sectoral collaboration.

The economic sector dominates the stakeholder map with 53 actors, primarily agricultural operators (44 farms and cooperatives), followed by seven associations and two consultancies. Most agricultural operators (35 farms and five associations) are ranked as having high interest and influence. These stakeholders are central to the soil health issue, as their activities directly affect soil conditions. Challenges include soil salinity, pests, nutrient imbalances, pesticide pollution, and water overuse, leading to reduced soil fertility, reduced crop yield production, and environmental degradation. Engagement in the LLs would offer those economic actors' opportunities to maintain production rates while adopting environmentally sustainable and cost-effective practices. Consultancies can enhance their expertise and connect with potential clients, while associations benefit by advocating for their members' interests and identifying practical solutions to existential threats.

The technological sector comprises 40 actors, including technological and chemical suppliers (18), innovation entities (9), research institutions (5), training providers (3), and utility enterprises (water and waste management). Among these, technological suppliers and innovation actors exhibit high interest and influence. Universities and public training entities also play pivotal roles, providing research and education to support sustainable practices. This sector serves as a critical enabler by offering tools, innovative solutions, and knowledge exchange. Stakeholders like universities and technology centres help bridge knowledge gaps, while suppliers align their offerings with the needs of transitioning farms. Participation in LLs helps these actors refine their technologies and anticipate future market demands.

Political stakeholders (10) include four municipalities, organic standards bodies (public and private), and regional agricultural and water ministries. Most political stakeholders rank high in interest and influence, as they provide the regulatory and policy framework for sustainable practices. Municipalities and ministries are crucial for implementing water management strategies and ensuring policy coherence with sustainable soil health goals. Organic standards bodies are particularly influential in aligning sustainability practices with certification requirements, either enabling or hindering their widespread adoption.

The environmental sector includes five NGOs dedicated to soil restoration and preservation. While smaller in number, these actors hold significant influence by acting as intermediaries between agricultural stakeholders and environmental objectives. Their participation in the LLs strengthens the farmers' commitment to sustainability and raises awareness of broader ecological impacts.

The social sector encompasses four stakeholders, including three consumer associations. Two of these associations have high relevance due to their potential to represent consumer perspectives and advocate for sustainable practices. Consumer associations provide indirect influence by shaping public opinion and advocating for environmentally conscious choices. Their involvement ensures that LL outcomes align with societal expectations and consumer demands.

Figure 10: Spanish Living Lab - Stakeholder Map

The stakeholder map for the Spanish Living Lab highlights the centrality of economic actors in the soil health challenge and emphasises the critical role of collaboration across sectors. By leveraging the strengths of each sector and addressing shared challenges, the Living Lab can advance sustainable agricultural practices and contribute to ecological and economic resilience.

The technological sector supports agricultural stakeholders with tools and knowledge, while political actors create the regulatory environment necessary for sustainable practices. Environmental and social actors influence indirectly by advocating for ecological and societal interests, shaping public discourse, and pressuring political actors. Political stakeholders have a key role in creating suitable governance frameworks and incentives to encourage the economic sector to follow sustainable soil practices. Private environmental governance approaches, such as above-standard organic labels, could play a crucial role for enabling a scaling of the uptake of sustainable soil practices, as they enable farmers to generate more income for the sometimes more costly production methods. This interdependence underscores the necessity of cross-sectoral collaboration. Economic, political, and technological stakeholders must work closely to develop and implement effective soil health solutions, while environmental and social actors provide the support and advocacy needed to sustain these efforts.

Power-interest Matrix

The stakeholder mapping of the Spanish Living Lab (LL) reveals a notable diffusion of power among stakeholders with vested interests in soil health and sustainable agricultural practices. The power-interest matrix highlights a strong correlation between stakeholders' levels of interest and influence, with many actors identified as possessing

both high power and high interest. However, this pattern could reflect an inherent bias among survey respondents, who may have assumed a high degree of interest corresponds with high power or vice versa.

Figure 11: Spanish Living Lab - Power-Interest Matrix

Manage closely - High Power, High Interest: The majority of stakeholders fall into this quadrant, reflecting their critical role in driving sustainable practices in the LL. Key stakeholders in this category include: most agricultural operators (35 farms and 5 associations) and agricultural consultancies are highly influential and deeply invested in addressing soil degradation and adopting innovative practices. Their predominance in this quadrant underscores their direct impact on and vulnerability to soil health issues. Their engagement is non-negotiable for the LL’s success. A significant portion of technological suppliers (15 out of 18) and innovation actors (7 out of 9) also exhibit high power and interest. Their contributions of tools, research, and innovations are essential to supporting the transition to sustainable agricultural practices. Municipalities, organic standards bodies, and regional ministries represent powerful actors who influence regulatory frameworks and policy directions. Municipalities and regional authorities rank highly in power and interest, highlighting their central role in policy implementation and governance. However, political actors with lower interest may require targeted engagement to ensure broader policy coherence. NGOs advocating for soil restoration possess high interest and leverage their influence to encourage sustainable practices among agricultural stakeholders. These actors require close engagement through regular collaboration, co-development of solutions, and alignment of objectives. These stakeholders often function as catalysts for change, leveraging advocacy and public opinion to influence high-power actors indirectly. Their role complements the direct actions of economic and technological stakeholders.

Keep Satisfied - High Power, Low Interest: The analysis of survey responses did not identify any stakeholders in this category. However, should such stakeholders emerge in the future, it is important to note that although their interest may be limited, their structural or technical roles grant them significant influence. These stakeholders should be engaged strategically, with efforts to increase their interest by demonstrating how sustainable practices align with their objectives.

Keep Informed - Low Power, High Interest: Only one stakeholder emerged in this category. A research institute with high interest but less direct influence on soil health management. Engaging them into the Living Lab offers the opportunity to benefit from their research and to empower them regarding their influence on soil health in the region.

Monitor - Low Power, Low Interest: Actors with minimal influence and interest include smaller utility enterprises and certain unranked political stakeholders. While their immediate role in the LL may be limited, their position should be monitored for potential changes in relevance, especially if the LL activities expand or evolve.

Baseline Analysis: Local Ecosystem of the Living Lab

Introduction

The baseline analysis of the Spanish Living Lab location in Southeast Spain (Murcia region and Almería) reveals a complex interplay of challenges and opportunities across PESTLE factors.

Living Lab leaders were asked to rate PESTLE influences on a scale from -5 (strong negative influence) to +5 (strong positive influence). These ratings are presented here as they offer a valuable overview for the analysis:

Overall, the region shows strong civil society support (+2) for environmental protection, as evidenced by active community participation in conservation efforts and growing awareness of the ecological importance of the Mar Menor lagoon in the Murcia Region. However, this positive engagement contrasts sharply with the current state of the region's environmental health (-3), most notably the severe eutrophication of the Mar Menor lagoon and the degradation of the Campo de Cartagena watershed.

The political and regulatory framework (scores -1 and 0 respectively) shows mixed effectiveness. While robust legislation is in place, including EU-level protection and regional measures, implementation challenges and conflicts between agricultural interests and environmental protection persist. The economic sphere is a major concern (-2), with short-term agricultural productivity often taking precedence over long-term environmental and economic sustainability, despite some promising developments in precision farming and sustainable agricultural practices.

Technological capacity currently has a slightly negative impact (-1), reflecting a paradoxical situation where advanced monitoring systems and precision farming technologies coexist with inadequate pollution control and water management infrastructure. This complex landscape particularly affects the Mar Menor ecosystem, which is under pressure from agricultural run-off, urban development and historical mining activities.

The following PESTLE analysis explores how existing strengths in civic engagement and technological innovation can be leveraged, while addressing critical weaknesses in economic incentives and policy implementation, to achieve more effective soil health management in the region.

Political Factors

Strengths of current political actions and policies for soil health: Several strong political actions and policies support soil health in Southeast Spain. At EU level, key legislation includes the Nature Restoration Law, Agenda 2030, Natura 2000, Horizon Europe and the Soil Monitoring Law. The regional government has also developed tailor-made agri-environmental measures (AEM) for the period 2007-2013, which are better adapted to local soil degradation problems. The Mar Menor lagoon is protected by several designations, including Regional Park status, Protected Landscape Areas, Special Protection Areas (SPAs), Sites of Community Importance (SCIs), Ramsar Wetlands and Specially Protected Area of Mediterranean Importance (SPAMI). Additional protection measures include an Integrated Management Plan for the Mar Menor and coastal areas, emergency regulations for the recovery of the ecosystem, the designation of "sensitive areas" under the Water Framework Directive and the required development of an Integrated Coastal Zone Management Strategy.

Weaknesses of current political actions and policies for soil health: Policy and action on soil health in Southeast Spain faces several major challenges. Territorial management and governance issues arise from conflicts of interest due to Spain's highly autonomous regional system. The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and local political interests have often worked against soil health objectives. Current policies have shown limited effectiveness, struggling with high administrative costs and poor adaptation to intensive agricultural practices in the region. Several key weaknesses have emerged in policy implementation. Previous policies and plans to prevent and correct nitrate pollution and eutrophication in the Mar Menor have not been adequately implemented. One reason for the lacking implementation are the high costs associated with implementation for the local economic actors. The agricultural actors often lack the financial resources necessary for implementation. The Murcia region lacks a comprehensive spatial planning instrument to effectively regulate land use and activities in the Mar Menor watershed. Despite existing regulations, illegal irrigation and agricultural practices continue to contribute to excessive nutrient loads in the lagoon.

Opportunities of soil health for local politics: Soil health improvements in Southeast Spain present valuable opportunities for local politics. Enhancing soil health can help strengthen resilience and food security by diversifying local food supplies. It also offers the chance to prevent local disasters and improve spatial planning. Addressing soil degradation can contribute to restoring the ecological, cultural, and socio-economic values of areas like the Mar Menor, benefiting both the environment and local communities. Successful soil health management can foster social mobilisation and influence political decisions, creating a platform for collaboration. By resolving conflicts between stakeholders, such as agricultural, tourism, and conservation groups, the region has the potential to become a model for sustainable coastal management and restoration, demonstrating a commitment to long-term environmental and economic sustainability.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local politics: Stricter regulations aimed at improving soil health could face resistance due to potential conflicts with established agricultural practices and local economic interests. In Spain's decentralised governance system, differences between regional and national/EU policies may lead to tensions and coordination challenges. Translating broad directives into practical, effective local actions can also be difficult, requiring strong political will and administrative capacity. Additionally, the up-

front costs of soil health initiatives, with benefits that may not be immediately visible, could create pressure to favour short-term economic gains over long-term sustainability. Finally, soil health efforts must compete with other pressing political priorities, which may require delicate negotiations and compromises to ensure their successful integration into broader policy agendas.

Economic Factors

Strengths of current economic actions for soil health: The strengths of economic activities include the transition by some actors to more sustainable irrigation practices, such as precision farming, which aligns nutrient availability with crop needs. A key economic initiative has been the mandatory installation of monitoring equipment for efficient water management in irrigated areas. These investments have improved soil microbiology and reduced nutrient leaching and greenhouse gas emissions, supporting sustainable economic growth while maintaining productivity. Additionally, ecotourism and sustainable forestry projects provide alternative income sources that promote soil health, showcasing a model for sustainable development in agricultural regions.

Weaknesses of current economic actions countering soil health: Current economic activities in Southeast Spain reveal significant weaknesses in addressing soil health issues. The main weakness stems from the increased water and nutrient flows into the Mar Menor lagoon, which have resulted in severe eutrophication and deteriorating water quality. This problem is largely caused by economic activities that prioritise short-term agricultural productivity over long-term environmental sustainability. A critical weakness lies in the agricultural water management system. The current economic model of the agricultural sector, while profitable in the short term, does not adequately address the environmental costs of these practices. The region's economic policies have also failed to effectively manage surface and groundwater pollution from agricultural and livestock activities. Despite the introduction of some monitoring systems, economic incentives and enforcement mechanisms have not been sufficient to prevent harmful practices. This suggests a fundamental weakness in aligning economic interests with the maintenance of soil health, particularly in the absence of effective economic sanctions or incentives for sustainable practices.

Opportunities of soil health for local economic development: Promoting soil health presents substantial opportunities for local economic development. Sustainable and precision farming methods offer potential for economic growth while safeguarding environmental resources. These approaches, alongside required reductions in nutrient and water inputs, can open new business prospects in agricultural technology and consultancy, enhancing agriculture's sustainability. The region could foster a green economic model by restoring healthy soils, which supports ecotourism and generates revenue through protected areas and sustainable forestry. This economic diversification may reduce reliance on intensive agriculture and create jobs in environmental management and sustainable tourism. Furthermore, the mandatory use of water management systems has created a demand for environmental monitoring equipment and expertise, which could expand into new soil health technologies, creating local business opportunities and attracting investment.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local economic development: Although not explicitly mentioned in the questionnaire, potential threats to economic development from improved soil health include concerns about transition costs, particularly in conventional agriculture where significant investment would be required to switch to sustainable practices. This could lead to reduced yields and financial strain in the short term. Business model disruption could be another challenge, particularly for farms dependent on monoculture and traditional industrial practices. Businesses would need to restructure their operations, potentially

facing higher costs and operational complexity. Economic adjustment pressures would affect sectors ranging from agriculture to tourism, requiring new management approaches and infrastructure.

Social Factors

Strengths of Social/Community Support for Soil Health: The Murcia and Almeria regions show strong social and community support for soil health initiatives among the engaged civil society, driven by a shared awareness of environmental challenges and the value of local landscapes, culture, and tourism. In the Murcia region, legal frameworks mandate the involvement of public authorities and society in protecting the Mar Menor ecosystem, supporting both public and private conservation activities. Grassroots efforts further demonstrate this commitment, with environmental organisations cleaning polluted areas, managing community orchards, and promoting recycling and sustainable land management practices. These collective effort from different segments of the community creates a strong foundation for promoting and maintaining soil health.

Weaknesses in Social/Community Efforts Against Soil Degradation: Several weaknesses hinder community-led soil health efforts in Southeast Spain. While there is a support for soil health initiatives for the engaged parts of civil society, the majority of the civil population has not yet developed an interest in the topic. Raising citizen awareness remains a pending task of local governments. Since the 1960s, rapid urbanisation and tourism have strained natural resources and reduced water and sediment retention, especially during tourist seasons. Persistent infrastructure issues, such as sewerage deficiencies, reflect broader social planning and maintenance gaps. Community behaviours also undermine soil health, including insufficient waste sorting, reliance on imported goods over local produce, and crop residue burning. Certain recreational activities additionally damage soils, indicating a disconnect between environmental awareness and actual practices.

Opportunities of soil health for local communities and social development: Improving soil health presents valuable opportunities for social development in the region. A key opportunity is the recognition and recovery of both the material and immaterial cultural heritage associated with the Mar Menor, particularly the preservation of local practices and traditional knowledge related to sustainable resource management. Additionally, sustainable farming practices have the potential to mitigate rural depopulation. Joint community participation in soil restoration initiatives fosters stronger community ties, while improved soil health enhances food security and community resilience. Better overall environmental conditions also contribute to improved air and water quality. The region faces serious societal risks from ongoing soil and water degradation, particularly in Mar Menor lagoon, which jeopardises tourism, recreation, and fishing. Soil degradation, on the other hand, threatens long-term food security and public health. Excessive fertilisation and poor water management create a cycle of environmental degradation, elevating contamination in aquifers and leading to greater exposure to soil pollutants.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local communities and social development: The provided data does not explicitly address potential threats of soil health improvements. Inferring from literature, following potential threats could be identified: Economic disruption is a possibility, as the transition to sustainable practices could temporarily reduce agricultural productivity, financially burden some farmers and displace traditional agricultural jobs. Social resistance could arise from changes to established practices, new regulations that create tensions between community groups, and restrictions that affect local cultural practices. Resource allocation could become a point of contention, with funding for soil health potentially reducing resources for other community needs, changes in land use limiting space for development or recreation, and investment in new technologies disadvantaging smaller farmers. In addition, tourism could be affected by environmental restrictions

limiting activities, changes in landscape management affecting attractions, and potential reductions in seasonal employment.

Technological Factors

Strengths of current technologies for soil health: There are significant technological strengths in agricultural management and maintaining soil health:

1. Advanced monitoring technologies, like sophisticated sensor networks, tensiometers to monitor soil moisture, real-time nutrient monitoring systems, equipment to optimise water and fertiliser application
2. Conservation infrastructure, like mandatory implementation of vegetative barriers, buffer strips to control run-off, erosion control structures, systems to promote nutrient uptake, which were recently implemented with the “Mar Menor” Law.
3. Digital management systems, like electronic registry systems to track the movement of livestock manure, advanced fertiliser application monitoring platforms, digital tools to control over-fertilisation, integrated data management systems

Weaknesses of current technologies countering soil health: Current technologies in the region have several significant weaknesses in addressing environmental and soil health issues:

1. Groundwater management problems, like inadequate technologies to control aquifer contamination, high levels of nutrients continue to enter the coastal lagoon, limited effectiveness in preventing groundwater pollution from agricultural activities, inadequate systems for managing increased recharge from rainfall
2. Deficiencies in erosion and sediment control, like current retention structures struggle to fully manage watershed runoff, inadequate technological solutions to control sedimentation, limited effectiveness of existing erosion control measures, challenges in managing pollutant transport through sediment movement

Opportunities of novel technologies: There are significant opportunities for technological advances in environmental management:

1. Agricultural innovation, like mandatory implementation of closed cropping systems, integration of nutrient recycling technologies, use of microbial inoculants for soil health, development of rainfed cropping technologies
2. Water management solutions, like mandatory rainwater harvesting in greenhouses, sustainable urban drainage systems, green roof technologies for new developments, stormwater runoff reduction systems, and nutrient recovery from wastewaters and polluted water bodies
3. Nature-based technologies, like implementation of vegetated buffers, biofilter installation, natural erosion control systems, nutrient retention through organic solutions
4. Waste management technologies, like enhancement of waste recycling systems, demolition reuse technologies (sustainable materials processing and circular economy solutions)

Potential threats of novel technologies: The implementation of new technologies in the region carries several risks, emphasizing the need for careful planning, thorough testing, and proper monitoring. Novel technologies may have unintended environmental side effects or fail to deliver the expected improvements. Additional risks include

high implementation costs, potential failures, challenges in operator training, difficulties in integrating with existing infrastructure, and unforeseen environmental consequences.

Legal Factors

Strengths of current legal regulations for soil health: The Region of Murcia has established a strong legal framework to protect soil health, particularly through the *Law for the Recovery and Protection of the Mar Menor* (Law 19/2022). This law recognises the Mar Menor lagoon and its basins as a 'sensitive area' with stricter controls on nutrient pollution, enabling targeted measures for soil health improvement. Key provisions include the promotion of sustainable and precision agriculture, restrictions on fertiliser use, mandatory vegetation structures on farms to retain water, and the return of abandoned irrigated land to natural states to reduce erosion. Additionally, the law tackles nitrate pollution by designating vulnerable zones and implementing action programmes. The creation of a specialised council enhances coordination and enforcement of these regulations. These efforts form a robust legal foundation aimed at soil health improvement and sustainable land management.

Weaknesses of current legal regulations countering soil health: Despite the strengths, several weaknesses hinder the law's effectiveness. Implementation and enforcement remain key challenges, particularly with coordination across different administrative levels and sectors. Limited resources for monitoring and enforcement further exacerbate these challenges. While the law restricts fertiliser use and land conversion, its impact on agricultural productivity and economic viability may cause resistance if not properly supported by incentives for farmers. Moreover, the law focuses on preventing future damage but fails to address the legacy of past practices, such as historical contamination from mining and accumulated nitrates. Additionally, regulations mainly focus on nutrient pollution and lack provisions for managing other pollutants, such as pesticides and herbicides. Finally, limited public awareness and participation in the regulatory process can undermine the effectiveness of the framework.

Opportunities associated with legal regulations for soil health: The legal framework offers several opportunities to enhance soil health management. One key opportunity is the development of a *Territorial Spatial Plan* for the Mar Menor watershed, integrating land use planning with environmental protection. The law provides opportunities for more targeted measures to reduce agricultural nutrient inputs, including promoting precision agriculture, optimising fertiliser use, and enhancing livestock waste management. Restoring abandoned or degraded farmland presents another significant opportunity for soil health improvement. Improved coordination and cooperation across government levels, stakeholders, and civil society could drive innovative solutions. Additionally, investing in research and fostering collaboration between policymakers, scientists, and practitioners can help implement more effective soil health management practices.

Potential threats associated with legal regulations for soil health: The main threats to soil health from the legal framework stem from environmental, economic, and social factors, highlighting the interrelationship with the analysed PESTLE factors: Ongoing environmental degradation due to diffuse pollution sources and past contamination, which complicate remediation efforts. Conflicts between sectors, such as agriculture and environmental protection, hinder effective coordination. Additionally, challenges in coordinating and enforcing regulations across different government levels limit the law's impact. Economic burdens on agriculture, particularly from restrictions on fertilisers and pesticides, may reduce farmers' cooperation. Lastly, social resistance, fuelled by a lack of awareness and public participation, could undermine the effectiveness of legal measures and delay necessary changes.

Environmental Factors

Strengths of the natural environment for soil health: The local environment in the Murcia region and Almeria presents several strengths that positively influence soil health. The region's dry conditions, characterised by limited rainfall, help reduce organic matter degradation and minimise pest outbreaks, promoting healthier soils. Additionally, the region benefits from ample sun hours, which support plant growth and soil development. The type of rainfall, often short and abundant, contributes to soil erosion, pushing the region towards infertile land and desertification. The diverse geology of the area results in a variety of soil types, each offering unique ecological functions. Rich animal and microbial biodiversity thrive in these harsh conditions, contributing to soil health through natural processes like nutrient cycling. The presence of valuable natural habitats, including seagrass meadows and endangered species, further strengthens the region's ecological balance. In some steep mountain areas forested areas in the watershed play a critical role in soil protection, runoff regulation, and carbon sequestration, offering additional benefits to soil health.

Weaknesses of the local environmental conditions countering soil health: Several environmental and ecological factors pose challenges to soil health in the Murcia region and Almeria. High temperatures accelerate the degradation of organic matter, which reduces soil fertility and structure. Limited access to high-quality water due to low rainfall further strains soil health, as insufficient moisture hinders plant growth and nutrient cycling. The region is also prone to high erosion rates driven by both infrequent and intense rain, and wind patterns, combined with unsustainable soil management practices, which deplete topsoil and degrade soil structure. Climate change exacerbates these issues, leading to reduced water availability, more extreme weather events, and the loss of biodiversity. The limited coverage with trees and bushes in vast agricultural agriculture exacerbate the effects, due to a lack of protection from the sun and erosion. These changes threaten well-established local plant varieties and contribute to increased risks of erosion, desertification, and salinisation, which ultimately undermine soil health and the broader ecosystem.

Opportunities of soil health for the natural environment: Improving soil health offers significant opportunities to enhance environmental resilience and reduce vulnerability to pests. Healthy soils support biodiversity reservoirs by maintaining diverse habitats, which are crucial for protected species. By enhancing the soil's filtering and cooling functions, soil health improvements contribute to better water and air quality. This is especially important in the Mar Menor region, where healthy soils prevent erosion and nutrient runoff, protecting aquatic environments like seagrass meadows. Such improvements support fish species, aid in the recovery of endangered species like the fan mussel, and benefit aquatic bird communities by sustaining a healthy food web and ecosystem.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for the natural environment: While improving soil health offers numerous benefits, there are risks to the environment and ecology. The use of agricultural inputs can increase contamination and nutrient transfer to the food chain, potentially degrading water quality in the Mar Menor lagoon. Reduced soil filtration capacity can exacerbate eutrophication, further harming aquatic ecosystems. Additionally, changes in land use to enhance soil health could increase the risk of flooding and soil erosion in the watershed. Excessive nutrient loading and contamination remain concerns, and improper management of soil health initiatives could negatively impact the overall balance of the ecosystem, undermining the benefits intended for the environment.

Implications for stakeholder mapping and co-creation

The stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis provide valuable insights for stakeholder engagement and co-creation within the Spanish Living Lab. The stakeholder mapping offers specific recommendations on managing stakeholder groups, identifying which stakeholders to engage closely, which to keep satisfied, which to inform, and which to monitor. Complementing this, the baseline analysis highlights opportunities presented by soil health initiatives across political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental dimensions. These opportunities can serve as compelling arguments to involve relevant stakeholders in Living Lab activities. Simultaneously, the analysis identifies potential threats associated with a focus on soil health that may concern specific stakeholder groups. These concerns can be taken into account in communication strategies and incorporated into Living Lab solutions, ensuring project partners are equipped with clear responses to alleviate existing fears.

This section summarises initial strategies derived from the stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis, recommending different engagement levels—from active co-creation to low-maintenance interactions with peripheral entities. These recommendations will be further refined in collaboration with Living Lab leaders in the coming months, with a particular focus on substantiating and detailing planned co-creation sessions in a publicly accessible report.

Recommended Strategies:

Active engagement through co-creation: Engaging core stakeholders with high interest and influence over soil health in the Living Lab area, such as agricultural operators, associations, consumer groups, organic certification bodies, research and innovation entities, and relevant political and public authorities, is crucial for the success of the co-creation process. Based on the challenges identified in the baseline analysis, involving public utility stakeholders in water management and soil monitoring will also be beneficial. By aligning their strengths with the Living Lab's mission and fostering trust, these stakeholders can drive the initiative's momentum and secure long-term success. Co-creation sessions can address key challenges in the Living Lab location, such as sustaining agricultural activity while reducing its negative impact on soil health, minimising soil pollution, enhancing restoration, and improving soil biodiversity. Co-creation sessions can thereby serve to define solutions, identify scaling pathways, co-create business models, and develop the necessary frameworks for their success. Moreover, participation in co-creation sessions fosters a sense of ownership and ensures long-term commitment to the project's objectives, which is essential for its sustained impact.

Empower Research Organisations and Learning Centres: Empowering leading research organisations to play a more active role in soil management and monitoring, e.g. by becoming an educative hub for practicing agricultural engineers, public auditors, and farmers.

Maintain Engagement with Peripheral Entities for Future Opportunities: By actively monitoring economic and technological stakeholders with less impact and interest in regard to the Living Lab, they remain within reach for dissemination and scaling of practices once the actions were tested successfully. In that case, their interest may rise and it will be possible to apply the solutions at smaller farms or other close regions that currently are outside the scope of the Living Lab.

Enable Long-term Planning: While the Living Lab will mainly test solutions for the particular identified challenges, there are also larger challenges to be tackled in regard to the long-term scaling and implementation of the solutions, which come from cross-sectoral challenges. The Living Lab could serve as the first step to overcome thinking silos and bridge sectoral barriers to enable long-term planning with a high acceptance of relevant stakeholders of all sectors. The Living Lab serves as the perfect hub to identify cross-sectoral strategies to reverse the soil deterioration. For this, key stakeholders of all sectors will have to be involved. Further, the engagement strategy should enable these stakeholders to set up procedures and networks that will inform the local policy making and economic decision making beyond the project's lifetime.

Raise Awareness for Soil Health Opportunities in the broader Community: While certain community groups strongly advocate for environmental sustainability, the majority of the general population is not yet fully aware of environmental concerns. The Living Lab can assist local governments in raising awareness by showcasing its results to a broader audience through targeted awareness campaigns.

Leveraging Cross-cutting Challenges for Engagement: Soil health is a truly cross-sectoral challenge in Murcia and Almeria, however the awareness for this issue is often trumped by more salient economic, political, and social challenges. Thus, by highlighting the cross-sectoral benefits of soil health and the risks of deteriorating soil health can help to engage more stakeholders which are currently less interested in participating.

Keep Tabs on “Monitor” Stakeholders for Future Gains: It is recommended to stay ahead of the curve by observing low-interest, low-power stakeholders for changes in their engagement levels. With a proactive monitoring strategy, the Italian Living Lab can seize opportunities to involve these actors when their relevance grows, ensuring no valuable ally slips through the cracks.

Swedish Soil Health Living Lab

Introduction

Overview of the Swedish Soil Health Living Lab's Objectives

The Swedish AgroSoils Living Lab addresses the challenges associated with soil health on crop and animal production farms. Its focus is on issues such as soil compaction, poor soil structure, reduced biodiversity, and nutrient imbalances, particularly phosphorus surplus. The objective of the project is to enhance soil health through the integration of collaborative research and practical implementation. A total of fifteen co-created test sites, in addition to one or two lighthouse farms, will be employed for the purposes of collaborative research and development. The Living Lab is led by the Department of Agriculture and Food of the Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE). Key stakeholders include research institutions, such as the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, as well as farmer representatives, such as HS Konsult and the Odling i balans network, and relevant authorities, such as the National Board of Agriculture and the National Veterinary Authority. This multi-sectoral collaboration provides a platform for the development and testing of practical solutions. The potential solutions under consideration include crop rotations to enhance soil fertility and nitrogen delivery, cover cropping, conservation tillage, the use of lightweight autonomous tractors, controlled drainage, the replacement of mineral fertilisers with bio-based alternatives, biostimulants and biochar, as well as the sharing of manure between animal and crop farms. It is anticipated that the project will yield improved soil health, augmented farm productivity, and more sustainable agricultural practices.

Geographical Location and Context

The Swedish Living Lab covers several coastal provinces in Götaland, the southernmost of Sweden's three regions. Götaland has an area of approx. 97,841 square kilometres and a population of approx. 4.8 million inhabitants. The topography of Götaland is varied: fertile coastal plains, which are ideal for agriculture, give way to rolling hills and valleys inland, which are often used for forestry or as pastureland. The extensive forests, dominated by coniferous production forest, but also deciduous forests, are of great economic and ecological importance. There are numerous groups of islands along the coast, which were formed as a result of reformation after the Ice Age. There are also many lakes and rivers in the region, including Vänern and Vättern. Although the southern Swedish highlands in Småland are not mountainous, they form the highest point of Götaland and are characterised by rounded hills, plateaus and valleys. The soils in the interior of the region are predominantly silt, with a higher percentage of peaty soils compared to the coastal areas. In contrast, the coastal areas are primarily clay soils, often containing some silt or sand, which may also be classified as loam (Råberg, 2008). As is common in the Nordic countries, the main problem of erosion is that phosphorus, pesticides and other water pollutants bound to eroded material end up in water bodies (Ulen, 2012). Other problems in the study area include soil compaction, poor soil structure and a decline in biodiversity.

Stakeholder Mapping Results

The stakeholder mapping for the Swedish Living Lab reveals a strong focus on economic and technological domains, which are central to the lab's objectives of promoting sustainable agricultural practices and innovative soil management solutions. The mapping identified a total of 67 stakeholders across five main sectors: economic (34), technological (14), political (10), environmental (5), and social (4). This distribution highlights the Living Lab's emphasis on aligning agricultural productivity with ecological sustainability, while also recognizing the important role of environmental, political, and social factors in shaping the broader landscape of soil management.

The Economic stakeholders, which include associations, farms, farm supply entities, and processing units, form the largest group and are critical to the success of the Living Lab. Key actors in the economic domain, such as farm associations and interest groups, are primarily classified as "Manage Closely." In total, 19 farms are also ranked in this category, indicating their central role in implementing sustainable agricultural practices. Smaller numbers of farm supply entities are classified as "Monitor" or "Keep Satisfied," suggesting that while they have an interest in sustainable practices, their current level of involvement is more limited. Processing stakeholders, although fewer in number, are also closely managed to ensure alignment with environmental sustainability standards. Economic stakeholders face challenges related to balancing high agricultural yields with soil health preservation. To engage these stakeholders, the Living Lab should prioritise co-creation processes and capacity-building initiatives, ensuring that their needs and objectives are aligned with the overarching goals of soil health and sustainable land use.

Environmental stakeholders are equally crucial, particularly in addressing soil degradation. This group includes environmental associations, innovation entities, and private organic standards organisations. One environmental association is classified as "Manage Closely," indicating a strong need for collaboration on sustainable practices that mitigate soil contamination and restore soil health. Of the two innovation facilitators in the environmental sector, one is closely managed while the other is kept informed. Similarly, the private organic standards group is categorised as "Manage Closely." These environmental stakeholders are driven by the need to combat soil degradation, protect biodiversity, and restore nutrient balance, making them essential collaborators for identifying and implementing solutions to these pressing environmental challenges. To engage this group effectively, the Living Lab should focus on fostering collaboration to develop and scale innovative solutions, aligning ecological and economic objectives in the process.

Political stakeholders, which include associations, innovation entities, and public authorities, play a pivotal role in shaping agricultural policies and ensuring compliance with soil health regulations. One political association is highly engaged and influential, while five public authorities have been identified, with three classified as "Manage Closely" and others as "Keep Informed" or "Monitor." Political stakeholders are primarily concerned with soil health monitoring and providing insights that inform government policy. Their engagement in the Living Lab is critical for influencing legislative frameworks and ensuring that the policies supporting sustainable land use are robust and well-enforced. To maximise the impact of political stakeholders, the Living Lab should focus on strengthening partnerships, leveraging data-driven insights to influence policy decisions, and advocating for the development of effective regulatory measures that align with sustainable agricultural practices.

Social stakeholders including innovation and training organisations, are key in promoting sustainable practices within local communities. This group is concerned with issues such as soil compaction, low carbon content, and nutrient imbalances, which directly affect soil health and agricultural productivity. Four innovation-focused

organisations have been identified, with two ranked as “Manage Closely” and one as “Keep Informed.” Additionally, one agricultural training provider is highly influential and engaged, reflecting the need for targeted training and education to support sustainable farming practices. Engaging social stakeholders should focus on building capacity through targeted training programs, facilitating knowledge-sharing platforms, and promoting cross-sectoral collaboration. These initiatives will enable local communities to adopt sustainable practices, building resilience in agricultural systems at the grassroots level.

Technological stakeholders which include innovation and research entities, are key players in the development of novel tools and technologies for sustainable soil management. Of the 14 technological stakeholders identified, five are innovation entities, with two ranked as highly influential and engaged, while nine are research organisations, including public and private institutes and universities. Four of these research organisations are highly engaged and influential. Technological stakeholders bring essential expertise in developing innovative technologies and practices that can enhance soil health, such as advanced soil monitoring systems and sustainable land management tools. The Living Lab should prioritise partnerships with these stakeholders, fostering collaboration between researchers and practitioners to accelerate the adoption of cutting-edge technologies and solutions for sustainable agriculture.

Figure 12: Swedish Living Lab: Stakeholder Map

In summary, the stakeholder analysis of the Swedish Living Lab underscores the importance of strategic engagement across different sectors. Economic stakeholders should be closely involved in co-creation and capacity-building efforts, while environmental and social stakeholders should be empowered through innovative

environmental challenges. Engaging these stakeholders in co-creation processes and decision-making forums will be key to developing and scaling sustainable solutions. In this quadrant, we also find public authorities and political interest groups with high influence on regulatory frameworks and policy. These stakeholders are concerned with soil health regulation and providing insights that inform government policy. Their high power and interest make them key allies in shaping the broader legislative and policy environment for sustainable agriculture and soil management. Innovation entities and research organisations focused on developing new technologies for soil monitoring and management also fall into this quadrant. Their high influence and technical expertise will be essential for advancing the Living Lab's technological innovations, making their active participation in the co-creation process vital to ensuring that cutting-edge technologies are effectively integrated into sustainable agricultural practices.

Keep Satisfied - High Power, Low Interest: Some farm supply entities and smaller processing units fall into this category. They possess significant power within the agricultural supply chain but may not yet have a strong interest in the specific goals of the Living Lab. Engaging these stakeholders involves demonstrating the long-term benefits of sustainable agricultural practices, highlighting how these align with their strategic objectives, such as resource efficiency and economic sustainability. A small subset of political stakeholders, such as certain public authorities, also fall into this quadrant. While they may not be directly involved in the day-to-day operations of the Living Lab, they possess the power to shape policies and influence the regulatory environment. Efforts to keep these stakeholders satisfied should focus on providing evidence of the broader benefits of sustainable soil management and the lab's contributions to achieving national or regional policy goals.

Keep Informed - Low Power, High Interest: One farm is classified as “Keep Informed,” reflecting their interest in sustainable practices and soil health but lower power to directly influence the lab's operations. These stakeholders may benefit from knowledge-sharing opportunities, training, and capacity-building efforts that help them adopt innovative practices at the farm level. A few environmental innovation entities fall into this quadrant, indicating their interest in solving soil-related environmental challenges but with a limited capacity to influence broader sectoral or policy changes. Keeping these stakeholders informed through regular updates and engaging them in knowledge exchange forums will be key to enhancing their capacity to advocate for sustainable soil management. Innovation and training organisations focused on local community engagement are also classified as “Keep Informed.” These stakeholders are highly interested in promoting sustainable practices but may not have the power to drive large-scale change. Providing targeted capacity-building opportunities and creating spaces for knowledge-sharing will empower these stakeholders to play a more active role in promoting sustainable agricultural practices at the grassroots level.

Monitor - Low Power, Low Interest: Some farm supply entities and smaller processing stakeholders are classified as “Monitor,” reflecting their minimal current interest in the lab's objectives. They may not yet see the value of engaging in the lab's activities but could become more engaged as the project develops. Certain political actors and public authorities also fall into this category, indicating that they are currently not actively involved in the Living Lab. However, as the lab progresses, their interest in soil health and sustainable agricultural practices may increase, particularly if policy changes or regulatory requirements evolve.

Baseline Analysis: Local Ecosystems of the Living Lab

Introduction

Living Lab leaders were asked to rate PESTLE influences on a scale from -5 (strong negative influence) to +5 (strong positive influence). These ratings are presented here as they offer a valuable overview for the analysis:

The state of soil health in the Living Lab locations in Sweden is a complex interplay of different factors. The initial assessment indicates a predominantly positive environment for soil health initiatives, with particularly strong political support (rated +4) and civil society engagement (rated +4). While economic incentives (rated +2) and technological implementations (rated +2) show moderate positive impacts, there is room for further development. The legal and regulatory framework (rated +3) provides a supportive foundation for soil health protection, and the current soil condition maintains a moderately healthy status (rated +2). This generally favourable context sets the stage for a detailed examination of the PESTLE factors affecting soil health in southern Sweden. The following analysis examines the strengths, weaknesses, risks and opportunities in each of these dimensions, providing a thorough understanding of the current situation and potential pathways for improvement in soil health management.

Political Factors

Strengths of current political actions and policies for soil health: The strengths of current policy and action for soil health in Southern Sweden are multi-faceted. The European Soil Monitoring Act provides a robust framework for monitoring and promoting soil health, promoting accountability and action at different levels. The Swedish Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy (European Commission, 2022a) shows a clear commitment to environmental and climate objectives, in particular by supporting organic production and precision farming. Regulations on environmental considerations in agriculture, especially regarding plant nutrients (Föreskrifter om ändring i Statens jordbruksverks föreskrifter och allmänna råd), help to mitigate problems related to nutrient leaching. The involvement of nature conservation organisations is crucial. The Swedish Society for Nature Conservation (Naturskyddsföreningen) promotes the sustainable use of natural resources, including topsoil management, while the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (Naturvårdsverket) actively proposes and implements environmental policies related to soil health at both national and European level. The existence of a Nordic network for discussing soil health issues, including standardised sampling methods and practices, enables knowledge sharing and promotes regional cooperation. This collaborative approach strengthens the overall implementation of soil health initiatives across the region. While the economic support system primarily favours large-scale agriculture, there are provisions to support young farmers who could potentially drive innovation in sustainable soil management practices.

Weaknesses of current political actions and policies countering soil health: Sweden's soil health policies reveal weaknesses rooted in historical decisions and current agricultural practices. Since the 1800s, policies promoting farm expansion have led to larger fields and heavy machinery use, causing deep soil compaction that is difficult to reverse. The economic support system favours large-scale farming, reinforcing this trend and worsening soil health issues. Policies aiming to increase yields have also led to higher nutrient inputs. However, research in Sweden indicates that as long as nitrogen application remains within the N-optimum, higher input does not necessarily result in increased nutrient losses. Eutrophication risks may still arise during autumn rains if crops do not fully utilize the applied nutrients. Despite the existence of directives and regulations, balancing environmental

and productivity goals is challenging, and coordination among stakeholders such as conservation groups, farmers, and policymakers often leads to gaps in implementation. Additionally, the current policy framework lacks direct economic incentives for maintaining soil health.

Opportunities of soil health for local politics: Swedish respondents highlighted the opportunities presented by soil health initiatives, such as the iCOSHells Living Lab, for political development. A key benefit lies in the data and knowledge generated by the Living Labs, which provide practical demonstrations of sustainable soil management solutions. These insights can feed directly into European Commission decision-making, shaping future policy recommendations and regulations. Locally, improving soil health can support agricultural productivity, ensuring food availability and affordability, which contributes to social stability and reduces the risk of political unrest.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local politics: Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local politics include financial burdens on smaller farmers, which may deepen the rural-urban divide and provoke resistance. Short-term productivity losses could increase pressure from agricultural lobbies, while investment demands might weaken support for incumbent leaders. Conflicts may arise between food security and environmental goals, as well as local priorities and EU regulations. Competition for agricultural funding and perceived restrictive regulations could lead to protests, echoing recent European demonstrations. Resistance from traditional farming constituencies and allied industries may further hinder progress. Administrative challenges, such as enforcing standards and managing complex regulations, could undermine political credibility and provoke backlash.

Economic Factors

Strengths of current economic actions for soil health: The strengths of the current economic measures for soil health in Sweden are noteworthy and contribute positively to sustainable agricultural practices. A key strength is the existence of economic incentives, such as the investment packages offered by Svensk kolinlagring, which support farmers in implementing measures to improve soil health and promote carbon sequestration. These incentives include carbon credits and research funding to develop sustainable farming techniques. In addition, the Swedish Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) offers eco-schemes and coupled payments that encourage practices that benefit soil health, such as intercropping, catch crops, precision farming and organic production. This financial support helps farmers to adopt practices that improve soil quality and reduce environmental impacts. In addition, growing recognition of the ecological value of healthy soils has led to increased investment in sustainable farming practices. However, it is important to note, that while this shift can benefit the environment and open opportunities for farmers to diversify into emerging markets for organic products, economic challenges such as inflation and recession have currently led to decreased organic consumption, prompting some farmers to return to conventional practices for economic viability.

Weaknesses of current economic actions countering soil health: A major problem is that the existing economic support system tends to favour large-scale farming and the use of heavy machinery. This has led to soil compaction, which is detrimental to soil structure and health. There is also a tendency to specialise in annual cash crops with short rotations, which can reduce soil fertility and biodiversity. The lack of deep-rooted crops or legumes in the southern region further exacerbates soil degradation. Another concern is the accumulation of manure from concentrated livestock farms, which leads to nutrient leaching and greenhouse gas emissions. This not only affects soil health, but also contributes to environmental problems such as eutrophication of waterways. In addition, the focus on maximising yields through high nutrient inputs can create a cycle of dependence on chemical fertilisers,

which can degrade soil health over time. These economic practices often overlook the long-term sustainability of soil ecosystems, resulting in adverse effects that counteract efforts to promote soil health.

Opportunities of soil health for local economic development: Maintaining healthy soils offers significant opportunities for local economic development by enhancing agricultural productivity and reducing the risks associated with soil degradation. Healthy soils support higher crop yields, directly benefiting farmers' incomes and overall economic stability. Sustainable practices such as reduced tillage, crop rotation, and biochar applications not only improve soil quality but also contribute to long-term economic resilience. Moreover, while consumer demand for organic and sustainably produced foods has shown fluctuations, these practices still hold potential to create new market opportunities for farmers, particularly in regions or markets where such demand remains strong. Technological innovations like precision agriculture also enhance soil health while boosting productivity, creating growth prospects in agricultural technology. On the other hand, healthy soils help mitigate risks such as soil erosion, flooding, and droughts, which can severely disrupt agricultural activities and lead to higher costs for remediation. By preventing these challenges, healthy soils reduce financial burdens and support a more stable, sustainable agricultural economy.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local economic development: Soil health initiatives are generally viewed as beneficial for local economic development. However, they may be perceived as a threat by traditional economic actors who favour large-scale, intensive farming with heavy machinery. The transition period could be associated with temporary yield losses, reduced productivity, and lower profitability until sustainable farming practices are fully established. Potential threats to economic development include the financial burden of high initial investment costs for new farming practices, specialised equipment, and training. Additionally, if soil health initiatives promote sustainable farming, there may be market-related risks, such as competitive disadvantages arising from higher production costs compared to conventional farming methods.

Social Factors

Strengths of social/community support for soil health: An important strength of social factors for soil health is the active involvement of organisations such as the Swedish Society for Nature Conservation, which promotes the sustainable use of natural resources and raises awareness of the importance of soil health. In addition, initiatives such as Svensk kolinlagring link farmers with companies willing to pay for practices that improve soil health, such as crop rotation and carbon storage. This collaboration promotes community engagement and provides financial incentives for sustainable practices. Projects at institutions such as the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) also support 'soil health entrepreneurs', encouraging innovation and the adoption of new farming practices. These educational programmes help build capacity within communities and empower farmers to implement practices that benefit soil health. Community-based initiatives, such as Andelsodling i Berg and Odling I balans, promote sustainable farming practices and increase soil literacy among local residents. These grassroots efforts encourage farmers to work together and create a shared commitment to improving soil health. Finally, the willingness of neighbouring farmers to work together, as seen in initiatives such as the Hasta farm, demonstrates a strong community spirit focused on developing new approaches to soil health and sustainability.

Weaknesses of social/community activities countering soil health: An important issue is the lack of experience and knowledge among some community members, which can slow down the adoption of new crops and innovative farming practices. This lack of understanding can hinder effective action to improve soil health. In addition, community initiatives may face resistance due to local concerns, such as the potential for unpleasant odours when

animal manure is shared between farms. This can lead to backlash against soil health practices, creating tensions within communities. Also, a lack of coordination between different community groups and stakeholders can lead to fragmented efforts rather than a unified approach to soil health.

Opportunities of soil health for local communities and social development: Opportunities of soil health for local communities and social development in Sweden include several key benefits. Healthy soils contribute to higher crop yields and better-quality produce, improving food security and providing a stable food supply. Promoting soil health also enhances ecosystem services, such as water retention and filtration, crucial for maintaining clean water supplies. Improved soil and environmental quality support local recreational activities, fostering community well-being. Community involvement in soil health initiatives strengthens collective responsibility and stewardship. Furthermore, good soil health enhances environmental resilience. For instance, soil health improvements enhance water retention and reduce the risk flooding and infrastructure damage.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for local communities and social development: Several potential challenges may hinder initiatives to improve soil health in local communities. Social conflicts could arise from community resistance to new practices, potentially marginalising existing local knowledge and creating tensions. Power imbalances might emerge when larger agricultural units dominate decision-making, sidelining local communities and their priorities. Resource competition may lead to environmental trade-offs, diverting attention from other pressing community needs. Knowledge gaps, stemming from inadequate training or information overload, could result in poor implementation and unintended land degradation. Additionally, climate change impacts present adaptation challenges that could threaten the long-term success of soil health initiatives. Finally, the erosion of cultural heritage may occur if culturally significant farming practices are undermined.

Technological Factors

Strengths of current technologies for soil health: Current technologies used to improve soil health in Sweden have a number of significant strengths. In particular, the adoption of precision farming techniques has revolutionised crop management by using data and analysis to inform decision making. This enables farmers to optimise nutrient application, irrigation and pest control, ultimately leading to improved soil health and increased productivity. The integration of autonomous machinery, such as solar-powered tractors and automated planting systems, represents an emerging innovation with significant potential, though its adoption remains limited so far. By minimising the weight and frequency of machine traffic on fields, these innovations help to reduce soil compaction, preserving soil structure and health. Another notable development is the Nonstop Battery Concept, an innovative approach designed to facilitate the transition to battery-powered agricultural equipment and reduce dependence on fossil fuels. Although still in its early stages and not yet widely adopted, this concept enables robots or machines to operate continuously without separate stops to recharge or replace batteries. This shift helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions and supports sustainable farming practices. In addition, soil amendment technologies such as biochar and beneficial micro-organisms play a vital role in improving soil quality and promoting long-term carbon storage.

Weaknesses of current technologies countering soil health: The weaknesses of current soil health technologies in Sweden present several challenges. A major problem is the historical trend towards increasing field sizes and machine sizes, which has led to deeper soil compaction. This compaction is difficult to repair and has a negative impact on soil structure and health. In addition, the reliance on high nutrient inputs to increase crop yields can cause environmental problems if not managed properly. Excessive nutrient application can lead to nutrient run-off,

contributing to eutrophication in waterways and harming aquatic ecosystems. Another concern is specialisation in either animal or crop production, which can lead to an imbalance in nutrient supply in certain areas. This lack of diversity in farming systems can reduce the overall resilience of farming practices and soil health.

Opportunities of novel technologies: Emerging technologies hold great promise for improving soil health and promoting sustainable agriculture. The strategic use of biochar, beneficial microorganisms and mycorrhizal fungi can potentially increase soil quality while facilitating long-term carbon sequestration. In addition, AI-enabled soil analysis and management systems can provide farmers with actionable insights, enabling them to adopt more sustainable and environmentally responsible farming practices. In addition, innovative solutions such as the Compaction Prevention System can enable farmers to make informed decisions about the timing and use of equipment, minimising greenhouse gas emissions from the soil. The Compaction Prevention System is a technology that provides automated, real-time monitoring of potential soil compaction. It enables farmers to make informed decisions about their operations, optimise equipment use and minimise the risk of soil compaction, ultimately promoting healthier soils and more sustainable farming practices (Novel Agro, n.d).

Potential threats of novel technologies: A notable concern is the potentially high financial investment required to adopt new technologies, such as autonomous machinery and advanced precision farming tools. For smallholders, these costs may be insurmountable, leading to unequal access to beneficial innovations. Questions may also be raised about the reliability and long-term effectiveness of new technologies. If these innovations fail to meet expectations or have unforeseen adverse effects on soil health or the environment. There is also a risk of over-reliance on technology, which could lead to the abandonment of traditional farming practices that are essential for maintaining soil health. This could create a dependency on technological solutions, ultimately reducing the resilience of farming systems in the face of environmental challenges and unforeseen perturbations. The introduction of new technologies can also disrupt established farming practices and community dynamics, creating challenges for farmers trying to integrate new systems into traditional methods.

Legal Factors

Strengths of current legal regulations for soil health: Sweden's commitment to environmental sustainability is underpinned by a strong legislative framework, including the European Soil Monitoring Directive and national environmental objectives such as "A diverse agricultural landscape", "Zero eutrophication" and "A non-toxic environment" (OECD, 2018). These objectives provide a solid foundation for preserving biodiversity, reducing nutrient leaching and minimising the use of chemical pesticides. In addition, KRAV's organic certification standards (KRAV, 2023), which in some cases exceed EU requirements, play a crucial role in promoting soil-friendly farming practices. By encouraging farmers to adopt more sustainable and environmentally conscious practices, these standards help to ensure the long-term health and fertility of Sweden's soils, ultimately supporting a more sustainable food system.

Weaknesses of current legal regulations countering soil health: While the existing legislative framework includes positive measures such as fertiliser limits and manure management rules, significant limitations remain. In particular, the European Soil Observation Law lacks legally binding targets and robust soil biodiversity descriptors, making it insufficient to effectively address soil degradation. This represents a missed opportunity to establish concrete mechanisms to ensure the long-term sustainability of Europe's soils. While initiatives such as KRAV standards and potential Soil Management Index-based (cf. Williams et al., 2020) support schemes are promising, their effectiveness depends on successful implementation and stakeholder engagement.

Opportunities associated with legal regulations for soil health: The active involvement of policy stakeholders, in particular the Swedish Board of Agriculture and the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, in the Living Lab creates significant opportunities for evidence-based policy development. The ability of the Living Lab to provide these stakeholders with data, reviews and conclusions that directly inform their daily work can more effectively influence future legislation. One promising opportunity is the development of innovative subsidy schemes based on the Soil Management Index, which could incentivise farmers to adopt better soil management practices without the need for costly and time-consuming field sampling. This approach would represent a shift from traditional categorisation (such as organic versus conventional) to performance-based incentives that directly reward environmental services. In addition, the existing framework of KRAV standards, which exceed EU requirements for organic production, demonstrates the potential for implementing more stringent soil health measures.

Potential threats associated with legal regulations for soil health: A key concern with current legislation is the complex interplay between implementation requirements and stakeholder engagement. While the Living Lab approach facilitates engagement with policy stakeholders, effective implementation of soil health measures requires coordination across multiple regulatory levels - local, regional, national and European. The current framework requires careful monitoring and enforcement. The proposed move to Soil Management Index-based subsidy schemes, while promising for incentivising better soil management practices, would require significant changes to existing regulatory structures and measurement systems. These challenges are further complicated by the need to engage different stakeholders, including lawyers and local authorities, to ensure transparency and accountability in soil management decisions.

Environmental Factors

Strengths of the natural environment for soil health: Sweden's temperate climate, with a mean annual temperature of around 8°C and 500–750 mm of rainfall, provides favourable conditions for soil health. The moderate climate supports the accumulation of organic matter in soils, which is essential for maintaining soil structure and biological activity. The combination of cool temperatures and adequate rainfall helps prevent soil erosion and promotes water retention, which benefits plant growth and supports the development of extensive root systems. These root systems enhance soil stability by binding soil particles together and improving water infiltration. Additionally, the cooler climate helps maintain steady moisture levels, which is beneficial for soil organisms, including mycorrhizal fungi. Reduced mechanical disturbance, along with Sweden's focus on sustainable farming practices, further supports soil health by encouraging biodiversity and enhancing the soil's capacity to deliver ecosystem services like natural pest control and pollination.

Weaknesses of the natural environment countering soil health: Sweden's current climate provides favourable conditions for soil health, but climate change is affecting these dynamics. Rising temperatures are lengthening the growing season, potentially enhancing plant growth and increasing carbon input to the soil. However, the extended growing season may also make perennial weeds more competitive. Additionally, climate change also brings more unpredictable weather patterns. Droughts can reduce crop yields by limiting plant growth, which in turn leads to less carbon being sequestered in the soil after harvest. Additionally, drought conditions may necessitate increased irrigation, further stressing the system. Intense rainfall events can also disrupt farming operations by preventing harvesting and promoting soil compaction. This reduces crop quality and creates conditions that favour fungal diseases. Flooding, worsened by soil compaction, leads to oxygen-deprived conditions that harm soil microorganisms. Additionally, flooding can cause soil erosion, which often results in phosphorus leaching, further degrading water quality. The loss of biodiversity, particularly pollinators, can limit ecosystem services like pest

management, which may reduce crop yields and subsequently, the amount of carbon left in the soil. While the loss of pollinators has a more indirect impact on soil health, it affects agricultural sustainability in the long term.

Opportunities of soil health for the natural environment: Maintaining healthy soils offers several environmental benefits. Soil compaction can lead to reduced yields and shallower root systems, which degrade soil structure and increase the risk of flooding by reducing water infiltration. Healthy, well-structured soils improve water retention and reduce runoff, helping to mitigate flooding. A diverse cropping sequence, including intercropping and catch crops, can promote a more resilient ecosystem by supporting a greater diversity of soil organisms and insects. By maintaining continuous ground cover and avoiding fallow periods, soil health helps reduce nutrient leaching, preventing excess nutrients from entering nearby water bodies and reducing the risk of eutrophication. Additionally, healthy soils retain moisture more effectively, which can reduce the need for irrigation. This helps reduce pressure on local water resources, such as rivers, where water extraction for irrigation can impact surrounding ecosystems.

Potential threats of soil health improvement measures for the natural environment: Changes in soil chemistry resulting from new amendments may impact existing microbial communities, potentially favouring invasive species over native ones. Water systems may be affected by reduced stream flow due to enhanced soil retention, alterations in drainage patterns impacting wetlands, and shifts in nutrient cycling that could disrupt aquatic ecosystems. Carbon cycling might also be altered, which could affect nutrient availability and slow decomposition processes. Biodiversity may face risks as new management practices could disadvantage native species, modify habitats through changes in soil structure, and lead to the loss of specialised soil organisms. Furthermore, over-application of amendments could create chemical imbalances, affecting nutrient levels, altering soil pH, and leading to the accumulation of undesirable compounds.

Implications for stakeholder engagement and co-creation

The stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis provide valuable insights for stakeholder engagement and co-creation within the Swedish Living Lab. The stakeholder mapping offers specific recommendations on managing stakeholder groups, identifying which stakeholders to engage closely, which to keep satisfied, which to inform, and which to monitor. Complementing this, the baseline analysis highlights opportunities presented by soil health initiatives across political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental dimensions. These opportunities can serve as compelling arguments to involve relevant stakeholders in Living Lab activities. Simultaneously, the analysis identifies potential threats associated with a focus on soil health that may concern specific stakeholder groups. These concerns can be taken into account in communication strategies and incorporated into Living Lab solutions, ensuring project partners are equipped with clear responses to alleviate existing fears.

This section summarises initial strategies derived from the stakeholder mapping and baseline analysis, recommending different engagement levels—from active co-creation to low-maintenance interactions with peripheral entities. These recommendations will be further refined in collaboration with Living Lab leaders in the coming months, with a particular focus on substantiating and detailing planned co-creation sessions in a publicly accessible report.

Recommended strategies:

Active engagement through co-creation: Engaging core stakeholders in the Living Lab activities is pivotal to developing innovative, scientifically robust, practical, and locally accepted soil health solutions in the Swedish LL. Key stakeholders, like agricultural associations, farms, research institutions, and environmental and public authorities, hold high influence and exhibit high interest in the project outcomes. Their contributions can encompass improvement of decisions considering environmental and socio-economic factors, discussing possible implementations and barriers for soil health in the different sites, refining pre-selected solutions, planning and implementing solution testing, and monitoring, evaluating, adapting tested solutions. Participation in co-creation sessions also fosters a sense of ownership and ensures long-term commitment to the project's objectives, which is essential for its sustained impact, as well as avoidance of fragmented efforts, but rather a unified approach. Special emphasis should be placed on engaging key farms and agricultural associations. Actively involving them in co-creation not only enhances solution development but also raises awareness of soil health challenges and empowers them to implement effective solutions. Moreover, cultivating these relationships through regular consultations and tailored communication strategies is crucial, particularly for stakeholders unable to participate directly in co-creation activities.

Boost Engagement with Strategic Powerhouses: Engage stakeholders, such as farm supply entities and public authorities, by demonstrating how the Living Lab's initiatives align with their strategic objectives. For example, emphasise the long-term benefits of sustainable soil practices and agroforestry techniques in enhancing productivity and soil health. Focus on fostering a deeper understanding of the economic, environmental, and policy benefits through targeted communication, case studies, and evidence-based demonstrations. This will help transition them toward more active involvement and enhance their support for the project.

Highlight the potential for social and economic development: Soil health initiatives can generate economic opportunities, leading to job creation in sectors such as sustainable farming, agritourism, and environmental services. These opportunities can be further supported by green investments. The Living Lab can highlight these benefits by developing case studies and engaging with economic and community associations to raise awareness and promote the potential advantages of soil health improvements.

Empower the Grassroots with Knowledge and Tools: Prioritise capacity-building initiatives for stakeholders in the "Keep Informed" quadrant, including innovation-focused organisations and smaller farms. These stakeholders have a high level of interest in the project's objectives but less direct influence. Provide opportunities for training, networking, and knowledge-sharing to empower these stakeholders and enhance their ability to advocate for sustainable practices. Engaging them through collaboration on pilot projects will increase their influence over time and solidify their role as key supporters of the Living Lab's long-term sustainability goals.

Inclusiveness within the engagement strategy: It is important to acknowledge that not all farms have the same economic capacity. Therefore, it is crucial to ensure equal involvement of different farm types to avoid creating disparities between stakeholders. New technologies can disrupt established farming practices and community dynamics, presenting challenges for farmers who are trying to integrate new systems with traditional methods.

Conclusion and Outlook

This report has mapped local stakeholders of the six iCOSHells Living Labs and analyzed their ecosystems using a PESTLE approach. Each Living Lab showcases unique regional strategies for soil health, addressing specific challenges with tailored solutions: The Basque Lab emphasizes collaborative governance and technological innovation to tackle environmental issues through nature-based solutions. The Bulgarian Lab specializes in viticulture, utilizing precision agriculture tools to address demographic challenges and support economic stakeholders. The Greek Lab focuses on the post-lignite transition, aiming to build community resilience and integrate traditional and modern practices for economic diversification. The Italian Lab manages experimental sites with site-specific strategies, integrating with the tourism sector and emphasizing water management and heritage conservation. The Spanish Lab takes a cross-sectoral approach to soil degradation, collaborating with agricultural operators and water utilities to develop long-term planning strategies. Meanwhile, the Swedish Lab adopts a multi-stakeholder approach, balancing economic and ecological interests while promoting collaborative decision-making for sustainable soil management. Each Living Lab addresses region-specific challenges but shares the common goal of promoting soil health and sustainable development.

Several transversal highlights emerge from the analysis of these Living Labs. Firstly, the importance of stakeholder engagement and collaboration is evident across all regions. Whether through collaborative governance in the Basque Lab, multi-stakeholder approaches in Sweden, or cross-sectoral collaboration in Spain, involving diverse stakeholders is crucial for developing effective and sustainable soil health solutions. Secondly, the integration of traditional and modern practices is a common theme, particularly in the Greek and Italian Labs, where heritage conservation and economic diversification are key objectives. Additionally, the use of precision agriculture and technological innovation is a shared strategy, as seen in the Bulgarian and Basque Labs, highlighting the role of technology in addressing soil health challenges.

Building on these insights, the report lays the groundwork for transforming each Living Lab into a Mission Soil Living Lab. These labs will serve as user-centered, place-based, and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, involving multiple partners such as land managers, scientists, citizens, businesses, and local authorities. The goal is to co-design, test, monitor, and evaluate soil health solutions in real-life settings, ensuring they are practical and locally accepted. To achieve this, the report outlines initial recommendations for co-creation and stakeholder engagement activities for each living lab. These findings will guide the Living Labs in developing tailored methodologies that align with their unique objectives and stages of development. A series of co-creation sessions is planned, involving high-interest and high-influence stakeholders. These sessions will refine soil health solutions, assess progress, and share successful strategies with a broader audience to ensure the sustainability of the project. Thus, effective communication will be crucial, with tailored strategies for different stakeholder groups and regular updates to foster knowledge sharing. By integrating scientific and practical expertise, the Living Labs will not only develop sustainable solutions but also facilitate broader implementation and knowledge transfer, ensuring long-term success and impact.

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Appendix

Annex I. Stakeholder Mapping Excel Survey

#	Why do we ask for this?	What do we expect as an answer?
LL location	This way we know which LL the entry is about. It also allows us to combine the Excel files of the individual LLs in the end.	Simply select your location from the drop-down menu for each row that you start filling out.
Author (Your name)	This step allows for transparency and accountability. It also makes your job easier in case multiple colleagues are working on the same file.	Please write your first and last name into this cell.
Stakeholder Organisation	These are the organisation names of the stakeholders relevant for your LL.	Simply write their name in here. If your stakeholder is an individual, simply leave the cell blank and use the next column.
Stakeholder Name	These are the names of the contact persons relevant for your LL.	Simply write the name of an individual here. If you have indicated an organisation, we assume that this person will be your contact at the organisation.
Website of organisation AND/OR LinkedIn Profile of contact	This will help us to learn about the stakeholder, and save time when we do additional analysis.	You can just paste the link into this cell.
What is Your relationship with the stakeholder?	Knowing your relationship provides us with a better understanding of what may be needed for the recruitment of relevant stakeholders.	You can simply select from the drop-down menu.
Type	The type informs us which sector of the local socio-environmental system the actor is mostly active in.	You can select from the drop-down menu. The type was chosen to match the PESTLE categories of the baseline analysis. It only serves as a general category.
Please describe the organisation's main fields of work/tasks/activities.	This brief explanation will give us a detailed idea of the kind of work of this stakeholder.	Please briefly but clearly describe what this stakeholder does, especially in relation to the LL area.
Are they already dedicated to / engaged in the topic of soil health in the LL location?	This column helps us in the analysis of the level of interest of the stakeholder, which is relevant for our analytical framework.	Please select from the drop-down menu. A dedicated or engaged actor is one that is actively working on or concerned with the matter of soil health.
How would you rate their position towards the iCOSHELLS objectives.	This column helps us in the analysis of the relevance of the stakeholder, as one of our analytical frameworks requires this information.	Please select from the drop-down menu to the best of your knowledge.

Which barriers or challenges does the stakeholder face in regard to soil health?	Knowing of their (potential) challenges and barriers will help us understanding the stakeholders' interests in participation, their potential concerns, role in the project, and more.	Please briefly but clearly describe them to the best of your knowledge. We are aware that you may only have small amounts of knowledge about the stakeholder, yet we trust your judgement.
What opportunities do healthy soils provide to the stakeholder?	Knowing of their (potential) benefits from healthy soils will help us understanding the stakeholders' interests in participation, their potential motivations, their role, and more.	Please briefly but clearly describe them to the best of your knowledge. We are aware that you may only have small amounts of knowledge about the stakeholder, we trust your judgement.
Power - How would you rate the stakeholder's ability to influence soil health in the living labs?	This column helps us directly in the analysis of the power of the stakeholder, as this is relevant for our analysis.	Please choose a whole number from 0 to 4. (0 = no power, 4 = very high power) Here, we refer to the power a stakeholder has to influence soil health outcomes in the LL.
Please explain the power of the stakeholder.	Your explanations will greatly improve our understanding of the local context and the stakeholders' power. It will also help us to understand how you interpreted interest in this context.	Please briefly but clearly describe them to the best of your knowledge. We are aware that you may only have small amounts of knowledge about the stakeholder, we trust your judgement.
Interest - How important is the issue of soil health in this area to the stakeholder?	This column helps us in the analysis of the interest of the stakeholder, as this is relevant for our analysis.	Please choose a whole number from 0 to 4. (0 = no importance, 4 = very important)
Please explain the interest of the stakeholder.	Your explanations will greatly improve our understanding of the local context and the stakeholders' interest. It will also help us to understand how you interpreted interest in this context.	Please briefly but clearly describe them to the best of your knowledge. We are aware that you may only have small amounts of knowledge about the stakeholder, we trust your judgement.
How affected is the stakeholder by the outcomes of the living lab?	This column helps us in the analysis of the interest of the stakeholder, as this is relevant for our analysis.	Please choose a whole number from 0 to 4. (0 = not affected at all, 4 = very affected)
How is the stakeholder affected by the outcomes of the LL?	Your explanations will greatly improve our understanding of the local context and the stakeholders' relevance. It can also help us to figure out how to empower the stakeholder.	Please briefly but clearly describe them to the best of your knowledge. We are aware that you may only have small amounts of knowledge about the stakeholder, we trust your judgement.
How important do you consider their participation in the LL?	This column helps us in the analysis of the relevance of the stakeholder, as this is relevant for our analysis.	Please choose a whole number from 0 to 4. (0 = not important at all, 4 = very important)
Why do you consider them as an important actor / stakeholder?	Your explanations will greatly improve our understanding the stakeholders' relevance. It will also help us to understand how you interpreted their importance in this context.	Please briefly but clearly describe them to the best of your knowledge. We are aware that you may only have small amounts of knowledge about the stakeholder, we trust your judgement.

Annex II. Survey for LL Baseline Analysis

Survey for LL Baseline Analysis

To ensure a thorough understanding of the Living Labs (LLs) local ecosystems, we kindly ask for your participation in completing the following questions about relevant **political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental** aspects as well as the **status quo of your living lab**.

Your input is crucial and will **play a significant** role in developing a holistic perspective of the LLs environment.

- Please answer all questions **specifically for your LL location** (not for soil health in general)
- Please try to answer in an **easy-to-understand** manner
- If possible, **provide sources** to support your answers. Simply pasting the **links** to the sources is sufficient.
- We know that each LL includes multiple different sites. If possible, please answer the questions in a way that is generally true to all sites. If some sites stand out, please mention it and describe how they are different.

Jump to sections of the baseline questionnaire using these links:

1. General	2
2. Political factors	3
3. Economic factors	4
4. Social factors	5
5. Technological factors:.....	6
6. Legal factors	7
7. Environmental Factors.....	8
8. Status Quo of LL planning.....	10
9. Stakeholder and Community Engagement.....	11
10. Other	13

Your name:	Your affiliation:	Your living lab:
XX	XX	XX

1. General

Please rate the following aspects for your LL location.

Description	Rating										
	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	+5
1. The local political support for soil health in the LL location. +5 = political efforts strongly support the restoration/protection of soil health -5 = political efforts strongly oppose the restoration/protection of soil health											
2. Economic incentives to improve soil health in the LL location. +5 = economic incentives strongly support the restoration/protection of soil health -5 = economic incentives strongly oppose the restoration/protection of soil health											
3. The support for soil health interventions shown by local civic society in the LL location. +5 = civic engagement strongly supports the restoration/protection of soil health -5 = civic engagement strongly opposes the restoration/protection of soil health											
4. The impact of current technologies on soil health in LL location. +5 = technologies currently used have a strong positive effect on soil health -5 = technologies currently used have a strong negative effect on soil health											
5. The legal and regulatory obligations for key stakeholders to improve soil health in LL location. +5 = Laws & regulations strongly support the restoration/protection of soil health -5 = Laws & regulations strongly oppose the restoration/protection of soil health											
6. The current average level of soil health across the LL sites. +5 = soils are currently completely healthy -5 = soils are currently completely unhealthy											

2. Political factors

Please answer following questions on political factors influencing soil health **in your LL**.

<p>1. Which local, regional, national, and/or European political factors influence the state of soil health in the LL location? Think of any form of political support that the LL location has received, policies & regulations that affect soil health in the LL, political discourses that shape land use etc.</p> <p>Briefly describe political factors with positive impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>Briefly describe political factors with negative impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>Briefly describe political factors with neutral or mixed impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
<p>2. How does soil health in the LL location affect local, regional, national and/or European politics? Think of the impact of soil degradation (e.g., reduced land productivity, desertification, land quality issues etc.) and its impact on politics, or how soil health achievements might be used for political purposes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • •
<p>Please paste links to relevant documents below, or attach them in your e-mail response. These documents are highly valuable for the baseline analysis and we are thankful for any contributions. Pasting links is sufficient. You do not need to describe the documents.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • •

3. Economic factors

Please answer following questions on economic factors influencing soil health **in your LL**.

<p>1. Which are the major economic activities that influence the state of soil health in the LL location? Think about how the soil health is impacted by the economic activity.</p> <p>Briefly describe major economic activities with positive impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>Briefly describe major economic activities with negative impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>Briefly describe major economic activities with neutral or mixed impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
<p>2. How are economic activities affected by soil health in the LL location? Think of how the soil health degradation may lead to risks and inefficiencies in economic processes. It may also help to think of which economic processes depend on soil health.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • •
<p>Please paste links to relevant documents below, or attach them in your e-mail response. These documents are highly valuable for the baseline analysis and we are thankful for any contributions. Pasting links is sufficient. You do not need to describe the documents.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • •

4. Social factors

Please answer following questions on social factors influencing soil health **in your LL**.

<p>1. How do local communities influence the state of soil health In the LL locations? Think of ways how local groups may impact the soil health. Perhaps there are groups, individuals, or organizations, which are engaged in activities around soil health, or engage in activities that negatively impact soil health. Please also consider informal social norms that might contribute or negatively affect soil health.</p>
<p>Briefly describe social/ community actions with positive impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>Briefly describe social/ community actions with negative impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>Briefly describe social/ community actions with neutral/ mixed impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
<p>2. How are local communities affected by the state of soil health in the LL location? Think of safety, health, jobs, and other elements that enable a good life.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • •
<p>Please paste links to relevant documents below, or attach them in your e-mail response.</p> <p>These documents are highly valuable for the baseline analysis and we are thankful for any contributions. Pasting links is sufficient. You do not need to describe the documents.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • •

5. Technological factors:

Please answer following questions on technological factors influencing soil health **in your LL**.

Please note that in our analysis “technological” refers to more than just electronics and machines.

In our analysis, technological factors include several aspects, e.g.:

- **Biological:** Using biological mechanisms to work the soil, including planting special crops, working with animals, bacteria, insects.
- **Chemical:** Chemical and biochemical substances and mechanisms that are applied on the land, such as fertilizers, pesticides and herbicides of artificial or natural origin.
- **Electric / Electronic:** From small devices to large machines.
- **Mechanical and hydraulics:** From small devices to large machines.
- **Skilled practices:** Labor-based practices on soil that require specialized knowledge or training.

<p>1. Which technologies are currently used in the LL location and how do they impact soil health?</p> <p>Please consider that technologies refer to biological, chemical, electronic, mechanical, and labor-based skilled practices in our analysis.</p> <p>Briefly describe technologies with a positive impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>Briefly describe technologies with a negative impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>Briefly describe technologies with a neutral or mixed impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
<p>2. Will the improvement of soil health in the LL location require the deployment of more or novel technologies? Which technologies might be useful?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
<p>Please paste links to relevant documents below, or attach them in your e-mail response.</p> <p>These documents are highly valuable for the baseline analysis and we are thankful for any contributions. Pasting links is sufficient. You do not need to describe the documents.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • •

6. Legal factors

Please answer following questions on legal factors influencing soil health **in your LL**.

<p>1. What are the main legal and regulatory frameworks governing soil health in the LL location? Think of all policies, laws, regulations, taxes, etc. that have an impact on how soils are treated in the LL location. If available, please include links to the mentioned documents.</p> <p>Local level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>Regional / state level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>National level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>European level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
<p>2. What are the main benefits of existing laws and regulations for soil health? You may include both, criticisms of you or other stakeholders on the regulation in the LL location, or in a more general sense.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • • •
<p>3. What are the main criticisms of existing laws and regulations regarding soil health and protection? You may include both, criticisms of you or other stakeholders on the regulation in the LL location, or in a more general sense.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • •

•
<p>Please paste links to relevant documents below, or attach them in your e-mail response.</p> <p>These documents are highly valuable for the baseline analysis and we are thankful for any contributions. Pasting links is sufficient. You do not need to describe the documents.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • •

7. Environmental Factors

Please answer following questions on environmental factors influencing soil health **in your LL**.

<p>1. Which environmental factors influence the state of soil health in the LL location? Think about environmental factors like air quality, climate, floods, water quality, soil organisms etc. that exist in your LL locations.</p>
<p>Briefly describe major environmental factors with a positive impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>Briefly describe major environmental factors with a negative impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>Briefly describe major environmental factors with a neutral or mixed impact on soil health:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
<p>2. How are climate change, biodiversity loss, and other future environmental developments expected to impact the state of soil health in the LL location? Consider how likely environmental developments like climate change, biodiversity loss etc. increase or decrease the current effects on soil health in the LL location. For instance, changing rainfall patterns may have an effect on soil health in the future.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • •

•
<p>3. How is the environment affected by the state of soil health in the LL location? Think of the consequences of the soil degradation to environmental functions (cooling, filtering air, absorbing rainfall, ...), the biodiversity in flora and fauna, and other environmental consequences.</p>
• • • • • •
<p>Please paste links to relevant documents below, or attach them in your e-mail response.</p> <p>These documents are highly valuable for the baseline analysis and we are thankful for any contributions. Pasting links is sufficient. You do not need to describe the documents.</p>
• • • •

8. Status Quo of LL planning

In each LL location, solutions to restore or protect soil health will be tested. We aim to gain an overview of where each LL is currently standing in terms of identifying challenges & solutions.

We will consider the information you presented during the kick-off meeting in Gothenburg about your living lab. Please provide additional information below.

<p>1. Which soil health challenges would you like to address in the LL experiments? Please elaborate which soil health challenges or soil health objectives you would like to focus on. Feel open to communicate if you have not fully decided on this.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
<p>2. Which solutions to protect or restore soil health could you test in the LL experiments? Feel open to communicate if you have not explored any ideas yet. It is not necessary at this stage of the project to have fixed ideas. It can even be beneficial for the co-creative processes to still be very open.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • • <p>How far have you progressed in terms of planning on these ideas? Are these simply a general selection of potential solutions, or have you already decided on them and made concrete steps in the planning for their implementation? Please elaborate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
<p>3. Which skills or capacities are required to develop the LLs? Think of technical skills, communication skills, management skills, skills to engage stakeholders, capacities to host events, etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
<p>4. In each LL, a series of co-creation sessions with relevant stakeholders is planned. What do you hope to achieve with the co-creation sessions? What would you use them for? Think of whether the co-creation sessions would be useful to develop new solutions, select solutions, further develop solutions, plan the implementation of solutions etc. Maybe you already have concrete ideas of questions to discuss in the sessions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • •

9. Stakeholder and Community Engagement

<p>1. How are political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental stakeholders <u>currently</u> engaged in protecting or restoring soil health in your LL location? Think about which stakeholders currently decide on how the soil is used, in how far other stakeholders are consulted or involved in decision-making, who is informed about soil health in the LL location etc.</p> <p>2. Why is it generally important to engage each stakeholder group in the LL? Think about how the stakeholder group can support or hinder the LL, negative consequences that might arise when the stakeholder group is not involved, what each stakeholder group can influence in the LL.</p> <p>3. In your opinion, which benefits might each stakeholder group have from participating in the iCOSHells project? Think about economic benefits, reputational benefits, and how LL contributes to the objectives of each stakeholder group.</p>
<p><u>Political stakeholders</u></p> <p>How do you currently involve political stakeholders in your LL?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • <p>Why is it generally important to engage political stakeholders in the LL?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>How might political stakeholders benefit from participating in the LL?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
<p><u>Economic stakeholders</u></p> <p>How do you currently involve economic stakeholders in your LL?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • <p>Why is it generally important to engage economic stakeholders in the LL?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • <p>How might economic stakeholders benefit from participating in the LL?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •

<p><u>Social stakeholders</u></p> <p>How do you currently involve social stakeholders (e.g. local communities) in your LL?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Why is it generally important to engage social stakeholders in the LL?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>How might social stakeholders benefit from participating in the LL?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p><u>Technological stakeholders</u></p> <p>How do you currently involve technological stakeholders in your LL?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Why is it generally important to engage technological stakeholders in the LL?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>How might technological stakeholders benefit from participating in the LL?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p><u>Legal stakeholders</u></p> <p>How do you currently involve legal stakeholders (e.g. lawyers, local authorities) in your LL?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Why is it generally important to engage legal stakeholders in the LL?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>How might legal stakeholders benefit from participating in the LL?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p>

Environmental stakeholders

How do you currently involve environmental stakeholders in your LL?

-
-

Why is it generally important to engage environmental stakeholders in the LL?

-
-
-

How might environmental stakeholders benefit from participating in the LL?

-
-
-

10. Other

Please feel free to share any additional information that you believe is important for us to understand the status quo of your LL and relevant political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental influences on soil health in your LL location.

-
-
-

Thank you for your valuable input!

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